

Rhythmic and melodic analysis of the Hymn to Nikkal, Rig Veda, and the poetry of Sappho and Alcaeus

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This report provides a comprehensive analysis of rhythmic and melodic accent patterns in the Rig Veda, the Hymn to Nikkal, and the poetry of Sappho and Alcaeus. It is integral part of my research that discusses these topics.

Hymn to Nikkal

Hymn structure

To evaluate the frequency of the openings and cadences, the hymn has been split in five parts, composed of 5, 7, 7, 8, and 7 dyads. This division is not crucial towards the comparison with the Rig Veda, as it can be demonstrated that even if other divisions are applied, the conclusions remain the same.

Position length and notation of rhythm in this document

To generate a metric of comparison with the Rig Veda, we distinguish only long and short syllables or notes, as the Rig Veda has no way of denoting extra long syllables. In the original score from Ugarit I = do = short syllable. II = DOO = long syllable. III = DOO, IIII = DOOO: longer syllables, potentially with caesura. To encode the rhythm towards running a computer analysis we utilize the convenient symbols:

I=long syllables,
c= short syllables,
(=start of an opening,
)=end of a cadence.

The rhythms extracted from the hymn

In this notation style, the five parts and two cadences are as follows:

- Part 1. Iclcl , followed by “uštamare” — prelude
- Part 2. Iclllcl — opening
- Part 3. Iccclcll or ccclcll — first cadence
- Part 4. ccclclcl— opening or a variation blending the first and final cadences
- Part 5. Illclcl — final cadence

Melody and notation of melody in this document

To generate a metric plus melodic line comparison, we use the following notation:

C, L, 1 = accented syllables
c, l, 0 = unaccented syllables

The music extracted from the hymn

In this notation style, the five parts and two cadences are as follows:

- Part 1. LcLcL, 10101 followed by “uštamare” — prelude
- Part 2. lclLcL, 0001001 — opening
- Part 3. lCclclL, 0100001 or ccclcll — first cadence
- Part 4. cCcLcLcL, 01010101 — opening or a variation blending the first and last cadence
- Part 5. lllLcLcL, 0010101 — final cadence

Cadence analysis in the metrically restored text

Here we utilize the metrically restored text by Van Nooten & Holland, 1994, available online from UT Austin (Thomson, Slocum, 2025). We perform the analysis on each pada (half-line). Padas are around three to four words in length. However, when we create the corpus of 1000 permutations, we make sure each pada is changed, and not left unchanged. Specifically, the last word is never left unchanged.

Short and long syllables ratios:

Real Rig Veda per-book stats:

Book	Lines	Long	Short	Ratio
1	7740	45174	32958	1.371
2	1694	10589	7932	1.335
3	2349	14394	10184	1.413
4	2247	13470	9820	1.372
5	2854	16095	12014	1.340
6	2916	17332	12654	1.370
7	3190	19914	14105	1.412
8	5969	30050	22287	1.348
9	3745	19722	15292	1.290
10	6984	41400	30756	1.346

Total lines processed: 39688

Overall Real: Lines=39688, Long=228140, Short=168002, Ratio=1.358

Percentile of real ratio within permutations:

Book	RealRatio	#Perms	Percentile
1	1.371	999	100.0
2	1.335	999	100.0
3	1.413	999	100.0
4	1.372	999	100.0
5	1.340	999	100.0

6	1.370	999	100.0
7	1.412	999	100.0
8	1.348	999	100.0
9	1.290	999	100.0
10	1.346	999	100.0

Overall: RealRatio=1.358, #Perms=999, Percentile=100.0

Overall permutations syllable counts:

Long → min=225214, max=225785, median=225479.0

Short → min=170357, max=170928, median=170663.0

Per-book permutations syllable counts:

Book	Long (min max med)	Short (min max med)
1	44527 44753 44647.5	33379 33605 33484.5
2	10447 10568 10505.0	7953 8074 8016.0
3	14203 14331 14270.0	10247 10375 10308.0
4	13186 13319 13249.0	9971 10104 10041.0
5	15849 15968 15910.0	12141 12260 12199.0
6	17107 17232 17165.0	12754 12879 12821.0
7	19649 19801 19727.0	14218 14370 14292.0
8	29441 29610 29526.0	22727 22896 22811.0
9	19330 19476 19402.0	15538 15684 15612.0
10	40974 41190 41080.0	30966 31182 31076.0

Rhythm alone

Total distinct 7-syllable cadences: 127

Top 100 most frequent 7-syllable patterns (original vs. max permuted counts):

1. Pattern=lllclcl, OrigCount=3803, MaxPermCount=444
2. Pattern=lccclll, OrigCount=3673, MaxPermCount=627
3. Pattern=cllclcl, OrigCount=3206, MaxPermCount=609
4. Pattern=ccllcll, OrigCount=3053, MaxPermCount=374
5. Pattern=cclclcl, OrigCount=3041, MaxPermCount=462
6. Pattern=lclclcl, OrigCount=3008, MaxPermCount=1060
7. Pattern=ccclcll, OrigCount=2356, MaxPermCount=339
8. Pattern=lcllcll, OrigCount=1337, MaxPermCount=749
9. Pattern=lccclcl, OrigCount=1190, MaxPermCount=306
10. Pattern=ccllclc, OrigCount=1074, MaxPermCount=254
11. Pattern=clclcll, OrigCount=1024, MaxPermCount=1154
12. Pattern=llccclcl, OrigCount=1014, MaxPermCount=461
13. Pattern=lllclcc, OrigCount=1002, MaxPermCount=148
14. Pattern=cllclcc, OrigCount=861, MaxPermCount=156
15. Pattern=ccclclc, OrigCount=768, MaxPermCount=162
16. Pattern=cclclcc, OrigCount=734, MaxPermCount=98
17. Pattern=lclclcc, OrigCount=686, MaxPermCount=271
18. Pattern=clccclcl, OrigCount=579, MaxPermCount=493

19. Pattern=llclcll, OrigCount=527, MaxPermCount=684
20. Pattern=lcllclc, OrigCount=522, MaxPermCount=408
21. Pattern=lccccl, OrigCount=515, MaxPermCount=358
22. Pattern=llccclcc, OrigCount=319, MaxPermCount=116
23. Pattern=llllcll, OrigCount=316, MaxPermCount=335
24. Pattern=clclclc, OrigCount=295, MaxPermCount=670
25. Pattern=clllcll, OrigCount=273, MaxPermCount=634
26. Pattern=clccclcc, OrigCount=190, MaxPermCount=99
27. Pattern=lllllcl, OrigCount=185, MaxPermCount=335
28. Pattern=lclllcl, OrigCount=165, MaxPermCount=683
29. Pattern=lclcccl, OrigCount=160, MaxPermCount=611
30. Pattern=cclllll, OrigCount=147, MaxPermCount=385
31. Pattern=lllcccl, OrigCount=140, MaxPermCount=369
32. Pattern=llclclc, OrigCount=140, MaxPermCount=485
33. Pattern=cllllcl, OrigCount=139, MaxPermCount=501
34. Pattern=lccllll, OrigCount=137, MaxPermCount=600
35. Pattern=lcccclcc, OrigCount=119, MaxPermCount=81
36. Pattern=cllcccl, OrigCount=111, MaxPermCount=328
37. Pattern=lcllccl, OrigCount=95, MaxPermCount=958
38. Pattern=cclllcl, OrigCount=88, MaxPermCount=356
39. Pattern=llllclc, OrigCount=87, MaxPermCount=286
40. Pattern=lclccll, OrigCount=84, MaxPermCount=812
41. Pattern=lccccll, OrigCount=84, MaxPermCount=273
42. Pattern=llllccl, OrigCount=83, MaxPermCount=580
43. Pattern=cccllll, OrigCount=83, MaxPermCount=314
44. Pattern=lclllll, OrigCount=79, MaxPermCount=734
45. Pattern=cclccll, OrigCount=75, MaxPermCount=300
46. Pattern=ccllccl, OrigCount=73, MaxPermCount=363
47. Pattern=lllccll, OrigCount=63, MaxPermCount=363
48. Pattern=lcclccl, OrigCount=62, MaxPermCount=379
49. Pattern=clccccl, OrigCount=61, MaxPermCount=408
50. Pattern=cclcccl, OrigCount=60, MaxPermCount=220
51. Pattern=lllccll, OrigCount=60, MaxPermCount=409
52. Pattern=cccclcl, OrigCount=57, MaxPermCount=158
53. Pattern=lcclllc, OrigCount=56, MaxPermCount=305
54. Pattern=lllllll, OrigCount=56, MaxPermCount=289
55. Pattern=cccccll, OrigCount=56, MaxPermCount=108
56. Pattern=clllclc, OrigCount=51, MaxPermCount=450
57. Pattern=cllccll, OrigCount=50, MaxPermCount=456
58. Pattern=llcccll, OrigCount=46, MaxPermCount=272
59. Pattern=lcllllc, OrigCount=43, MaxPermCount=403
60. Pattern=llcllll, OrigCount=41, MaxPermCount=566
61. Pattern=lllllcc, OrigCount=41, MaxPermCount=113
62. Pattern=lclllcc, OrigCount=41, MaxPermCount=196
63. Pattern=llclccl, OrigCount=40, MaxPermCount=620
64. Pattern=lclclll, OrigCount=40, MaxPermCount=1320
65. Pattern=ccllllc, OrigCount=40, MaxPermCount=257
66. Pattern=llcllcl, OrigCount=39, MaxPermCount=606
67. Pattern=lllcccc, OrigCount=37, MaxPermCount=120

68. Pattern=clllccl, OrigCount=35, MaxPermCount=563
69. Pattern=lllccll, OrigCount=34, MaxPermCount=295
70. Pattern=llcclll, OrigCount=34, MaxPermCount=446
71. Pattern=clclccl, OrigCount=31, MaxPermCount=823
72. Pattern=lccllcl, OrigCount=29, MaxPermCount=517
73. Pattern=cllclll, OrigCount=29, MaxPermCount=585
74. Pattern=lllcclc, OrigCount=29, MaxPermCount=386
75. Pattern=cllllll, OrigCount=28, MaxPermCount=565
76. Pattern=lclcclc, OrigCount=27, MaxPermCount=450
77. Pattern=lclcccc, OrigCount=27, MaxPermCount=168
78. Pattern=cllcccc, OrigCount=27, MaxPermCount=91
79. Pattern=clcllcl, OrigCount=27, MaxPermCount=804
80. Pattern=clcllll, OrigCount=26, MaxPermCount=1131
81. Pattern=cllllcc, OrigCount=25, MaxPermCount=158
82. Pattern=ccclccl, OrigCount=25, MaxPermCount=181
83. Pattern=llllllc, OrigCount=24, MaxPermCount=193
84. Pattern=ccclllc, OrigCount=22, MaxPermCount=191
85. Pattern=cclllcc, OrigCount=21, MaxPermCount=92
86. Pattern=lclcllc, OrigCount=21, MaxPermCount=520
87. Pattern=cclcccc, OrigCount=19, MaxPermCount=53
88. Pattern=ccllccc, OrigCount=19, MaxPermCount=76
89. Pattern=lcccclc, OrigCount=18, MaxPermCount=147
90. Pattern=lcllccc, OrigCount=18, MaxPermCount=169
91. Pattern=llccccl, OrigCount=15, MaxPermCount=206
92. Pattern=cccclcc, OrigCount=15, MaxPermCount=38
93. Pattern=cclcclc, OrigCount=15, MaxPermCount=169
94. Pattern=llclllc, OrigCount=14, MaxPermCount=444
95. Pattern=llllccc, OrigCount=14, MaxPermCount=143
96. Pattern=cclclll, OrigCount=13, MaxPermCount=594
97. Pattern=llccclc, OrigCount=13, MaxPermCount=255
98. Pattern=llclccc, OrigCount=12, MaxPermCount=199
99. Pattern=clccccl, OrigCount=12, MaxPermCount=282
100. Pattern=lcccccl, OrigCount=12, MaxPermCount=143

The two cadences of the Hymn to Nikkal with book by book matching statistics in the Rig Veda

Cadence	Book	Count of	RelFreq	
lllclcl	1	736	7740	0.0951
lllclcl	2	50	1694	0.0295 #the family books have low frequency
lllclcl	3	132	2349	0.0562
lllclcl	4	134	2247	0.0596
lllclcl	5	329	2854	0.1153 #only this family book is high
lllclcl	6	203	2916	0.0696
lllclcl	7	95	3190	0.0298
lllclcl	8	1182	5969	0.1980
lllclcl	9	570	3745	0.1522
lllclcl	10	372	6984	0.0533

lcclcll	1	683	7740	0.0882	
lcclcll	2	157	1694	0.0927	#the family books have high frequency
lcclcll	3	343	2349	0.1460	
lcclcll	4	381	2247	0.1696	
lcclcll	5	222	2854	0.0778	
lcclcll	6	395	2916	0.1355	
lcclcll	7	484	3190	0.1517	
lcclcll	8	74	5969	0.0124	
lcclcll	9	141	3745	0.0377	
lcclcll	10	793	6984	0.1135	

Cadence diversity of each book:

Book	TotalLines	DistinctPatterns	InverseSimpson
1	7733	113	17.543697
2	1684	74	15.132959
3	2349	83	13.543441
4	2224	88	12.649549
5	2853	104	17.772266
6	2914	110	16.140454
7	3187	90	14.839802
8	5961	108	11.232213
9	3745	96	12.828921
10	6936	119	18.394108

Cadence diversity with word accent considered, for each book:

Book	TotalLines	DistinctPatterns	InvSimpson
1	7733	1819	507.759032
2	1684	749	333.394780
3	2349	824	342.104346
4	2224	858	333.480043
5	2853	1084	493.219960
6	2914	1121	444.110669
7	3187	1029	301.259647
8	5961	1540	367.617304
9	3745	1112	359.939048
10	6936	1831	527.825156

Duplets, testing the rhythm with cadences of different length. Seven is the full length. The smaller numbers are added to demonstrate robustness.

Duplets with cadences of length 7.

Total distinct duplets: 2313
Stats min=19, max=7476, median=1001.0, mean=1447.8

Min: [cclcccc|cclcccc] -> f1=19, f2=19, uniq=19
 Median: [cllclcc|llclclc] -> f1=861, f2=140, uniq=1001
 Max: [lllclcl|lccclll] -> f1=3803, f2=3673, uniq=7476

Top 10 duplets with most matches:

Rank	Pattern (7 7)	Matches
1.	[lllclcl lccclll]	7476
2.	[cllclcl lllclcl]	7009
3.	[lccclll cllclcl]	6879
4.	[ccllcll lllclcl]	6856
5.	[lllclcl cclclcl]	6844
6.	[lclclcl lllclcl]	6811
7.	[ccllcll lccclll]	6726
8.	[cclclcl lccclll]	6714
9.	[lclclcl lccclll]	6681
10.	[cllclcl ccllcll]	6259
11.	[cllclcl cclclcl]	6247
12.	[cllclcl lclclcl]	6214s
13.	[cccclll lllclcl]	6159
14.	[ccllcll cclclcl]	6094
15.	[ccllcll lclclcl]	6061
16.	[cclclcl lclclcl]	6049
17.	[lccclll cccclll]	6029
18.	[cccclll cllclcl]	5562
19.	[ccllcll cccclll]	5409
20.	[cclclcl cccclll]	5397
21.	[cccclll lclclcl]	5364
22.	[lcllcll lllclcl]	5140
23.	[lcllcll lccclll]	5010
24.	[lccclcl lllclcl]	4993
25.	[ccllclc lllclcl]	4877
26.	[lccclll lccclcl]	4863
27.	[lllclcl clclcll]	4827
28.	[lllclcl llcccll]	4817
29.	[lllclcc lllclcl]	4805
30.	[lccclll ccllclc]	4747
31.	[lccclll clclcll]	4697
32.	[llcccll lccclll]	4687
33.	[lllclcc lccclll]	4675
34.	[cllclcc lllclcl]	4664
35.	[cllclcl lcllcll]	4543
36.	[cclclcc lllclcl]	4537
37.	[cllclcc lccclll]	4534
38.	[lllclcl lclclcc]	4489
39.	[lccclll cccclcl]	4441
40.	[cclclcc lccclll]	4407
41.	[cllclcl lccclcl]	4396
42.	[lcllcll ccllcll]	4390
43.	[lllclcl clcccll]	4382

44.	[ccclclcl lcllclll]	4378
45.	[lcclclll lclclcc]	4359
46.	[lcllclll lclclcl]	4345
47.	[lllclclcl llclclll]	4330
48.	[lcllclcl lllclcl]	4325
49.	[lllclclcl lccclcl]	4318
50.	[cllclclcl ccllclcl]	4280
51.	[lcclclll clccclcl]	4252
52.	[lcclclcl ccllclll]	4243
53.	[ccclclcl lccclcl]	4231
54.	[clclclll cllclcl]	4230
55.	[llccclcl cllclcl]	4220
56.	[lllclclcc cllclcl]	4208
57.	[llclclll lccclll]	4200
58.	[lcclclcl lclclcl]	4198
59.	[lcllclcl lccclll]	4195
60.	[lcclclll lccclcl]	4188
61.	[ccllclcl ccllclll]	4127
62.	[lllclclcl llccclcc]	4122
63.	[llllclll lllclcl]	4119
64.	[ccllclcl cclclcl]	4115
65.	[clclclcl lllclcl]	4098
66.	[lclclclcl ccllclcl]	4082
67.	[ccllclll clclclll]	4077
68.	[lllclclcl clllclll]	4076
69.	[cllclclcc cllclcl]	4067
70.	[ccllclll llccclcl]	4067
71.	[ccclclcl clclclll]	4065
72.	[ccclclcl llccclcl]	4055
73.	[ccllclll lllclcc]	4055
74.	[lllclclcc cclclcl]	4043
75.	[clclclll lclclcl]	4032
76.	[llccclcl lclclcl]	4022
77.	[lclclclcl lllclcc]	4010
78.	[lllclclcl clccclcc]	3993
79.	[lcclclll llllclll]	3989
80.	[lllclclcl lllllcl]	3988
81.	[cllclclcl cccclcl]	3974
82.	[lcllllcl lllclcl]	3968
83.	[clclclcl lccclll]	3968
84.	[lllclclcl lclcccl]	3963
85.	[lllclclcl ccllllll]	3950
86.	[lcclclll clllclll]	3946
87.	[lllclclcl lllcccl]	3943
88.	[lllclclcl llclclcl]	3943
89.	[cllllclcl lllclcl]	3942
90.	[cllclclcl cclclcc]	3940
91.	[lcclllll lllclcl]	3940
92.	[lccclcc lllclcl]	3922

- 93. [lllclcl|cllcccl] 3914
- 94. [ccllcll|cllclcc] 3914
- 95. [cclclcl|cllclcc] 3902
- 96. [lcllcccl|lllclcl] 3898
- 97. [lclclcc|cllclcl] 3892
- 98. [cclllcl|lllclcl] 3891
- 99. [lllclcl|llllclc] 3890
- 100. [lllclcl|lclccll] 3887

Duplets with cadences of length 6.

Total distinct duplets: 1036
 Stats min=24, max=13060, median=964.5, mean=2109.9

Min: [clclll|clclll] -> f1=24, f2=24, uniq=24
 Median: [ccclcl|lclclc] -> f1=572, f2=439, uniq=1011
 Max: [llclcl|clclcl] -> f1=7010, f2=6050, uniq=13060

Top 10 duplets with most matches:

Rank	Pattern (6 6)	Matches
1.	[llclcl clclcl]	13060
2.	[llclcl cclcll]	13039
3.	[clclcl cclcll]	12079
4.	[llclcl cllcll]	11401
5.	[cllcll clclcl]	10441
6.	[cllcll cclcll]	10420
7.	[llclcl cclclc]	8968
8.	[llclcc llclcl]	8874
9.	[cllclc llclcl]	8606
10.	[lccclcl llclcl]	8603
11.	[llclcl lclcll]	8562
12.	[llclcl clclcc]	8430
13.	[clclcl cclclc]	8008
14.	[cclcll cclclc]	7987
15.	[clclcl llclcc]	7914
16.	[cclcll llclcc]	7893
17.	[clclcl cllclc]	7646
18.	[clclcl lccclcl]	7643
19.	[cllclc cclcll]	7625
20.	[lccclcl cclcll]	7622
21.	[llclcl lllcll]	7603
22.	[lclcll clclcl]	7602
23.	[ccclcl llclcl]	7582
24.	[lclcll cclcll]	7581
25.	[llclcl lccclcc]	7519
26.	[clclcc clclcl]	7470
27.	[llclcl lclclc]	7449
28.	[clclcc cclcll]	7449

29.	[llclcl llllcl]	7335
30.	[clllcl llclcl]	7263
31.	[llclcl llcccl]	7261
32.	[clllll llclcl]	7236
33.	[llclcl ccllll]	7231
34.	[clcccl llclcl]	7230
35.	[llclcl cllcccl]	7178
36.	[clcccl llclcl]	7169
37.	[llclcl ccccll]	7150
38.	[lllclcl llclcl]	7149
39.	[ccclcc llclcl]	7144
40.	[lllcccl llclcl]	7128
41.	[llcccl llclcl]	7124
42.	[llclcl lcccll]	7117
43.	[llclcl llclll]	7099
44.	[ccclcc llclcl]	7097
45.	[llclcl llllll]	7094
46.	[cllllc llclcl]	7093
47.	[llclcl cclllc]	7088
48.	[lclcccl llclcl]	7081
49.	[lcllll llclcl]	7077
50.	[llclcl llllcc]	7076
51.	[lcllcl llclcl]	7076
52.	[llcccc llclcl]	7074
53.	[llclcl clllcc]	7072
54.	[llclcl clclll]	7063
55.	[clcccc llclcl]	7056
56.	[llcllc llclcl]	7056
57.	[lcclll llclcl]	7055
58.	[llclcl clcccl]	7052
59.	[llclcl ccllcl]	7050
60.	[cllccc llclcl]	7047
61.	[llclcl llcccl]	7047
62.	[lllllc llclcl]	7042
63.	[llclcl cccccl]	7039
64.	[lcccc llclcl]	7037
65.	[llclcl clllc]	7034
66.	[llclcl lccclc]	7033
67.	[llclcl lllccc]	7028
68.	[llclcl lclccc]	7026
69.	[llclcl cccccl]	7026
70.	[llclcl lccllc]	7023
71.	[llclcl lcccc]	7021
72.	[llclcl lcllcc]	7019
73.	[ccllcc llclcl]	7018
74.	[cccllc llclcl]	7018
75.	[llclcl ccccll]	7016
76.	[cccccc llclcl]	7015
77.	[llclcl llclcl]	7010

78.	[lllccl clclcl]	6643
79.	[ccclcl clclcl]	6622
80.	[cclcll lllccl]	6622
81.	[ccclcl cclcll]	6601
82.	[clclcl lccclcc]	6559
83.	[cclcll lccclcc]	6538
84.	[clclcl lclclc]	6489
85.	[cclcll lclclc]	6468
86.	[llllcl clclcl]	6375
87.	[llllcl cclcll]	6354
88.	[cclclc cllcll]	6349
89.	[clclcl clllcl]	6303
90.	[llcccl clclcl]	6301
91.	[clllcl cclcll]	6282
92.	[llcccl cclcll]	6280
93.	[clllll clclcl]	6276
94.	[clclcl ccllll]	6271
95.	[clclcl clcccl]	6270
96.	[cclcll clllll]	6255
97.	[cllcll llclcc]	6255
98.	[cclcll ccllll]	6250
99.	[cclcll clcccl]	6249
100.	[cllcll clclcl]	6218

Duplets with cadences of length 5.

Total distinct duplets: 403

Stats min=70, max=20645, median=956.0, mean=3056.9

Min: [lcllc|lcllc] -> f1=70, f2=70, uniq=70

Median: [lllll|cclcc] -> f1=313, f2=643, uniq=956

Max: [clcll|lclcl] -> f1=7585, f2=13060, uniq=20645

Top 10 duplets with most matches:

Rank	Pattern (5 5)	Matches
1.	[clcll lclcl]	20645
2.	[lclcl llcll]	18046
3.	[lclcl lclcc]	16344
4.	[lclcl clclc]	15457
5.	[cclcl lclcl]	15225
6.	[lclcl llclc]	14796
7.	[lclcl cclcc]	13703
8.	[lclcl lllcl]	13638
9.	[lclcl lcccl]	13531
10.	[lllll lclcl]	13373
11.	[lclcl cllll]	13355
12.	[llccl lclcl]	13346
13.	[lccll lclcl]	13333

14.	[lccl cccl]	13308
15.	[clcc lclcl]	13218
16.	[lclcl lclll]	13202
17.	[lclcl lllcc]	13188
18.	[llllc lclcl]	13177
19.	[lcccc lclcl]	13170
20.	[lclcl cllcl]	13166
21.	[lclcl clllc]	13166
22.	[lclcl lcccl]	13139
23.	[cllc lclcl]	13130
24.	[lclcl llccc]	13115
25.	[lclcl ccclc]	13112
26.	[cclll lclcl]	13111
27.	[lclcl ccccl]	13103
28.	[lclcl clccc]	13094
29.	[lclcl ccllc]	13081
30.	[lclcl cllcc]	13077
31.	[lclcl cccc]	13076
32.	[lclcl lclcl]	13060
33.	[clcll llcll]	12571
34.	[lclcc clcll]	10869
35.	[clcll clclc]	9982
36.	[cclcl clcll]	9750
37.	[llclc clcll]	9321
38.	[llcll lclcc]	8270
39.	[clcll cclcc]	8228
40.	[clcll lllcl]	8163
41.	[clcll lcccl]	8056
42.	[clcll lllll]	7898
43.	[clcll cllll]	7880
44.	[llccl clcll]	7871
45.	[clcll lcccl]	7858
46.	[cccll clcll]	7833
47.	[clcc clcll]	7743
48.	[clcll lclll]	7727
49.	[clcll lllcc]	7713
50.	[llllc clcll]	7702
51.	[lcccc clcll]	7695
52.	[clcll clllc]	7691
53.	[cllcl clcll]	7691
54.	[clcll lcccl]	7664
55.	[clcll clllc]	7655
56.	[llccc clcll]	7640
57.	[ccclc clcll]	7637
58.	[clcll cclll]	7636
59.	[clcll ccccl]	7628
60.	[clccc clcll]	7619
61.	[clcll ccllc]	7606
62.	[cllcc clcll]	7602

63.	[cccc clcll]	7601
64.	[clcll clcll]	7585
65.	[clclc llcll]	7383
66.	[llcll cclcl]	7151
67.	[llcll llclc]	6722
68.	[clclc lclcc]	5681
69.	[llcll cclcc]	5629
70.	[lllcl llcll]	5564
71.	[lcccl llcll]	5457
72.	[lclcc cclcl]	5449
73.	[lllll llcll]	5299
74.	[cllll llcll]	5281
75.	[llccl llcll]	5272
76.	[llcll lccll]	5259
77.	[llcll cccll]	5234
78.	[llcll clcc]	5144
79.	[lclll llcll]	5128
80.	[lllcc llcll]	5114
81.	[llcll llllc]	5103
82.	[llcll lcccc]	5096
83.	[llcll clllc]	5092
84.	[llcll cllcl]	5092
85.	[lcccl llcll]	5065
86.	[llcll lcllc]	5056
87.	[llcll llccc]	5041
88.	[llcll ccclc]	5038
89.	[cclll llcll]	5037
90.	[llcll ccccl]	5029
91.	[lclcc llclc]	5020
92.	[llcll clccc]	5020
93.	[ccllc llcll]	5007
94.	[llcll cllcc]	5003
95.	[cccc llcll]	5002
96.	[llcll llcll]	4986
97.	[cclcl clclc]	4562
98.	[clclc llclc]	4133
99.	[lclcc cclcc]	3927
100.	[cclcl llclc]	3901

Duplets with cadences of length 4.

Total distinct duplets: 131

Stats min=91, max=27849, median=1036.0, mean=4836.0

Min: [cllc|cllc] -> f1=91, f2=91, uniq=91

Median: [ccll|ccc]

Max: [lcll|clcl] -> f1=12572, f2=15277, uniq=27849

Top 10 duplets with most matches:

Rank	Pattern (7 8)	Matches
1.	[lc11 clcl]	27849
2.	[clcl lclc]	19411
3.	[clcc clcl]	19209
4.	[lc11 lclc]	16706
5.	[clcc lc11]	16504
6.	[clcl llcl]	15961
7.	[clcl llll]	15887
8.	[ccll clcl]	15799
9.	[clcl cccl]	15791
10.	[lccl clcl]	15721
11.	[clcl lllc]	15500
12.	[clcl clll]	15470
13.	[clcl llcc]	15422
14.	[clcl cclc]	15408
15.	[cccc clcl]	15403
16.	[cllc clcl]	15368
17.	[clcl lccc]	15367
18.	[clcl clcl]	15277
19.	[llcl lc11]	13256
20.	[llll lc11]	13182
21.	[lc11 ccll]	13094
22.	[cccl lc11]	13086
23.	[lccl lc11]	13016
24.	[lc11 lllc]	12795
25.	[clll lc11]	12765
26.	[lc11 llcc]	12717
27.	[lc11 cclc]	12703
28.	[cccc lc11]	12698
29.	[lc11 cllc]	12663
30.	[lc11 lccc]	12662
31.	[lc11 lc11]	12572
32.	[lclc clcc]	8066
33.	[llcl lclc]	4818
34.	[llll lclc]	4744
35.	[lclc ccll]	4656
36.	[lclc cccl]	4648
37.	[clcc llcl]	4616
38.	[lclc lccl]	4578
39.	[llll clcc]	4542
40.	[ccll clcc]	4454
41.	[cccl clcc]	4446
42.	[clcc lccl]	4376
43.	[lclc lllc]	4357
44.	[lclc clll]	4327
45.	[lclc llcc]	4279
46.	[cclc lclc]	4265
47.	[lclc cccc]	4260
48.	[lclc cllc]	4225

49.	[lc lc lccc]	4224
50.	[cl cc lllc]	4155
51.	[lc lc lc lc]	4134
52.	[cl ll cl cc]	4125
53.	[ll cc cl cc]	4077
54.	[cl cc cc lc]	4063
55.	[cl cc cccc]	4058
56.	[cl cc cl lc]	4023
57.	[lccc cl cc]	4022
58.	[cl cc cl cc]	3932
59.	[llll ll cl]	1294
60.	[ll cl cc ll]	1206
61.	[cc cl ll cl]	1198
62.	[cc ll ll ll]	1132
63.	[ll cl lc cl]	1128
64.	[cc cl ll ll]	1124
65.	[llll lc cl]	1054
66.	[cc ll cc cl]	1036
67.	[cc ll lc cl]	966
68.	[lc cl cc cl]	958
69.	[ll cl ll lc]	907
70.	[cl ll ll cl]	877
71.	[llll ll lc]	833
72.	[ll cc ll cl]	829
73.	[cc lc ll cl]	815
74.	[ll cl cccc]	810
75.	[llll cl ll]	803
76.	[ll cl cl lc]	775
77.	[ll cc ll ll]	755
78.	[ll lc cc ll]	745
79.	[cc lc ll ll]	741
80.	[ll lc cc cl]	737
81.	[llll cccc]	736
82.	[cc ll cl ll]	715
83.	[cc cl cl ll]	707
84.	[cl lc ll ll]	701
85.	[lccc ll ll]	700
86.	[ll cl ll cl]	684
87.	[lc cl ll lc]	667
88.	[ll cc cc ll]	667
89.	[cc cl ll cc]	659
90.	[cc lc cc ll]	653
91.	[cc ll cccc]	648
92.	[cc cl cc lc]	645
93.	[cc cl cccc]	640
94.	[cl ll lc cl]	637
95.	[cl lc cc ll]	613
96.	[cc ll lccc]	612
97.	[llll ll ll]	610

98. [cllc cccl]	605
99. [cccl lccc]	604
100. [lccl llcc]	589

Rhythm and melody

The most frequent cadences considering rhythm and accents

Total distinct 7-syllable cadences: 3826

Top 100 most frequent 7-syllable patterns (original vs. max permuted counts):

Top 100 most frequent 7-syllable patterns (original vs. max permuted counts):

1. Pattern=cclclcl|100010, OrigCount=291, MaxPermCount=28
7 positions between two cadences, exact rhythm and approximate accent pattern

2. Pattern=lcclcll|010001, OrigCount=230, MaxPermCount=43
#exact first cadence, rhythm and accent pattern

3. Pattern=cclclcl|100100, OrigCount=211, MaxPermCount=19

4. Pattern=lcclcll|010010, OrigCount=206, MaxPermCount=36

5. Pattern=cclclcl|0010010, OrigCount=195, MaxPermCount=37

6. Pattern=lllclcl|001000, OrigCount=190, MaxPermCount=13
#final cadence, exact rhythm, and compatible accent pattern

7. Pattern=ccclcll|010001, OrigCount=188, MaxPermCount=27

8. Pattern=lllclcl|010010, OrigCount=186, MaxPermCount=22

9. Pattern=cclclcl|000010, OrigCount=181, MaxPermCount=22

10. Pattern=lclclcl|010010, OrigCount=170, MaxPermCount=63

11. Pattern=ccllcll|100100, OrigCount=169, MaxPermCount=11

12. Pattern=cclclcl|0010010, OrigCount=163, MaxPermCount=26

13. Pattern=ccllcll|1000100, OrigCount=162, MaxPermCount=15

14. Pattern=lcclcll|0010001, OrigCount=159, MaxPermCount=43

15. Pattern=ccclcll|0100010, OrigCount=157, MaxPermCount=25

16. Pattern=lclclcl|0000010, OrigCount=156, MaxPermCount=59

17. Pattern=lllclcl|0010100, OrigCount=156, MaxPermCount=24

18. Pattern=lllclcl|0000100, OrigCount=153, MaxPermCount=17

19. Pattern=ccllcll|1000010, OrigCount=152, MaxPermCount=22

20. Pattern=cclclcl|0100010, OrigCount=152, MaxPermCount=31

21. Pattern=cclclcl|0000100, OrigCount=151, MaxPermCount=30

22. Pattern=lcclcll|0010100, OrigCount=149, MaxPermCount=25

23. Pattern=lllclcl|0100010, OrigCount=147, MaxPermCount=29

24. Pattern=lclclcl|0000100, OrigCount=146, MaxPermCount=31

25. Pattern=lclclcl|1000100, OrigCount=145, MaxPermCount=36

26. Pattern=lcclcll|0100100, OrigCount=145, MaxPermCount=23

27. Pattern=clclcll|0010100, OrigCount=144, MaxPermCount=44

28. Pattern=cclclcl|0100100, OrigCount=143, MaxPermCount=25

29. Pattern=cllcll|0100100, OrigCount=143, MaxPermCount=17
 30. Pattern=lllclcl|1100010, OrigCount=140, MaxPermCount=13
 31. Pattern=ccclcll|0010010, OrigCount=139, MaxPermCount=26
 32. Pattern=cllclcl|0001000, OrigCount=137, MaxPermCount=31
 33. Pattern=ccclcll|0010001, OrigCount=137, MaxPermCount=24
 34. Pattern=ccllcll|0100001, OrigCount=136, MaxPermCount=16
 35. Pattern=lcclcll|0001001, OrigCount=135, MaxPermCount=39
 36. Pattern=lllclcl|0010010, OrigCount=134, MaxPermCount=34
 37. Pattern=lclclcl|1000010, OrigCount=131, MaxPermCount=70
 38. Pattern=cclclcl|0010100, OrigCount=130, MaxPermCount=20
 39. Pattern=lcclcll|0000010, OrigCount=129, MaxPermCount=32
 40. Pattern=cllclcl|0100010, OrigCount=128, MaxPermCount=29
 41. Pattern=ccllcll|0010100, OrigCount=127, MaxPermCount=21
 42. Pattern=ccllcll|0101000, OrigCount=125, MaxPermCount=15
 43. Pattern=lcclcll|0001010, OrigCount=123, MaxPermCount=35
 44. Pattern=lllclcl|0000010, OrigCount=121, MaxPermCount=18
 45. Pattern=lllclcl|1000010, OrigCount=120, MaxPermCount=14
 46. Pattern=cllclcl|0010000, OrigCount=120, MaxPermCount=15
 47. Pattern=lcclcll|0000100, OrigCount=120, MaxPermCount=32
 48. Pattern=cllclcl|1000010, OrigCount=119, MaxPermCount=35
 49. Pattern=lllclcl|0100000, OrigCount=119, MaxPermCount=15
 50. Pattern=cllclcl|0010100, OrigCount=119, MaxPermCount=26
 51. Pattern=cllclcl|0010001, OrigCount=119, MaxPermCount=41
 52. Pattern=lcclcll|0010010, OrigCount=119, MaxPermCount=31
 53. Pattern=lcclcll|0001100, OrigCount=119, MaxPermCount=18
 54. Pattern=cclclcl|0101000, OrigCount=117, MaxPermCount=21
 55. Pattern=lllclcl|1010010, OrigCount=115, MaxPermCount=21
 56. Pattern=cclclcl|1000000, OrigCount=115, MaxPermCount=11
 57. Pattern=lllclcl|1010000, OrigCount=114, MaxPermCount=15
 58. Pattern=lclclcl|0100100, OrigCount=114, MaxPermCount=34
 59. Pattern=lllclcl|1001000, OrigCount=114, MaxPermCount=12
 60. Pattern=lcclcll|1100010, OrigCount=114, MaxPermCount=22
 61. Pattern=ccllcll|1001000, OrigCount=113, MaxPermCount=16
 62. Pattern=lcclcll|0000001, OrigCount=112, MaxPermCount=36
 63. Pattern=cclclcl|1001000, OrigCount=111, MaxPermCount=19
 64. Pattern=lclclcl|0010000, OrigCount=110, MaxPermCount=23
 65. Pattern=ccclcll|0001001, OrigCount=110, MaxPermCount=26
 66. Pattern=lcclcll|0001000, OrigCount=110, MaxPermCount=25
 67. Pattern=cclclcl|0000100, OrigCount=109, MaxPermCount=17
 68. Pattern=ccllcll|0010010, OrigCount=109, MaxPermCount=36
 69. Pattern=lllclcl|0001000, OrigCount=108, MaxPermCount=14
 70. Pattern=ccllcll|1000001, OrigCount=108, MaxPermCount=23
 71. Pattern=cllclcl|1000100, OrigCount=107, MaxPermCount=22
 72. Pattern=cllclcl|1001000, OrigCount=107, MaxPermCount=25
 73. Pattern=cllclcl|0100100, OrigCount=107, MaxPermCount=29
 74. Pattern=lllclcl|1010100, OrigCount=106, MaxPermCount=19
 75. Pattern=cclclcl|0000010, OrigCount=106, MaxPermCount=26
 76. Pattern=ccllcll|0011000, OrigCount=106, MaxPermCount=12
 77. Pattern=lcclcll|0010000, OrigCount=106, MaxPermCount=17

78. Pattern=lllclcl|1000100, OrigCount=105, MaxPermCount=14
79. Pattern=lllclcc|0010000, OrigCount=105, MaxPermCount=8
80. Pattern=lllclcl|0101000, OrigCount=104, MaxPermCount=21
81. Pattern=ccllclll|0100010, OrigCount=104, MaxPermCount=21
82. Pattern=lclclcl|0010010, OrigCount=101, MaxPermCount=56
83. Pattern=cclclcl|1000001, OrigCount=100, MaxPermCount=26
84. Pattern=cllclcl|0101000, OrigCount=99, MaxPermCount=32
85. Pattern=ccllclll|0001010, OrigCount=99, MaxPermCount=23
86. Pattern=ccclclll|0010100, OrigCount=99, MaxPermCount=17
87. Pattern=lclclcl|0010100, OrigCount=98, MaxPermCount=26
88. Pattern=lcllclll|1000100, OrigCount=97, MaxPermCount=35
89. Pattern=lcclclc|0100000, OrigCount=97, MaxPermCount=15
90. Pattern=ccllclll|0010001, OrigCount=97, MaxPermCount=34
91. Pattern=lcclclll|0001000, OrigCount=91, MaxPermCount=29
92. Pattern=ccllclll|0001000, OrigCount=90, MaxPermCount=12
93. Pattern=lclclcl|0001000, OrigCount=89, MaxPermCount=29
94. Pattern=lcclclll|0100000, OrigCount=89, MaxPermCount=10
95. Pattern=lclclcl|0100000, OrigCount=89, MaxPermCount=23
96. Pattern=cclclcl|0001000, OrigCount=89, MaxPermCount=17
97. Pattern=ccclclll|0001010, OrigCount=88, MaxPermCount=29
98. Pattern=ccclclll|0000100, OrigCount=88, MaxPermCount=12
99. Pattern=lclclcl|0010001, OrigCount=87, MaxPermCount=73
100. Pattern=cllclcl|1010010, OrigCount=87, MaxPermCount=17

First cadence, rhythm and melody matches

Original: 461/39688 match 'lCclclL)'
Perms: min=37, max=81, mean=57.86, std=6.64
Percentile: 100.0th

Original matches:

- 1.024.08c: apáde pādā prátidhātave 'kar
metric = cLlLlCclcll
- 1.024.09d: kṛtām cid énaḥ prá mumugdhi asmát
metric = cLcLlCclclL
- 1.024.10a: amí yá řkṣā níhitāsa uccá
metric = cLCLlCclclL
- 1.024.13c: ávainaṃ rájā váruṇaḥ sasṛjyād
metric = ClLlLlCclcll
- 1.034.09d: yéna yajñam nāsatiyopayāthāḥ
metric = LclLlclclL
- 1.035.05d: upásthe víśvā bhúvanāni tasthuḥ
metric = cLlLlCclcll

- 1.035.07b: gabhīráv epā ásurah sunītháh
metric = cLCllCclclL
- 1.035.10a: híraṇyahasto ásurah sunītháh
metric = ClcllCclclL
- 1.059.02c: táṃ tvā devāso 'janayanta devám
metric = LllLlccclclL
- 1.062.03b: vidát sarāmā tánayāya dhāsīm
metric = cLcClCclclL
- 1.062.13c: sunīthāya nah śavasāna nodháh
metric = cLlclccclclL
- 1.063.04b: vṛtrám yád vajrin vṛṣakarman ubhnáh
metric = lLlllccclclL
- 1.063.04d: ví dāsýũr yónāv ákr̥to vṛthāṣāt
metric = CLlllCclclL
- 1.063.08a: tuvám tyám na indara+ deva citrám
metric = cLLclccclclL
- 1.071.01c: svāsārah śyāvīm áruṣīm ajuṣrañ
metric = CllllCclcll
- 1.071.07d: vidá devēṣu prámatiṃ cikitvān
metric = cLlllCclclL
- 1.072.04c: vidán márto nemádhitā cikitvān
metric = cLlllCclclL
- 1.072.10d: prá nícīr agne áruṣīr ajānan
metric = CLlllCclcll
- 1.079.01a: híraṇyakeśo rájaso visāré
metric = ClcllCclclL
- 1.089.08a: bhadrám kárṇebhiḥ śṛṇuyāma devā
metric = lLlllccclcll
- 1.095.09a: urú te jráyah pári eti budhnám
metric = cClClCclclL
- 1.095.09c: víśvebhir agne svāyaśobhir iddhó
metric = LlcllCclclL
- 1.107.01a: yajñó devānām práti eti sumnám

- metric = lLlLlCclclL
- 1.108.04a: sámiddheṣu agníṣu ānajāná
metric = ClLclCclclL
- 1.108.04b: yatásrucā barhír u tistirāṇá
metric = cLcllCclclL
- 1.109.05a: yuvám indrāgnī vásuno vibhāgé
metric = cLlllCclclL
- 1.112.24b: kṛtám no dasrā vṛṣaṇā manīṣám
metric = cLlllCclclL
- 1.112.25a: dyúbhir aktúbhiḥ pári pātam asmán
metric = CclClCclclL
- 1.113.03a: samānó ádhvā svásaror anantás
metric = cLlLlCclclL
- 1.116.08a: himénāgnīm ghraṃsám avārayethām
metric = cLlLlCclclL
- 1.116.09a: párāvatám nāsatiyānudethām
metric = ClcLlccclclL
- 1.116.14b: yuvám narā nāsatiyāmumuktam
metric = cLcllccclclL
- 1.116.16d: ádhattám dasrā bhiṣajāv anarván
metric = LllllccclclL
- 1.116.17d: sám u śriyá nāsatiyā sacethe
metric = ClcLlccclclL
- 1.117.03c: minántā dásyor áśivasya māyá
metric = cLlLlCclclL
- 1.117.11d: sám viśpālám nāsatiyāriṇītam
metric = LlClLccclclL
- 1.117.12b: dívo napātā vṛṣaṇā śayutrā
metric = ClcllccclclL
- 1.117.21b: íṣam duhántā mánuṣāya dasrā
metric = ClcLlCclclL
- 1.117.23d: apatyasācam śrútiyam rarāthām
metric = clcLlCclclL

- 1.117.24d: új jīvása airayataṃ sudānū
metric = LlCclclcll
- 1.118.05c: pári vām ásvā vápuṣaḥ patamḡá
metric = CclLlCclclL
- 1.118.06c: níṣ ṭaugriyám pārayathaḥ samudrát
metric = LlcLlclclL
- 1.122.09a: jáno yó mitrāvaruṇāv abhidhrúg
metric = CllllcclclL
- 1.123.05a: bhágasya svásā váruṇasya jāmír
metric = CllClCclclL
- 1.123.08d: ékaikā krátum pári yanti sadyáḥ
metric = LllClCclclL
- 1.126.01a: ámandān stómān prá bhare manīṣá
metric = CllllCclclL
- 1.128.07f: sá nas trāsate váruṇasya dhūrtér
metric = CllclCclclL
- 1.130.10a: sá no návyebhir vṛṣakarman ukthaiḥ
metric = CllllcclclL
- 1.143.08d: ániṣadbbhiḥ pári pāhi no jáḥ
metric = CccllCclclL
- 1.148.04c: ád asya vāto ánu vāti śócír
metric = LlcLlCclclL
- 1.152.01d: ṛténa mitrāvaruṇā sacethe
metric = cLllclclclL
- 1.152.02a: etác caná tvo ví ciketad eṣāṃ
metric = llcLlCclcll
- 1.152.07b: námasā devāv ávasā vavṛtyām
metric = CclllCclcll
- 1.153.02b: áyāmi mitrāvaruṇā suvrktíḥ
metric = ClcllclclL
- 1.153.03b: jánāya mitrāvaruṇā havirdé
metric = ClcllclclL

- 1.157.05a: yuvám ha gárbhaṃ jágatīṣu dhattho
metric = cLcLlCclcll
- 1.158.01d: prá yát sasráthe ákavābhir ūtí
metric = CLLLLCclclL
- 1.161.14d: yuṣmāñ ichántaḥ śavaso napātaḥ
metric = lLcLlccclcll
- 1.162.19d: tá-tā píṇḍānām prá juhomi agnaú
metric = LLLLLCclclL
- 1.162.21c: hári te yúñjā pṛṣatī abhūtām
metric = CLLLLCclcll
- 1.164.47a: kṛṣṇám niyānaṃ hárayaḥ suparṇá
metric = lLcLlCclclL
- 1.165.01d: árcanti súṣmaṃ vṛṣaṇo vasūyá
metric = LlcLlCclclL
- 1.165.06d: víśvasya śátror ánamaṃ vadhasnaíḥ
metric = LlcLlCclclL
- 1.167.07d: sthirá cij jánīr váhate subhāgāḥ
metric = cLlClCclclL
- 1.169.01b: mahás cid asi tyájaso varūtá
metric = cLcclCclclL
- 1.171.03d: áhāni víśvā maruto jigīṣá
metric = ClcLlccclclL
- 1.171.05d: ugrá ugrébhi stháviraḥ sahodāḥ
metric = lClllCclclL
- 1.173.05d: vavavrúṣaś cit támaso vihantá
metric = clClLcclclL
- 1.174.03b: diyám ca yébhiḥ puruhūta nūnám
metric = cLcLlccclclL
- 1.177.03c: yuktvá vṛṣabhyām vṛṣabha kṣitínām
metric = lLClLccclclL
- 1.177.05a: ó súṣṭuta indara+ yāhi arvāñ
metric = LLcclclclL
- 1.179.01d: ápy ū nú pátnīr vṛṣaṇo jagamyuḥ

metric = LlCLlCclcll

1.179.02d: sám ū nú pátnīr vṛṣabhir jagamyuḥ

metric = ClCLlCclcll

1.180.04b: apó ná kṣódo avṛṇītam eṣé

metric = cLLLLcclclL

1.180.08b: vírudrasya prasrávaṇasya sātaú

metric = CllllCclclL

1.181.02a: á vām áśvāsaḥ śúcayaḥ payaspá

metric = LllllCclclL

1.181.05b: piśáṅgarūpaḥ sádanāni gamyāḥ

metric = cLcllCclcll

1.181.08d: gō´r ná séke mánuṣo daśasyán

metric = LCLlCclclL

1.186.03a: práyiṣṭhaṃ+ vo · átithiṃ gṛṇīṣe

metric = ClllCclcll

1.186.03c: ásad yáthā no váruṇaḥ sukīrtír

metric = ClCLlCclclL

1.186.04a: úpa va eṣe námasā jigīṣá

metric = CccllCclclL

1.186.10a: prá ūaśvínāv ávase kṛṇudhvam

metric = ClLClCclcll

1.189.06a: ví gha tuvávāṃ ṛtajāta yaṃsad

metric = CcclLcclcll

2.003.10c: trídihā sámaktaṃ nayatu prajānán

metric = ClClLcclclL

2.014.07b: bhúmyā upásthe ávapaj jaghanván

metric = LlclLlCclclL

2.018.05b: á catvāriṃśátā háribhir yujánāḥ

metric = LlllClCclclL

2.027.06c: ténāditiyā ádhi vocatā no

metric = LlcllCclcll

2.027.08c: ṛténādityā máhi vo mahitvám

metric = cLlllCclclL

- 2.027.15a: ubhé asmai pīpayataḥ samīcī
metric = cLlllcclclL
- 2.028.03c: yūyāṃ naḥ putrā aditer adabdhā
metric = lLlllcclcll
- 2.028.03d: abhī kṣamadhvaṃ yújiyāya devāḥ
metric = cLcllCclcll
- 2.028.09b: māhāṃ rājann anyākṛtena bhojam
metric = LlllCclcll
- 2.030.04b: vṛkadvaraso ásurasya vīrān
metric = ClcclCclclL
- 2.030.09d: druhé riṣantam pári dhehi rājan
metric = cLlllCclcll
- 2.030.10c: jiyóg abhūvann ánudhūpitāso
metric = cLcllCclcll
- 2.035.09d: híraṇyavarṇāḥ pári yanti yahvīḥ
metric = ClcllCclclL
- 2.035.12d: dádhāmi ánnaiḥ pári vanda ṛgbhīḥ
metric = ClcLlCclclL
- 2.038.03c: ahyárṣūṇāṃ cin ní ayāṃ aviṣyāṃ
metric = lLlllCclclL
- 2.039.01d: dūtéva hávyā jániyā purutrā
metric = lLcLlCclclL
- 2.040.01a: sómāpūṣaṇā jánanā rayīṇāṃ
metric = LllclCclclL
- 2.040.06a: dhíyam pūṣá jinvalu viśvaminvó
metric = CllllcclclL
- 3.001.05a: śukrēbhir ángai rája ātatanván
metric = lLcLlCclclL
- 3.001.16a: upakṣetāras táva supraṇīte
metric = cllllCclcll
- 3.004.11c: barhír na āstām áditiḥ suputrā
metric = lLcllCclclL

- 3.005.03d: ábhūd u vípro háviyo matīnām
metric = ClcLlCclclL
- 3.006.07a: divás cid á te rucayanta roká
metric = cLcLlccclclL
- 3.007.06b: mahó mahádbhyām anayanta súṣám
metric = cLcLlccclclL
- 3.007.09c: déva hotar mandrá taraś cikitvān
metric = LcLlLlCclclL
- 3.008.08c: sajóṣaso yajñám avantu devá
metric = cLcllCclclL
- 3.008.10b: caśálavantaḥ sváravaḥ pṛthivyām
metric = cLcllCclclL
- 3.014.04a: mitrás ca túbhyaṃ váruṇaḥ sahasvo
metric = lLcLlCclcll
- 3.017.05c: tásyānu dhárma prá yajā cikitvo
metric = LLcLlCclcll
- 3.020.01c: sujyótiṣo naḥ śṛṇuvantu deváh
metric = lLcllccclclL
- 3.030.07d: saháśradānā puruhūta rātíḥ
metric = cLcllccclclL
- 3.030.21a: á no gotrá dardṛhi gopate gáh
metric = LllLlccclclL
- 3.031.07c: sasána máryo yúvabhir makhasyānn
metric = cLcLlCclclL
- 3.032.01c: praprúthyā śípre maghavann ṛjīṣin
metric = lLlLlccclcll
- 3.032.02a: gávāśiram manthínam indra súkrám
metric = ClcllCclclL
- 3.033.03a: áchā síndhum mātṛtamām ayāsaṃ
metric = CLlLlCclcll
- 3.033.09c: ní śú namadhvam bhávatā supārá
metric = CLcllCclclL
- 3.034.04b: jigāyośígbhiḥ pṛtanā abhiṣṭíḥ

- metric = cLlLLCclclL
- 3.035.08b: sám indra góbhīr mádhūmantam akraṇ
metric = ClcLlCclcll
- 3.038.08d: ápīva yóṣā jānimāni vavre
metric = ClcLlCclcll
- 3.043.04c: dhānāvād índraḥ sávanam juṣāṇāḥ
metric = llcLlCclclL
- 3.043.05b: kuvíd rájānam maghavann ṛjīṣin
metric = cLlLlCclcll
- 3.043.06a: á tvā brhánto hárayo yujāná
metric = LlcllCclclL
- 3.052.07a: pūṣaṇvāte te cakṛmā karambhām
metric = llCllCclclL
- 3.052.08b: puroḷásam vīrátamāya nṛṇām+
metric = cLlLlCclclL
- 3.053.07b: divás putráso ásurasya vīráḥ
metric = cLlLlCclclL
- 3.054.21d: úd rāyó aśyām sádanam purukṣóḥ
metric = LllLlCclclL
- 3.055.04a: samāno rájā víbhṛtaḥ purutrā
metric = cLlLlCclclL
- 3.056.04c: ápaś cid asmā aramanta devīḥ
metric = LlcllCclclL
- 3.056.04d: pṛthag vrājantīḥ pári ṣīm avṛñjan
metric = ClCllCclcll
- 3.059.01a: mitró jānān yātayati bruvāṇó
metric = llCllCclclL
- 3.061.05b: prá vo bhāradhvaṃ námasā suvṛktīm
metric = ClcllCclclL
- 4.001.04a: tuvām no agne váruṇasya vidvān
metric = cLlLlCclclL
- 4.001.04b: devásya héḷo áva yāsisīṣṭhāḥ
metric = llcLlCclcll

- 4.001.04d: víśvā dvéśāṃsi prá mumugdhi asmát
metric = LLLLLCclclL
- 4.001.20c: agnír devānām áva āvr̥ṇānáḥ
metric = LLLLLCclclL
- 4.002.12b: nidhāráyanto dúriyāsu āyóḥ
metric = clClLCclclL
- 4.003.07d: brávaḥ kád agne śárave bṛhatyaí
metric = ClClLCclclL
- 4.003.10c: áspandamāno acarad vayodhá
metric = LlcllcclclL
- 4.003.12b: árṇobhir āpo mádhumadbhir agne
metric = LlclLCclclL
- 4.004.01c: tṛṣvīm ánu · práśitiṃ druṇānó°
metric = LlClCclclL
- 4.004.04c: yó no árātiṃ samidhāna cakré
metric = LlClcclclL
- 4.004.14c: ubhá śáṃsā sūdaya satyatāte
metric = cLLLLcclclL
- 4.004.15d: druhó nidó mitramaho avadyát
metric = cLcllcclclL
- 4.005.10d: vr̥ṣṇaḥ śocíṣaḥ práyatasya jihvá
metric = Ll̥ClCclclL
- 4.006.06a: bhadrá te agne suanīka saṃdṛḡ
metric = LLLLLcclclL
- 4.014.02b: jyótir víśvasmai bhúvanāya kṛṇván
metric = LLLLLCclclL
- 4.017.09a: ayám vr̥taś cātayate samícír
metric = cLClcclclL
- 4.017.12a: kíyat svid índro ádhi eti mātúḥ
metric = ClclLCclclL
- 4.018.08c: mámac cid āpaḥ śísave mamṛdyur
metric = ClclLCclclL

- 4.018.10a: gr̥ṣṭīḥ sasūva sthāviraṃ tavāgām
metric = lLcllCclclL
- 4.019.07c: dhānvāni ajrāṃ apṛṇak tṛṣāṇāṃ
metric = LlclLcclclL
- 4.020.09d: áthā dadhāti dráviṇaṃ jaritré
metric = ClcllCclclL
- 4.021.05a: úpa yó námo námasi stabhāyānn
metric = CcLClCclclL
- 4.023.03d: kathaínam āhuḥ pápurim̐ jaritré
metric = cLcllCclclL
- 4.027.03d: kṛśánur ástā mánasā bhuraṇyān
metric = cLcLlCclclL
- 4.033.09a: ápo hí eṣām ájuṣanta devá
metric = ClClLcclclL
- 4.033.10c: té rāyás póṣaṃ dráviṇāni asmé
metric = LLLLlCclclL
- 4.035.03d: gaṇām devānām ṛbhavaḥ suhastāḥ
metric = cLlLlCclclL
- 4.037.02c: prá vaḥ sutáso harayanta pūrṇāḥ
metric = ClclLcclclL
- 4.037.04c: índrasya sūno śavaso napāto
metric = LlclllcclclL
- 4.041.05c: sá no duhīyad yāvaseva gatví
metric = LlcllCclclL
- 4.041.10a: ásvyasya tmánā ráthiyasya puṣṭér
metric = LllClCclclL
- 4.042.01c: krátuṃ sacante váruṇasya devá
metric = ClcllCclclL
- 4.042.02c: krátuṃ sacante váruṇasya devá
metric = ClcllCclclL
- 4.042.03c: tváṣṭeva víśvā bhúvanāni vidván
metric = LlcllCclclL
- 4.042.06d: ubhé bhayete rájasī apāré

- metric = cLcllCclclL
- 4.043.05a: urú vāṃ ráthaḥ pári nakṣati dyám
metric = cClClCclclL
- 4.043.05c: mádhvā mādhuví mādhu vām pruṣāyan
metric = LllclCclcll
- 4.043.07d: śritáḥ kámo nāsatiyā yuvadrík
metric = cLlllcclclL
- 4.044.07d: śritáḥ kámo nāsatiyā yuvadrík
metric = cLlllcclclL
- 4.050.09d: brahmāṇe rájā tám avanti deváh
metric = lClLlCclclL
- 4.051.02d: uchántir avrañ chúcayaḥ pavākāḥ+
metric = cLlllCclclL
- 4.051.09d: súkrās tanúbhiḥ súcayo rucānáḥ
metric = lLcLlCclclL
- 4.055.02d: ṛtádhitayo rurucanta dasmáh
metric = cClclccclclL
- 4.055.06b: stuvítá devī ápiyebhir iṣṭaíḥ
metric = cLClLlCclclL
- 4.057.02a: kṣétrasya pate mádhumantam ūrmím
metric = LlccclCclclL
- 4.058.07b: vátapramiyāḥ patayanti yahváḥ
metric = LlccclccclclL
- 4.058.10d: ghṛtásya dhārā mádhumat pavante
metric = cLcLlCclcll
- 5.001.09a: prá sadyó agne áti eṣi anyán
metric = ClLllCclclL
- 5.002.03a: híraṇyadantaṃ súcivarṇam ārát
metric = ClcllCclclL
- 5.004.08b: sáhasaḥ sūno triṣadhastha havyám
metric = CclllccclclL
- 5.012.02b: ṛtásya dhārā ánu tṛndhi pūrvíḥ
metric = cLcLlCclclL

- 5.012.05b: śivásah sánto áśivā abhūvan
metric = cLLLLCclcll
- 5.029.08c: kāraṃ ná víśve ahuvanta devā
metric = lLCLlcclclL
- 5.030.05c: átaś cid índrād abhayanta devā
metric = ClcLlcclclL
- 5.030.13d: aktór víuṣṭau páritakmiyāyāḥ
metric = lLCLlCclcll
- 5.030.14a: aúchat sá rátrī páritakmiyā yāṃ
metric = LLLLLCclclL
- 5.030.15a: cátuḥsahasraṃ gáviyasya paśváḥ
metric = ClcllCclclL
- 5.031.11a: súraś cid rátham páritakmiyāyām
metric = LllCLCclcll
- 5.037.03d: purú saháśrā pári vartayāte
metric = cLcLlCclcll
- 5.040.04c: yuktvā háribhyām úpa yāsad arvān
metric = lLCLlCclclL
- 5.041.01a: kó nú vām mitrávaruṇāv ṛtāyán
metric = LClllcclclL
- 5.041.03b: vátasya pátman ráthiyasya puṣṭau
metric = LlcllCclclL
- 5.041.14b: apás ca áchā súmakhāya vocam
metric = cLcClCclcll
- 5.042.01d: átūrtapanthā ásuro mayobhúḥ
metric = ClcllCclclL
- 5.055.10b: nír aṃhatíbhyo maruto gṛṇānāḥ
metric = ClcLlcclclL
- 5.057.07b: candrávad rádho maruto dadā naḥ
metric = lCLLlcclcll
- 5.058.03d: etāṃ juṣadhvaṃ kavayo yuvānaḥ
metric = lLcllcclcll

- 5.062.01d: devānām śrēṣṭhaṃ vāpuṣām apaśyam
metric = lllllCclcll
- 5.062.02a: tát sú vām mitrāvaruṇā mahitvām
metric = LClllcclclL
- 5.062.02b: ĩrmá tasthúṣīr áhabhir duduhre
metric = lLlClCclcll
- 5.062.09c: téna no mitrāvaruṇāv aviṣṭaṃ
metric = Lclllcclcll
- 5.083.10d: utá prajābhyo avido manīṣām
metric = cLcLlccclclL
- 5.085.04d: taviṣīyántaḥ śrathayanta vīrāḥ
metric = cclllcclclL
- 6.001.11c: bṛhādbhir vājai sthāvirebhir asmé
metric = cLlllCclclL
- 6.003.05a: sá íd ásteva práti dhād asiṣyāñ
metric = CcLllCclclL
- 6.004.05b: vāyúr ná ráṣṭrī áti eti aktún
metric = lLCLlCclclL
- 6.004.05d: átyo ná hrútaḥ pátataḥ parihrút
metric = LLLClCclclL
- 6.005.04b: yó ántaro mitramaho vanuṣyāt
metric = LLcllcclclL
- 6.006.04a: yé te śukrásah śúcayah śuciṣmah
metric = LllllCclcll
- 6.006.07b: cítrakṣatra citrátamaṃ vayodhām
metric = LllclCclclL
- 6.007.01d: āsānn á pátraṃ janayanta devāḥ
metric = LllllcclclL
- 6.007.02a: nābhiṃ yajñānām sādanaṃ rayīṇām
metric = LllllCclclL
- 6.008.07b: asmākam pāhi triṣadhastha sūrīn
metric = LllllcclclL
- 6.010.04d: tirāḥ śocīṣā dadṛṣe pavākāḥ+

- metric = cLlClcclclL
- 6.015.16a: ágne víśvebhiḥ suanīka devaír
metric = LLLLLcclclL
- 6.018.10a: agnír ná śúṣkaṃ vānam indra hetí
metric = lLCLlCclclL
- 6.018.14a: ánu tváhighne ádha deva devá
metric = CLLLLcclclL
- 6.018.15d: uktháṃ návīyo janayasva yajñaiḥ
metric = lLClLcclclL
- 6.019.06b: ójiṣṭham ójo abhibhūta ugrám
metric = LlCLLcclclL
- 6.022.10a: á saṃyátam indara+ ṇaḥ suastīm
metric = LlCclcclclL
- 6.022.11a: sá no niyúdbhiḥ puruhūta vedho
metric = ClCLLcclclL
- 6.024.09d: aktór víuṣṭau páritakmiyāyām
metric = lLClLcclclL
- 6.025.05c: índra nákiṣ ṭvā práti asti eṣāṃ
metric = LcCLlCclclL
- 6.026.07c: tváyā yát stávante sadhavīra vīrás
metric = CLCLlclclL
- 6.027.01a: kím asya máde kím u asya pītāv
metric = ClcClCclclL
- 6.027.02a: sád asya máde sád u asya pītāv
metric = ClcClCclclL
- 6.027.06a: triṃśácchataṃ varmīṇa indra sākám
metric = lLcllCclclL
- 6.029.02a: á yásmin háste náriyā mimikṣúr
metric = LLLLLcclclL
- 6.029.02d: ádhvann áśvāso vṛṣaṇo yujānáḥ
metric = LLLLLcclclL
- 6.032.04c: puruvīrābhir vṛṣabha kṣitīnām
metric = ccLllcclclL

- 6.034.01d: paspr̥dhrá índre ádhi ukthaarká
metric = llCl̥l̥CclclL
- 6.034.04d: satrá vāv̥rdhur hávanāni yajñaiḥ
metric = ll̥l̥cl̥Cclcl̥L
- 6.036.01c: satrá vājānām abhavo vibhaktá
metric = LLLLl̥cclclL
- 6.036.01d: yád devéṣu dhāráyathā asuryām
metric = Lll̥cl̥CclclL
- 6.036.05c: áso yáthā naḥ śávasā cakānó
metric = Cl̥Cl̥l̥CclclL
- 6.037.05a: índro vājasya sthāvīrasya dātá
metric = LLLLl̥CclclL
- 6.040.02b: mādāya krátve ápibo virapsin
metric = Cl̥ll̥l̥Cclcll
- 6.044.19a: á tvā hárayo vṛṣaṇo yujāná
metric = Ll̥Ccl̥CclclL
- 6.044.22d: índur amuṣṇād áśīvasya māyāḥ
metric = Lccl̥l̥Cclcl̥L
- 6.047.08c: ṛṣvā ta indra sthāvīrasya bāhú
metric = l̥L̥cl̥l̥CclclL
- 6.047.17c: ánānubhūtīr avadhūnuvānāḥ
metric = Cl̥cl̥ll̥cclclL
- 6.049.05b: rátho virúkmān mánasā yujānāḥ
metric = Cl̥cl̥Ll̥CclclL
- 6.049.06a: párjanyavātā vṛṣabhā pṛthivyāḥ
metric = Ll̥cl̥ll̥cclclL
- 6.050.04d: bādhé marúto áhuvāma devān
metric = ll̥Ccl̥CclclL
- 6.051.06b: aghāyaté rīradhatā yajatrāḥ
metric = cl̥cl̥Ll̥cclcll
- 6.051.08c: námo devébhyo náma īśa eṣāṃ
metric = Cl̥ll̥l̥Cclcll

- 6.052.13d: āsadyāsmín barhíṣi mādayadhvam
metric = llllCclcll
- 6.063.02a: áram me gantaṃ hávanāya asmaí
metric = CllllCclclL
- 6.063.04c: prá hótā · gūrtāmanā urāṇó
metric = CLllCclclL
- 6.067.03d: chrudhīyatás cid yatatho mahitvá
metric = clcLlclclL
- 6.067.10d: nákir devébhīr yatatho mahitvá
metric = CllllclclL
- 6.068.03b: sumnébhīr índrāvāruṇā cakāná
metric = lLcLlCclclL
- 6.068.04c: prá ebhya indrāvaruṇā mahitvá
metric = ClcllclclL
- 6.068.07c: yéṣāṃ súṣmaḥ pṛtanāsu sāhvān
metric = LlllCclclL
- 6.068.08a: nú na indrāvaruṇā grṇāná
metric = CcllclclL
- 6.068.11c: idám vām ándhaḥ páriṣiktam asmé
metric = cLllCclclL
- 6.068.11d: āsadyāsmín barhíṣi mādayethām
metric = llllCclcll
- 6.069.04c: juṣéthāṃ víśvā hávanā matīnām
metric = cLllCclclL
- 6.072.05b: apatyasācaṃ śrútiyaṃ rarāthe
metric = clcLlCclcll
- 6.074.02c: āré bādhethāṃ níṛṛtim parācaír
metric = llllCclclL
- 6.075.03b: priyāṃ sákhāyam pariṣasvajāná
metric = cLcllclclL
- 6.075.07d: kṣiṇánti sátrūṃr ánapavyayantaḥ
metric = cLcLlCclcll
- 7.001.11a: má súne agne ní ṣadāma nṛṇām+

- metric = LLlllCclclL
- 7.001.18a: imó agne vītátamāni havyá
metric = cLlllCclclL
- 7.001.23a: sá máрто agne suanīka reván
metric = CLlllcclclL
- 7.002.02c: yé sukrátavaḥ súcayo dhiyaṃdhāḥ
metric = lLcclCclclL
- 7.002.11c: barhír na āstām áditiḥ suputrā
metric = lLcllCclclL
- 7.003.02c: ád asya vāto ánu vāti śócír
metric = LlcllCclclL
- 7.003.06d: citró ná súraḥ práti cakṣi bhānúm
metric = lLcllCclclL
- 7.004.02b: yáto yáviṣṭho ájaniṣṭa mātúḥ
metric = ClcllCclclL
- 7.005.07b: vāyúr ná páthaḥ pári pāsi sadyáḥ
metric = lLcllCclclL
- 7.008.03a: káyā no agne ví vasaḥ suvr̥ktim̐
metric = CllllCclclL
- 7.010.05c: sá hí kṣápāvāṃ ábhavad rayiṇām
metric = ClcllCclclL
- 7.018.11c: dasmó ná sádman ní śísāti barhíḥ
metric = lLcllCclclL
- 7.019.11a: nú indra súra stávamāna ūtí
metric = LlcllCclclL
- 7.021.01c: bódhāmasi tvā hariaśva yajñaír
metric = LlcllcclclL
- 7.021.04b: ápāṃsi víśvā náriyāṇi vidván
metric = ClcllCclclL
- 7.021.05a: ná yātáva indara+ jūjuvur no
metric = ClCclclcll
- 7.021.09c: vanvántu smā te ávasā samiké
metric = lLlllCclclL

- 7.024.02c: vísr̥ṣṭadhenā bharate suvr̥ktír
metric = Clc̣ḷḷc̣cḷcḷL
- 7.027.01a: índraṃ náro nemádhitā havante
metric = LlC̣ḷḷC̣cḷcḷḷ
- 7.033.05d: ur̥uṃ t̥ṛ̥tsubhyo ak̥ṛ̥ṇod ulokám̥t̥
metric = cLḷḷḷc̣cḷcḷL
- 7.033.06a: daṇḍá ivéd goájanāsa āsan
metric = llC̣ḷḷC̣cḷcḷḷ
- 7.033.08d: stómo vasiṣṭhā ánuetave vaḥ
metric = LlcḷḷC̣cḷcḷḷ
- 7.034.23d: ubhé ródasī pári pāsato naḥ
metric = cLḷcḷC̣cḷcḷḷ
- 7.035.05d: sám no rájasas pátir astu jiṣṇúḥ
metric = LlC̣cḷC̣cḷcḷL
- 7.035.07b: sám no grāvāṇaḥ sám u santu yajñāḥ
metric = LlḷḷḷC̣cḷcḷL
- 7.035.09d: sám no bhavítiraṃ sám u astu vāyúḥ
metric = LlC̣ḷḷC̣cḷcḷL
- 7.036.02a: imám̥ vām̥ mitrāvaruṇā suvr̥ktím̥
metric = cLḷḷḷḷc̣cḷcḷL
- 7.037.05b: yābhir víveṣo hariaśva dhībhīḥ
metric = LlC̣ḷḷc̣cḷcḷL
- 7.037.05c: vavanmá nú te yújiyābhir ūtí
metric = cLḷC̣ḷC̣cḷcḷL
- 7.037.06d: p̥ṛ̥kṣó no árvā ní uhīta vājí
metric = llḷḷḷC̣cḷcḷL
- 7.038.08b: dhāneṣu viprā amṛtā ṛtajñāḥ
metric = Clcḷḷc̣cḷcḷḷ
- 7.042.02d: huvé devánām̥ jánimāni sattāḥ
metric = cLḷḷḷC̣cḷcḷL
- 7.044.04b: ágre ráthānām̥ bhavati prajānán
metric = LlC̣ḷḷc̣cḷcḷL

- 7.045.02d: súraś cid asmā ánu dād apasyám
metric = LlcllCclclL
- 7.046.04c: á no bhaja barhíṣi jīvaśaṃsé
metric = LlcllCclclL
- 7.047.02a: tám ūrmīm āpo mádhumattamaṃ vo
metric = ClClLlCclcll
- 7.048.04c: sám asmé íṣaṃ vásavo dadīran
metric = ClLClCclcll
- 7.056.12d: chúcijanmānaḥ súcayaḥ pavākāḥ+
metric = CcllllCclclL
- 7.056.14d: gṛhamedhīyam maruto juṣadhvam
metric = cclLlclcll
- 7.056.18d: só ádvayāvī havate va ukthaiḥ
metric = LLclllcclclL
- 7.057.05b: anavadyāsaḥ súcayaḥ pavākāḥ+
metric = cclLlCclclL
- 7.058.01d: náḡsante nákaṃ níṛṛter avamśát
metric = LllLlCclclL
- 7.058.02d: víśvo vo yāman bhayate suvardḡk
metric = LllLlclclL
- 7.058.03c: gató ná ádhvā ví tirāti jantúm
metric = cLClLlCclclL
- 7.058.04a: yuṣmóto vípro marutaḥ śatasví
metric = lllLlclclL
- 7.058.04b: yuṣmóto árvā sáhuriḥ sahasrí
metric = lllLlCclclL
- 7.060.09d: urúm sudāse vṛṣaṇā ulokám†
metric = cLcLlclclL
- 7.061.03a: prá urór mitrāvaruṇā pṛthivyāḥ
metric = CcLllclclL
- 7.064.01a: diví kṣáyantā rájasaḥ pṛthivyám
metric = cLClLlCclclL
- 7.067.08a: ékasmin yóge bhuraṇā samāné

- metric = LllLlccclclL
- 7.068.04c: á valgú vípro vavṛtīta havyaíḥ
metric = LllLlccclclL
- 7.079.04b: yávat stotṛbhyo árado grṇāná
metric = LllLlCclclL
- 7.084.02c: pári no hélo váruṇasya vṛjyā
metric = CclLlCclcll
- 7.086.03d: ayám ha túbhyaṃ váruṇo hrṇīte
metric = cLcLlCclcll
- 7.086.08a: ayám sú túbhyaṃ varuṇa svadhāvo
metric = cLCLlccclcll
- 7.088.05c: bṛhántam mánam varuṇa svadhāvaḥ
metric = cLllLccclcll
- 7.088.07b: ví asmát páśam váruṇo mumocat
metric = CLllLcclcll
- 7.093.04c: índraagnī vṛtrahaṇā suvajrā
metric = Lcllllccclcll
- 7.093.04d: prá no návyebhis tirataṃ dayaṣṇaíḥ+
metric = CLllllccclclL
- 7.097.08b: bṛhaspátim vāvṛdhatur mahitvá
metric = ClCllccclclL
- 7.098.05c: yadéd ádevīr ásahiṣṭa māyá
metric = cLClLcclclL
- 7.099.03b: sūyavasínī mánuṣe daśasyá
metric = lccClCclclL
- 7.100.01a: nū´ mártio° dayate saniṣyán
metric = CLclccclclL
- 7.100.04b: kṣétrāya víṣṇur mánuṣe daśasyán
metric = LlclLlCclclL
- 7.103.09d: taptá gharmá ásnuvate visargám
metric = lllLlccclclL
- 7.104.13d: ubháv índrasya prásitau śayāte
metric = cLllllCclcll

- 8.009.15a: yán nāsatiyā parāké
metric = LlcccllL
- 8.042.01c: āsīdad víśvā bhúvanāni samráḍ
metric = LllllCclclL
- 8.048.10b: yó mā ná rīṣyed dhariaśva pītāḥ
metric = LlCLlcccllL
- 8.048.14a: trātāro devā ádhi vocatā no
metric = LllllCclcll
- 8.057.01d: idám tr̥tīyaṃ sávanam pibāthaḥ
metric = cLcLlCclcll
- 8.057.04c: píbatam sómam mádhumantam asmé
metric = CclllCclclL
- 8.080.10c: tásmā u rádhaḥ kṛṇuta praśastám
metric = LlcllcccllL
- 8.096.03d: āsānn eṣanta śrútiyā upāké
metric = lllllCclclL
- 8.096.09c: anāyudháso ásurā adevás
metric = clcllCclclL
- 8.101.14c: bṛhád dha tasthau bhúvaneṣu antāḥ
metric = cLcllCclclL
- 9.085.11b: gíro venānām akṛpanta pūrvīḥ
metric = CllllcccllL
- 9.088.04b: hantā vṛtrāṇām asi soma pūrbhít
metric = lllllcccllL
- 9.088.05d: íyarti sómaḥ pávamāna ūrmím
metric = ClcllCclclL
- 9.089.03d: áśya cákṣasā pári pāti ukṣá
metric = LcLclCclclL
- 9.089.05d: tá iṃ viśvátaḥ pári ṣanti pūrvīḥ
metric = LllClCclclL
- 9.092.05c: jyótir yád áhne ákṛṇod ulokámṭ
metric = LlCLlCclclL

- 9.093.03b: índur dhárābhiḥ sacate sumedhāḥ
metric = LLLLLcclclL
- 9.095.05b: punāná indo ví ṣiyā manīṣām
metric = cLCllCclclL
- 9.096.12a: yáthāpavathā mánave vayodhá
metric = CLcclCclclL
- 9.097.11a: ádha dhārayā mádhuvā pṛcānás
metric = CcLclCclclL
- 9.097.28a: áśvo ná krado vṛṣabhir yujānāḥ
metric = LLLclCclclL
- 9.097.41b: apām yád gárbho ávṛṇīta devān
metric = cLLLLCclclL
- 9.097.49c: abhī náraṃ dhījāvanaṃ ratheṣṭhām
metric = cLCllCclclL
- 9.107.09c: samudrām ná saṃvāraṇāni agman
metric = cLLClCclclL
- 10.002.04b: vidúṣām devā áviduṣṭarāsaḥ
metric = cLlllCclclL
- 10.004.07c: rákṣā ṇo agne tánayāni tokā
metric = LllllCclclL
- 10.008.06c: diví mūrdhānaṃ dadhiṣe suarṣām
metric = cLlllcclclL
- 10.010.02c: mahás putráso ásurasya vīrá
metric = cLlllCclclL
- 10.010.09a: rátrībhir asmā áhabhir daśasyet
metric = LlcllCclclL
- 10.010.13d: pári ṣvajāte líbujeva vṛkṣám
metric = ClcllCclclL
- 10.010.14b: pári ṣvajāte líbujeva vṛkṣám
metric = ClcllCclclL
- 10.014.01b: bahúbhyaḥ pánthām anupaspaśānám
metric = cLlllcclclL
- 10.014.11c: tábhiyām enam pári dehi rājan

metric = LclllCclcll

10.017.03b: ánaṣṭapaśur bhúvanasya gopáḥ
metric = ClcclCclclL

10.017.04a: áyur viśváyuh pari pāsati tvā
metric = LlllLlCclcll

10.022.13a: asmé tá ta indara+ santu satyá
metric = lLLclclclL

10.027.09d: átho áyuktaṃ yunajad vavanván
metric = ClClclclclL

10.027.15b: aṣṭóttarátāt sám ajagmīran té
metric = lLcLlCclclL

10.027.18a: ví krośanáso víṣuañca āyan
metric = LlclLlCclcll

10.027.19a: ápaśyaṃ grāmaṃ váhamānam ārād
metric = CllllCclclL

10.028.06c: purú sahásrā ní śísāmi sākám
metric = cLcLlCclclL

10.029.01b: chúcir vāṃ stómo bhuraṇāv ajīgaḥ
metric = Cllllclclcll

10.029.05c: gíraś ca yé te tuvijāta pūrvír
metric = ClcLlclclL

10.030.07a: yó vo vṛtábhyo ákṛṇod ulokáṃt
metric = LlclLlCclclL

10.030.07d: devamādanam prá hiṇotanāpaḥ
metric = lcLclCclcll

10.030.14b: ádhvaryavaḥ sādáyatā sakhāyaḥ
metric = LlcllCclcll

10.030.14c: ní barhíṣi dhattana somiyāso
metric = ClCclclcll

10.031.02a: pári cin márto dráviṇam mamanyād
metric = CclllCclcll

10.031.02d: śréyāṃsaṃ dáksam mánasā jagṛbhyāt
metric = LlllLlCclcll

- 10.042.11a: bṛhaspátir naḥ pári pātu paścād
metric = ClClLlCclclL
- 10.042.11b: utóttarasmād ádharād aghāyóḥ
metric = cLcllCclclL
- 10.043.11a: bṛhaspátir naḥ pári pātu paścād
metric = ClClLlCclclL
- 10.043.11b: utóttarasmād ádharād aghāyóḥ
metric = cLcllCclclL
- 10.044.07b: ásvā yéṣāṃ duryúja āyuyujré
metric = LLLLLCclclL
- 10.044.11a: bṛhaspátir naḥ pári pātu paścād
metric = ClClLlCclclL
- 10.044.11b: utóttarasmād ádharād aghāyóḥ
metric = cLcllCclclL
- 10.045.01d: índhāna enaṃ jarate suādhīḥ
metric = LlclllcclclL
- 10.046.02d: ichánto dhírā bhṛgavo avindan
metric = cLLLLCclclL
- 10.047.04c: dasyuhānam pūrbhídān indra satyám
metric = lcClLlCclclL
- 10.049.11c: víśvā ít tá te harivaḥ śacīvo
metric = LLLLLcclclL
- 10.055.08b: aśastihā viśvámanās turāṣāṭ
metric = clcLlCclclL
- 10.061.09d: sá dhartá jajñe sáhasā yavīyút
metric = CLLLLCclclL
- 10.061.24d: vípraś ca asi śrávasāś ca sātāú
metric = LlcllCclclL
- 10.061.26b: íti subándhur námasā suuktaíḥ
metric = CccLlCclclL
- 10.063.17a: evá platéḥ sūnúr avīvṛdhad vo
metric = llcLlCclclL

- 10.063.17b: víśva ādityā adite maṇiṣī
metric = LclllcclclL
- 10.064.17a: evá platēḥ sūnúr avīvr̥dhad vo
metric = lLcLlCclcll
- 10.064.17b: víśva ādityā adite maṇiṣī
metric = LclllcclclL
- 10.066.02a: índraprasūtā váruṇapraśiṣṭā
metric = LlcllCclcll
- 10.067.02b: divás putráso ásurasya vīráḥ
metric = cLlLlCclclL
- 10.067.11a: satyám āśiṣaṃ kṛṇutā vayodhai
metric = lLlCclclclL
- 10.070.02d: devébhiyo devátamaḥ suśūdat
metric = lLcllCclcll
- 10.070.09b: yád ángirasām ábhavaḥ sacābhúḥ
metric = CLcclCclclL
- 10.071.08d: óhabrahmāṇo ví caranti u tve
metric = LllllCclcll
- 10.071.11d: yajñásya mátrām ví mimīta u tvaḥ
metric = lLcLlCclcll
- 10.074.05d: bhártā yó vájraṃ náriyam purukṣúḥ
metric = LllLlCclclL
- 10.075.07a: řjīti éni rúsatī mahitvá
metric = ClcLlCclclL
- 10.077.06a: prá yád váhadhve marutaḥ parākād
metric = CLClcclclL
- 10.079.07a: víśūco áśvān yuyuje vanejá
metric = CllllcclclL
- 10.080.01c: agní ródasī ví carat samañján
metric = lLlclCclclL
- 10.080.03c: agnír átriṃ gharmá uruṣyad antár
metric = lClLlCclclL
- 10.083.04b: svayambhúr bhámo abhimātiśāhāḥ

metric = cLLLLcclclL

10.084.07b: asmábhyaṃ dattāṃ váruṇás ca manyúḥ
metric = LLLLLCclclL

10.085.14d: putráḥ pitárāv avṛṇīta pūṣá
metric = LcClcclclL

10.085.19c: bhāgāṃ devébhyo ví dadhāti āyán
metric = LLLLLCclclL

10.087.03c: utántárikṣe pári yāhi rájañ
metric = cLClcclcll

10.087.09b: práñcaṃ vásubhyaḥ prá ṇaya pracetaḥ
metric = LcClcclcll

10.087.12a: tát agne cákṣuḥ práti dhehi rebhé
metric = ClLLLLCclclL

10.088.01c: tásya bhármaṇe bhúvanāya devá
metric = LcLclCclclL

10.088.05a: yáj jātavedo bhúvanasya mūrdhánn
metric = LlcllCclclL

10.088.06d: ápo yát túrṇís cárati prajānán
metric = ClLLLLCclclL

10.088.09d: ṛjūyámāno atapan mahitvá
metric = cLClcclclL

10.088.16c: sá pratyán víśvā bhúvanāni tasthāv
metric = LLLLLCclcll

10.089.02b: éndro vavṛtyād ráthiyeva cakrá
metric = LlcllCclclL

10.089.04b: apáḥ prérayaṃ ságarasya budhnát
metric = cLLclCclclL

10.089.05b: dhúniḥ símivāñ chárumāñ ṛjīṣí
metric = ClClcclclL

10.089.15c: andhénāmítrās támasā sacantāṃ
metric = LLLLLCclcll

10.095.15b: má tvā vṛkāso áśivāsa u kṣan
metric = LcClcclcll

- 10.095.15d: sālāvṛkāṇaṃ hṛdayāni etā
metric = llcLlCclclL
- 10.098.05c: sá úttarasmād ádharaṃ samudrám
metric = CLcllCclclL
- 10.098.06b: ápo devébhīr nívr̥tā atīṣṭhan
metric = LlllLlCclcll
- 10.099.03a: sá vājaṃ yātā ápaduṣpadā yán
metric = ClllLlCclclL
- 10.101.09c: sá no duhīyad yávaseva gatvī
metric = LlcllCclclL
- 10.103.06c: imāṃ saajātā ánu vīrayadhvam
metric = cLcllCclcll
- 10.103.08c: devasenānām abhibhañjatīnām
metric = lcLllcclclL
- 10.103.12d: andhénāmītrās támasā sacantām
metric = llllLlCclcll
- 10.104.03d: dhībhīr vísvābhiḥ śáciyā gṛṇānāḥ
metric = llllLlCclclL
- 10.104.05a: práṇītibhiḥ ṭe hariaśva suṣṭóḥ
metric = ClclllcclclL
- 10.108.01b: dūré hí ádhvā jáguriḥ parācaíḥ
metric = llCllCclclL
- 10.110.01c: á ca váha mitramahaś cikitván
metric = LcCclcclclL
- 10.110.10a: upávasṛja tmāniyā samañján
metric = cLcclCclclL
- 10.110.11b: agnīr devānām abhavat purogāḥ
metric = llllLlCclclL
- 10.117.05c: ó hí vārtante ráthiyeva cakrá
metric = LClLlCclclL
- 10.120.07c: á mātārā sthāpayase jigatnū
metric = LlClllcclclL

- 10.123.03c: ṛtāsya sánāv ádhi cakramāṇá
metric = cLcLlCclclL
- 10.123.06c: híraṇyapakṣaṃ váruṇasya dūtám
metric = ClcllCclclL
- 10.124.05c: ṛténa rājann ánṛtaṃ viviñcán
metric = cLcllCclclL
- 10.128.04d: víśve devāso ádhi vocatā naḥ
metric = LllllCclcll
- 10.129.01d: ámbhaḥ kím āsīd gáhanaṃ gabhírám
metric = LlClLlCclclL
- 10.131.05d: sárasvatī tvā maghavann abhiṣṇak
metric = Clclllcclcll
- 10.139.01d: sampásyan víśvā bhúvanāni gopáḥ
metric = lllllCclclL
- 10.148.02a: ṛṣvās tuvám indara+ sūra jātó
metric = llcClcclclL
- 10.161.01d: tásyā indrāgnī prá mumuktam enam
metric = LllllCclcll
- 10.165.03a: hetíḥ pakṣíṇī ná dabhāti asmán
metric = llLClCclclL
- 10.179.03d: píbendra vajrin purukṛj juṣāṇáh
metric = ClclllcclclL
- 10.180.03d: urúṃ devébhyo akṛṇor ulokám†
metric = cLllllcclclL
- 10.182.02a: nárāśámso no avatu prayājé
metric = ClLllcclclL
- 10.191.03a: samānó mántraḥ sámītiḥ samāní
metric = cLlllCclclL

Final cadence, rhythm and melody matches

Original: 724/39688 match 'llLcLcL)'
Perms: min=35, max=81, mean=55.78, std=6.91
Percentile: 100.0th

Original matches:

- 1.001.01c: hótāraṃ ratnadhātamaṃ
metric = Llllclcl
- 1.001.07a: úpa tvāgne divé-dive
metric = Clllclcl
- 1.001.07b: dóṣāvastar dhiyá vayám
metric = Llllclcl
- 1.003.03c: á yātaṃ rudravartanī
metric = Llllclcl
- 1.003.07a: ómāsaś carṣaṇīdhṛto
metric = Llllclcl
- 1.005.01c: sákhāya stómavāhasaḥ
metric = ClLLclcl
- 1.005.03a: sá ghā no yóga á bhuvat
metric = ClLLclcl
- 1.006.02c: sóṇā dhṛṣṇú nṛvāhasā
metric = Llllclcl
- 1.007.07c: ná vindhe asya suṣṭutím
metric = Clllclcl
- 1.007.08a: vṛṣā yūthéva váṃsagaḥ
metric = ClLLclcl
- 1.007.08c: íśāno ápratiṣkutaḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 1.009.01b: víśvebhiḥ somapárvabhiḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 1.009.03b: stómebhir viśvacarṣaṇe
metric = Llllclcl
- 1.011.06c: úpātiṣṭhanta girvaṇo
metric = Clllclcl
- 1.013.08b: hótārā daíviyā kaví
metric = Llllclcl
- 1.014.01b: víśvebhiḥ sómapítaye
metric = Llllclcl

- 1.014.10c: píbā mitrásyā dhámabhiḥ
metric = CllLcLcl
- 1.016.01c: índra tvā súrācakṣasaḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.017.09a: prá vām aśnotu suṣṭutír
metric = Clllclcl
- 1.018.03c: rákṣā ṇo brahmaṇas pate
metric = Llllclcl
- 1.019.04b: ánādhṛṣṭāsa ójasā
metric = Clllclcl
- 1.020.06b: tvāṣṭur devásya níṣkṛtam
metric = LllLcLcl
- 1.021.05b: índrāgnī rákṣa ubjatam
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.022.03c: táyā yajñám mimikṣatam
metric = CllLclcl
- 1.022.07b: vásóś citrásya rádhasaḥ
metric = CllLcLcl
- 1.022.09c: tvāṣṭāraṃ sómapītaye
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.022.16a: áto devá avantu no
metric = CllLclcl
- 1.023.08b: dévāsaḥ púṣarātayaḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.023.10a: víśvān devān havāmahe
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.023.12b: áto jātá avantu naḥ
metric = CllLclcl
- 1.023.17c: tá no hinvantu adhvarám
metric = Llllclcl
- 1.023.18c: síndhubhyaḥ kártuvaṃ havíḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.023.23a: ápo adyānv acāriṣaṃ

- metric = LllLclcl
- 1.025.02b: jihīlānāsya rīradhaḥ
metric = clLLclcl
- 1.026.04a: ā no barhī riśādaso
metric = LllLcLcl
- 1.027.08c: vājo asti śravāyiaḥ
metric = LlllcLcl
- 1.027.12b: daīvyah ketúḥ śṛṇotu nah
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.030.01c: máṃhiṣṭhaṃ siñca índubhiḥ
metric = LlllcLcl
- 1.030.05b: gírvāho vīra yāsya te
metric = LlllcLcl
- 1.030.07a: yóge-yoge tavástaraṃ
metric = LlllcLcl
- 1.030.07b: vāje-vāje havāmahe
metric = Llllcclcl
- 1.030.09a: ánu pratnāsya ókaso
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 1.036.03a: prá tvā dūtāṃ vṛṇīmahe
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.036.12b: ágne devéṣu ápiyam
metric = LllLcLcl
- 1.037.05a: prá śamsā góṣu ághniyaṃ
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 1.039.05d: dévāsaḥ sárva yā viśá
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.040.01a: út tiṣṭha brahmaṇas pate
metric = Llllcclcl
- 1.041.02c: áriṣṭaḥ sárva edhate
metric = ClLLclcl
- 1.044.07d: ágne devāṃ ihá dravát
metric = LllLcLcl

- 1.044.11a: ní tvā yajñásya sádhanam
metric = LllLcLcl
- 1.045.06d: ágne havyáya vólhave
metric = LllLcLcl
- 1.047.04b: mádhvā yajñám mimikṣatam
metric = LllLcLcl
- 1.050.10d: áganma jyótir uttamám
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 1.050.12c: átho hāridravéṣu me
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 1.053.05b: sám vājebhiḥ puruścandraír abhidyubhiḥ
metric = LllLclllLcLcl
- 1.075.01b: váco devápsarastamam
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 1.075.02b: ágne vedhastama priyám
metric = LllLcLcl
- 1.075.04b: ágne mitró asi priyáh
metric = LllLcLcl
- 1.075.05b: yájā devāṃ ṛtám bṛhát
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 1.078.02a: tám u tvā gótamo girá
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 1.078.03a: tám u tvā vājasátamam
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 1.078.04a: tám u tvā vṛtrahántamam
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 1.080.02b: sómaḥ śyenābhṛtaḥ sutáḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 1.080.05a: índro vṛtrásya dódhataḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 1.080.09d: índrāya bráhma údyatam
metric = LllLcLcl

- 1.081.09b: víśvam puṣyanti vāriyam
metric = LlllcLcl
- 1.084.11b: sómaṃ śrīṇanti pṛśnayaḥ
metric = LlllcLcl
- 1.084.11d: vājraṃ hinvanti sāyakaṃ
metric = LlllcLcl
- 1.090.06c: mādhvīr naḥ santu óṣadhīḥ
metric = LlllcLcl
- 1.091.08b: rákṣā rājann aghāyatáḥ
metric = LlllcLcl
- 1.092.15b: áśvāñ adyāruṇāñ uṣaḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 1.093.02c: tásmāi dhattaṃ suvīriyaṃ
metric = LlllcLcl
- 1.093.09c: sám devatrā babhūvathuḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 1.093.10a: ágnīṣomāv anéna vāṃ
metric = LlllcLcl
- 1.093.11a: ágnīṣomāv imāni no
metric = LlllcLcl
- 1.105.05d: kúva pratná va áhutir
metric = ClLlLcLcl
- 1.105.06c: kád aryamṇó mahás pathá
metric = ClLlLcLcl
- 1.105.09b: tátrā me nābhir átatā
metric = LllLcLcl
- 1.105.10b: mādhye tasthúr mahó diváḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 1.105.12b: dévāsaḥ supravācanám
metric = LlllcLcl
- 1.114.01d: víśvam puṣṭám grāme asmínn anāturám
metric = LllLllLlLcLcl
- 1.126.07b: má me dabhrāṇi manyathāḥ

- metric = LllLclcl
- 1.127.02c: víprebhiḥ śukra mánmabhiḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 1.127.06d: ādad dhavyāni ādadír
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.127.10e: víśvāsu kṣāsu jóguve
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.128.04d: krátvā vedhá iṣūyaté
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.128.04e: víśvā jātāni paspaśe
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.129.10g: rírikṣantaṃ cid adrivaḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 1.129.11g: rakṣohāṇaṃ tvā jíjanad vaso
metric = llClLLclcl
- 1.130.01g: māmhiṣṭhaṃ vājasātaye
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.130.03e: síṣāsann āngirastamaḥ
metric = ClLLclcl
- 1.130.08e: tvācam kṛṣṇām arandhayat
metric = ClLLclcl
- 1.132.05e: bādhe arcanti ójasā
metric = Llllclcl
- 1.133.04b: abhivlaṅgaír apāvapaḥ
metric = clLLclcl
- 1.134.02c: góbhiḥ krāṇá abhídyavaḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.135.02e: sómo devéṣu hūyate
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.135.08a: átrāha tát vahethe mádhva áhutiṃ
metric = LLclclllclcl
- 1.136.01c: svádiṣṭhaṃ mṛḷayádbhiyām+
metric = Llllclcl

- 1.136.05g: stómair ābhúṣati vratám
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.137.01b: góśrītā matsarā imé
metric = LlllcLcl
- 1.137.01c: sómāso matsarā imé
metric = LlllcLcl
- 1.137.01d: á rājānā divisṛṣā
metric = Llllcclcl
- 1.139.01e: nābhā saṃdāyi návyasī
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.139.05a: śácībhir naḥ śacīvasū
metric = Clllclcl
- 1.139.08d: yád vaś citráṃ yugé-yuge
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.139.09d: téṣāṃ devéṣu áyatir
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.142.08b: hótārā daíviyā kaví
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.142.09a: śúcir devéṣu árpitā
metric = Clllclcl
- 1.162.22a: sugáviyaṃ no vājí suásviam
metric = cCllllLclcl
- 1.170.02c: tébhiḥ kalpasva sādhyā
metric = Llllcclcl
- 1.175.02a: á nas te gantu matsaró
metric = Llllcclcl
- 1.182.02c: pūrṇāṃ ráthaṃ vahethe mádhva ácitaṃ
metric = lClclllLclcl
- 1.187.05b: táva svādiṣṭha té pito
metric = Clllclcl
- 1.187.07c: átrā cin no madho pito
metric = Llllcclcl

- 1.188.07b: hótārā daíviyā kaví
metric = LllLclcl
- 1.188.09a: tváṣṭā rūpāṇi hí prabhúḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 2.001.16a: yé stotṛbhyo góagrām ásvapeśasam
metric = LllLllllclcl
- 2.002.12c: vásvo rāyāḥ puruścandrāsya bhúyasah
metric = LllLclllclcl
- 2.002.13a: yé stotṛbhyo góagrām ásvapeśasam
metric = LllLllllclcl
- 2.005.05d: svásāro yá idam̐ yayúḥ
metric = ClLLclcl
- 2.005.06d: yávo vṛṣṭíva modate
metric = ClLLclcl
- 2.032.07c: tasyai viśpátniyai havíḥ
metric = lllLclcl
- 2.041.07b: ásvāvad yātam aśvinā
metric = Llllclcl
- 2.041.11b: ná naḥ paścād agham̐ naśat
metric = ClLLclcl
- 2.041.15b: dévāsaḥ púṣarātayaḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 3.012.01a: índrāgnī á gataḥ sutam̐
metric = LllLclcl
- 3.012.09a: índrāgnī rocaná divāḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 3.013.06c: sám naḥ śocā marúdvṛdho
metric = Llllclcl
- 3.016.03c: túvidyumna várṣiṣṭhasya prajāvato
metric = ClLcLllllclcl
- 3.021.02d: śréṣṭham̐ no dhehi vāriyam
metric = Llllclcl
- 3.024.03a: ágne dyumnéna jāgrve

- metric = LllLclcl
- 3.027.08c: vípro yajñásya sádhanah
metric = LllLcLcl
- 3.028.01c: prātaḥsāvé dhiyāvaso
metric = lllLclcl
- 3.029.04a: íḷāyās tvā padé vayam
metric = ClllcLcl
- 3.029.04d: ágne havyāya vólhave
metric = LllLcLcl
- 3.037.05a: índram vṛtráya hántave
metric = LllLcLcl
- 3.040.04c: kṣáyam candrása índavaḥ
metric = ClllcLcl
- 3.040.05c: táva dyukṣása índavaḥ
metric = ClllcLcl
- 3.041.01c: háribhyām yāhi adrivaḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 3.044.02b: súr्याm haryánn arocayaḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 3.044.05a: índro haryántam árjunaḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 3.044.05b: vájram śukraír abhívṛtam
metric = LllLcLcl
- 3.045.02d: índro dṛḷhā+ cid ārujáḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 3.051.12a: prá te aśnotu kukṣiyóḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 3.052.01c: índra prātár juṣasva naḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 3.052.02c: túbhyam havyáni sisrate
metric = LllLclcl
- 3.052.04b: prātaḥsāvé juṣasva naḥ
metric = lllLclcl

- 3.062.09c: sá naḥ pūṣávitá bhuvat
metric = CllLcLcl
- 3.062.17c: drághišṭhābhiḥ śucivratā
metric = Llllclcl
- 4.007.02b: bhúvad devásya cétanam
metric = CllLcLcl
- 4.030.02b: víśvā cakréva vāvṛtuḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 4.030.14c: ávāhann indra sámbaram
metric = Clllclcl
- 4.030.16b: párāvṛktaṃ śatákratuḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 4.030.17c: índro vidvám̐ apārayat
metric = LllLclcl
- 4.031.02b: máṃhiṣṭho matsad ándhasaḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 4.032.02a: bhṛmíś cid ghāsi tútujir
metric = Clllclcl
- 4.032.05a: sá naś citrábhir adrivo
metric = CllLclcl
- 4.032.14c: sómānām indra somapāḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 4.037.05c: índrasvantaṃ havāmahe
metric = Llllclcl
- 4.037.07a: ví no vājā ṛbhukṣaṇaḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 4.047.01a: váyo śukró ayāmi te
metric = LllLclcl
- 4.047.03d: á yātaṃ sómapītaye
metric = LllLclcl
- 4.055.10c: índro no rádhasá gamat
metric = LllLclcl

- 4.056.07b: táranti pípratī ṛtám
metric = CllLclcl
- 5.005.11c: sváhā devébhiyo havíḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 5.006.06b: víśvam puṣyanti vāriyam
metric = LlllcLcl
- 5.010.05b: bhrájanto yanti dhṛṣṇuyá
metric = Lllclcl
- 5.013.01a: árcantas tvā havāmahe
metric = Lllclcl
- 5.013.05a: tvám agne vājasátamaṃ
metric = LlllcLcl
- 5.013.05b: víprā vardhanti súṣṭutam
metric = LlllcLcl
- 5.018.03a: tám vo dīrghāyusociṣaṃ
metric = LllLclcl
- 5.019.05a: kríḷan no raśma á bhuvah
metric = LlllcLcl
- 5.020.01c: tám no gīrbhíḥ śravāyiyam
metric = LllLclcl
- 5.020.03a: hótāraṃ tvā vṛṇīmahe
metric = Lllclcl
- 5.020.03d: prāyasvanto havāmahe
metric = Cllclcl
- 5.021.02c: srúcas tvā yanti ānuśák
metric = Cllclcl
- 5.022.04d: stómair vardhanti átrayo
metric = LlllcLcl
- 5.023.03c: hótāraṃ sádmasu priyám
metric = LllLclcl
- 5.024.04a: tám tvā śociṣṭha dīdivah
metric = Lllclcl
- 5.025.03c: ágne rāyó didīhi nah
metric = Lllclcl

- metric = LllLclcl
- 5.026.04c: hótāraṃ tvā vṛṇīmahe
metric = Llllclcl
- 5.027.04d: dádan medhám ṛtāyaté
metric = ClLLclcl
- 5.035.06d: hávante vājasātaye
metric = ClLLclcl
- 5.038.01c: ádhā no viśvacarṣaṇe
metric = Clllclcl
- 5.038.02a: yád īm indra śravāyīyam
metric = ClllLcll
- 5.039.03a: yát te ditsú prarādhiyam
metric = LllLclcl
- 5.039.05c: tásmā u bráhmavāhase
metric = LllLclcl
- 5.039.05d: gíro vardhanti átrayo
metric = ClllLcll
- 5.039.05e: gíraḥ śumbhanti átrayaḥ
metric = ClllLcll
- 5.052.02b: sákhāyaḥ sánti dhṛṣṇuyá
metric = ClLLclcl
- 5.052.03b: áti śkandanti sárvariḥ
metric = ClllLcll
- 5.052.04b: stómaṃ yajñám ca dhṛṣṇuyá
metric = LllLclcl
- 5.052.05a: árhanto yé sudánavo
metric = LllLclcl
- 5.052.09d: ádrim bhindanti ójasā
metric = Llllclcl
- 5.052.12d: úmā āsan dṛśí tviṣé
metric = Llllclcl
- 5.052.14a: ácha rṣe mārutaṃ gaṇám
metric = ClLLclcl

- 5.053.13d: rádho viśvāyu saúbhagam
metric = LllLcLcl
- 5.056.02a: yáthā cin mányase hṛdá
metric = ClLLclcl
- 5.061.04b: máryāso bhádrajānayaḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 5.061.09b: práti śyāvāya vartaním
metric = ClLLclcl
- 5.061.16b: puruścandrā riśādasah
metric = clLLclcl
- 5.064.02d: víśvāsu kṣāsu jóguve
metric = LllLcLcl
- 5.064.03d: áhiṃsānasya saścire
metric = ClLLclcl
- 5.068.01c: máhikṣatrāv ṛtám bṛhát
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 5.071.01a: á no gantaṃ riśādasā
metric = Llllclcl
- 5.073.06b: nārā sumnéna cétasā
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 5.074.06d: ávobhir vājinīvasū
metric = ClLLclcl
- 5.074.08b: yáyiṣṭho+ yātu aśvinā
metric = ClLLclcl
- 5.074.09c: arvācīná vicetasā
metric = lllLclcl
- 5.074.09d: víbhiḥ śyenéva díyatam
metric = ClLLclcl
- 5.075.02d: súṣumnā síndhuvāhasā
metric = ClLLclcl
- 5.075.05d: ní yātho ádvayāvinam
metric = ClLLclcl

- 5.079.01b: úṣo rāyē divítmatī
metric = CllLcLcl
- 5.079.01e: sújāte áśvasūṅṛte
metric = CllLcLcl
- 5.079.02e: sújāte áśvasūṅṛte
metric = CllLcLcl
- 5.079.03a: sá no adyábharádvasur
metric = LllLcLcl
- 5.079.03e: sújāte áśvasūṅṛte
metric = CllLcLcl
- 5.079.04e: sújāte áśvasūṅṛte
metric = CllLcLcl
- 5.079.05e: sújāte áśvasūṅṛte
metric = CllLcLcl
- 5.079.06e: sújāte áśvasūṅṛte
metric = CllLcLcl
- 5.079.07e: sújāte áśvasūṅṛte
metric = CllLcLcl
- 5.079.08e: sújāte áśvasūṅṛte
metric = CllLcLcl
- 5.079.09e: sújāte áśvasūṅṛte
metric = CllLcLcl
- 5.079.10e: sújāte áśvasūṅṛte
metric = CllLcLcl
- 5.082.01c: śráyiṣṭhaṃ+ sarvadhátamaṃ
metric = ClllLcLcl
- 5.086.05c: árhantā cit puró dadhe
metric = LlllLcLcl
- 6.002.09d: vánā vṛścánti śíkvasaḥ
metric = CllLcLcl
- 6.015.17c: yám añkūyántam áñayann
metric = CllLcLcl
- 6.016.02a: sá no mandrábhir adhvaré

- metric = CllLclcl
- 6.016.03c: ágne yajñéṣu sukrato
metric = LllLclcl
- 6.016.05b: dívodāsāya sunvaté
metric = Clllclcl
- 6.016.15b: sám idhe dasyuhántamam
metric = Clllclcl
- 6.016.19c: dívodāsasya sátpatiḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 6.016.22b: stómaṃ yajñám ca dhr̥ṣṇuyá
metric = LllLclcl
- 6.016.30c: rákṣā ṇo brahmaṇas kave
metric = Llllclcl
- 6.016.31a: yó no agne duréva á
metric = Llllclcl
- 6.016.31c: tásmān naḥ pāhi áṃhasaḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 6.016.35a: gárbhe mātúḥ pitúṣ pitá
metric = LllLclcl
- 6.016.45a: úd agne bhārata dyumád
metric = Clllclcl
- 6.042.02b: sómebhiḥ somapátamam
metric = Llllclcl
- 6.043.03b: máde dṛ̥ḷhá+ avásṛjaḥ
metric = CllLclcl
- 6.045.04a: sákhāyo bráhmavāhase
metric = CllLclcl
- 6.045.10a: tám u tvā satya somapā
metric = Clllclcl
- 6.045.12b: vājāṃ indra śraváiyān
metric = Llllclcl
- 6.045.19b: sákhāyaṃ kīricódanam
metric = Clllclcl

- 6.045.21c: gómadbhir gopate dhr̥ṣát
metric = Llllclcl
- 6.046.06b: rájan devéṣu hūmahe
metric = LllLclcl
- 6.046.10b: abhipraghnánti dhr̥ṣṇuyá
metric = clLLclcl
- 6.047.23d: dívodāsād asāniṣam
metric = ClLLclcl
- 6.048.10b: ádabdhair áprayutvabhiḥ
metric = ClLLclcl
- 6.051.15b: índrajyeṣṭhā abhídyavaḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 6.052.08a: yó vo devā ghr̥tásnunā
metric = Llllclcl
- 6.052.09c: sum̥ṛṭikā+ bhavantu naḥ
metric = clLLclcl
- 6.053.03a: áditsantaṃ cid āghr̥ṇe
metric = ClLLclcl
- 6.053.08a: yám pūṣan brahmacódanīm
metric = Llllclcl
- 6.055.02b: íśānaṃ rádhaso maháḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 6.055.05b: svásur jārāḥ śṛṇotu naḥ
metric = ClLLclcl
- 6.056.02c: índro vr̥trāṇi jighnate
metric = LllLclcl
- 6.057.03b: hárī anyásya sámbr̥tā
metric = ClLLclcl
- 6.057.03c: tábhyām vr̥trāṇi jighnate
metric = LllLclcl
- 6.059.01d: índrāgnī jívatho yuvám
metric = LllLclcl

- 6.059.04a: yá indrāgnī sutéṣu vāṃ
metric = Clllclcl
- 6.059.07c: má no asmín mahādhané
metric = LllLclcl
- 6.059.10a: índrāgnī ukthavāhasā
metric = Llllclcl
- 6.060.08c: índrāgnī tábhir á gatam
metric = LllLclcl
- 6.060.09c: índrāgnī sómapītaye
metric = LllLclcl
- 6.061.06c: rádā pūṣéva naḥ saním
metric = CllLclcl
- 6.061.09b: svásṛ̥ anyá ṛ̥távarī
metric = CllLclcl
- 6.075.16b: śáraye bráhmasaṃśite
metric = CllLclcl
- 7.015.05c: ágre yajñásya śócataḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 7.015.06c: yájiṣṭho havjaváhanaḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 7.031.01c: sákhāyaḥ somapāvane
metric = Clllclcl
- 7.031.06b: puroyodhás ca vṛ̥trahan
metric = clLLclcl
- 7.032.04d: háribhyāṃ yāhi óka á
metric = Clllclcl
- 7.032.16d: nákiṣ ṭvā góṣu vṛ̥ṇvate
metric = CllLclcl
- 7.055.01b: víśvā rūpāṇi āviśán
metric = LllLclcl
- 7.066.06b: ádabdhasya vratásya yé
metric = Clllclcl
- 7.074.03d: má no mardhiṣṭam á gatam

metric = LlllcLcl

7.074.04d: á devā yātam asmayú
metric = LlllcLcl

7.094.01b: índrāgnī pūrviyāstutiḥ
metric = LlllcLcl

7.094.03a: má pāpatvāya no narā
metric = LllLclcl

7.094.06b: prāyasvanto havāmahe
metric = Clllclcl

7.094.11b: yá mandāná cid á girá
metric = LllLclcl

7.096.04c: sárasvantaṃ havāmahe
metric = Clllclcl

7.103.01c: vácam parjānyajinivātā
metric = LllLclcl

8.001.06a: vásyāṃ indrāsi me pitúr
metric = LlllcLcl

8.001.07d: prá gāyatrā agāsiṣuḥ
metric = Clllclcl

8.001.16d: ádhā te vaśmi suṣṭutím
metric = Clllclcl

8.002.39c: yé asmin kāmam áśriyan
metric = LllLclcl

8.003.06d: índre svānása° índavaḥ
metric = LllLclcl

8.003.22c: ádād rāyó vibódhanam
metric = Clllclcl

8.004.03a: yáthā gauró apá kṛtām
metric = Clllclcl

8.004.18d: máṃhiṣṭho vājasātaye
metric = LllLclcl

8.005.05a: máṃhiṣṭhā vājasātamā
metric = LlllcLcl

- 8.005.13b: yáviṣṭaṃ túyam á gatam
metric = LllLcLcl
- 8.005.14c: mádhvo rātásya dhiṣṇiyā
metric = LllLcLcl
- 8.005.25a: yáthā cit kaṇvam ávatam
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 8.005.25c: átriṃ śiñjāram aśvinā
metric = LllLcLcl
- 8.005.28b: híraṇyābhīsum aśvinā
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 8.005.37c: yáthā cic caidiyāḥ kaśúḥ
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 8.006.01c: stómair vatsásya vāvṛdhe
metric = LllLcLcl
- 8.006.03b: stómair yajñásya sādhanam
metric = LllLcLcl
- 8.006.06a: ví cid vṛtrásya dódhato
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 8.006.11b: gíraḥ śumbhāmi kaṇvavát
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 8.006.21b: kaṇvā ukthéna vāvṛdhuḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 8.006.24c: ágre vikṣú pradídayat
metric = LllLcLcl
- 8.006.30b: jyótiṣ paśyanti vāsarám
metric = LllLcLcl
- 8.006.31b: víśve vardhanti paúṃsiyam
metric = LllLcLcl
- 8.006.36b: háribhyāṃ haryatābhiyām
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 8.006.37c: hávante vājasātaye
metric = ClLLcLcl

- 8.006.38a: ánu tvā ródasī ubhé
metric = CllLclcl
- 8.006.38c: ánu svānása° índavaḥ
metric = CllLcLcl
- 8.006.40b: vṛṣā vajrī aroravīt
metric = CllLclcl
- 8.006.43c: kāṇvā ukthéna vāvṛdhuḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.007.19c: vārdhān kāṇvāsya mánmabhiḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 8.007.21b: stómebhir vṛktabarhiṣaḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.008.07b: á no gantaṃ suvarvidā
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.008.09c: áriprā vṛtrahantamā
metric = CllLclcl
- 8.008.10b: átiṣṭhad vājinīvasū
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.008.11d: áśamsīt kāvīyāḥ kavīḥ
metric = ClllLcL
- 8.008.17a: á no gantaṃ riśādasā
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.008.22b: gíro vardhantu ásvinā
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.008.22c: púrutrā vṛtrahantamā
metric = CllLclcl
- 8.009.16c: ví āvar devi á matīm
metric = ClllLcL
- 8.009.21c: yád vā sumnébhir ukthiyā
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.012.11a: gárbho yajñásya devayúḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.012.20b: sómebhiḥ somapátamam

- metric = Llllclcl
- 8.012.22a: índraṃ vr̥trāya hántave
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.013.05b: yát tvā sunvánta ímahe
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.013.13b: háve madhyāṃdine diváḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.015.02b: sáho dādhāra ródasī
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.015.03b: éko vr̥trāṇi jighnase
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.015.11b: éko vr̥trāṇi tośase
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.015.13b: víśvā rūpāṇi āviśán
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.017.05a: á te siñcāmi kuṣṭiyór
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.017.08c: índro vr̥trāṇi jighnate
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.018.17a: té no bhadrēṇa śármaṇā
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.019.21c: yájiṣṭhaṃ havyaváhanam
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.019.25a: yád agne mártiyas tuvám
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.019.28c: sádā devásya mártiyah
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.019.31b: índhānaḥ siṣṇav á dade
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.019.36a: ádān me paurukutsiyáh
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.020.01b: prásthāvāno mápa sthātā samanyavaḥ
metric = Llllllllclcl

- 8.020.07c: váhante áhрутapsavaḥ
metric = CllLclcl
- 8.020.21a: gávaś cid ghā samanyavaḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.021.01c: váje citráṃ havāmahe
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.021.04d: víśvebhiḥ sómapītaye
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.021.11a: tváyā ha svid yujá vayám
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.021.13a: abhrātrvyó anā tuvám
metric = lllLclcl
- 8.022.05b: híraṇyābhiśur aśvinā
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.022.08c: á yātaṃ sómapītaye
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.023.05b: stávāno deviyá kṛpá
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.023.10a: áchā no áṅgirastamaṃ
metric = CllLclcl
- 8.023.23b: jyáyiṣṭhābhir+ viaśvavát
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.023.24b: stómebhi sthūrayūpavát
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.024.14b: dáḳṣam pṛñcántam abravam
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.024.17b: nákiṣ ṭe pūrviyástutim
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.024.25b: yénā daṃsiṣṭha kṛtvane
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.024.26b: návyam daṃsiṣṭha sányase
metric = Llllclcl

- 8.025.12b: áriṣyantah sudánave
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.026.04b: rátho yātu śrutó narā
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.026.05b: á manyethāṃ vṛṣaṇvasū
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.026.13a: yó vāṃ yajñébhīr ávr̥to
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.026.16b: stómo dūtó huvaṇ narā
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.027.10b: dévāso ásti ápiyam
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.027.15a: prá vaḥ śamsāmi adruhaḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.027.16d: áriṣṭah sārva edhate
metric = CllLclcl
- 8.027.19d: yád vā madhyāṃdine diváh
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.027.20d: úpa stheyāma mádhya á
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.027.22c: aśyāma tát ādityā júhvato havír
metric = llcCllllclcl
- 8.028.03a: té no gopá apāciyās
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.031.04b: ásaścanti divé–dive
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.032.02c: vádhīd ugró riṇánn apáh
metric = CllLclcl
- 8.032.12a: sá naḥ śakrás cid á śakad
metric = CllLclcl
- 8.032.22c: dhénā indrāvacākaśat
metric = LlllcLcl
- 8.033.01d: pári stotāra āsate

- metric = CllLclcl
- 8.033.02d: índra svabdíva váṃsagaḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.033.03a: káṇvebhir dhṛṣṇav á dhṛṣád
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.033.15d: mādāya dyukṣa somapāḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.034.04b: hávante vājasātaye
metric = CllLclcl
- 8.035.04d: íṣaṃ no voḷham aśvinā
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.035.05d: íṣaṃ no voḷham aśvinā
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.035.06d: íṣaṃ no voḷham aśvinā
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.035.10d: úrjaṃ no dhattam aśvinā
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.035.11d: úrjaṃ no dhattam aśvinā
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.035.12d: úrjaṃ no dhattam aśvinā
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.038.01c: índrāgnī tāsya bodhatam
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.038.02c: índrāgnī tāsya bodhatam
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.038.03c: índrāgnī tāsya bodhatam
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.038.04c: índrāgnī á gataṃ narā
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.038.05c: índrāgnī á gataṃ narā
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.038.06c: índrāgnī á gataṃ narā
metric = LllLclcl

- 8.038.07c: índrāgnī sómapītaye
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.038.08c: índrāgnī sómapītaye
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.038.09c: índrāgnī sómapītaye
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.039.01f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.039.02f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.039.03f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.039.04f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.039.05f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.039.06f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.039.07f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.039.08f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.039.09f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.039.10f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.040.01b: sáhantā dásatho rayím
metric = CllLclcl
- 8.040.01f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.040.02g: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl

8.040.03f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl

8.040.04f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl

8.040.05f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl

8.040.06f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl

8.040.07f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl

8.040.08d: úhānā yanti síndhavo
metric = ClllcLcl

8.040.08f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl

8.040.09f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl

8.040.10f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl

8.040.11f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl

8.041.01f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl

8.041.02f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl

8.041.03f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl

8.041.04f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl

8.041.05f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl

8.041.06f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl

8.041.07f: nábhantām anyaké same

- metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.041.08f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.041.09a: yásya śvetā vicakṣaṇā
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.041.09f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.041.10f: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.042.04c: nāsatyā sómapītaye
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.042.04d: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.042.05a: yáthā vām átrir aśvinā
metric = CllLclcl
- 8.042.05c: nāsatyā sómapītaye
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.042.05d: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.042.06c: nāsatyā sómapītaye
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.042.06d: nábhantām anyaké same
metric = ClllcLcl
- 8.043.24b: ádhyakṣaṃ dhármaṇām imám
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.043.28c: táṃ tvā gīrbhír havāmahe
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.044.02b: várdhasvānéna mánmanā
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.044.04c: ágne śukrása īrate
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.044.05c: ágne havyā juṣasva naḥ
metric = LllLclcl

- 8.044.08c: ágne yajñam naya rtuthá
metric = LLLLcLcL
- 8.044.20a: ádabdhasya svadhávato
metric = ClllcLcL
- 8.044.22c: ágne sakhyásya bodhi nah
metric = LLLLcLcL
- 8.044.23a: yád agne syám ahám tuvám
metric = ClllcLcL
- 8.044.25c: gíro vāsrása īrate
metric = ClllcLcL
- 8.045.26c: átrādediṣṭa paúṃsiyam
metric = LlllcLcL
- 8.045.27b: vídāno ahnavāiyám
metric = ClllcLcL
- 8.045.38b: ásinvan bhūri āvayaḥ
metric = ClllcLcL
- 8.045.39b: hārī gr̥bhṇe sumádrathā
metric = ClllcLcL
- 8.046.05a: dádhāno gómad ásvavat
metric = ClllcLcL
- 8.046.19d: jyáyīṣṭham+ codayanmate
metric = ClllcLcL
- 8.046.22b: úṣṭrānām viṃśatím śatā
metric = LlllcLcL
- 8.046.23a: dáśa śyāvā ṛdhádrayo
metric = ClllcLcL
- 8.047.01c: yám ādityā abhí druhó
metric = ClllcLcL
- 8.047.02b: ádityāso apákṛtim
metric = LlllcLcL
- 8.047.13b: dévāso ásti duṣkṛtám
metric = LlllcLcL

- 8.050.06b: víbhūtiṃ rādhaso maháḥ
metric = CllLclcl
- 8.051.02b: cháyānaṃ jívrim úddhitam
metric = CllLcLcl
- 8.051.07d: dānaṃ devásya pṛcyate
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.052.01b: sómaṃ śakrápibaḥ sutám
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.052.04b: váje vājiñ chatakrate
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.052.06a: yásmai tuvāṃ vaso dānáya máṃhase
metric = LlcLclllLclcl
- 8.053.03b: mádhvaḥ siñcantu ádrayaḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.054.03b: dévāso gántanópa naḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.054.05d: bhágo dānáya vṛtrahan
metric = CllLclcl
- 8.060.01b: hótāraṃ tvā vṛṇīmahe
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.060.03d: víprebhiḥ śukra mánmabhiḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.060.14b: jámbhāso yád vitíṣṭhase
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.060.20a: má no rákṣa á veśid āghṛṇīvaso
metric = LllcLlllclcl
- 8.062.02b: ékaḥ kṛṣṭír ayásiyaḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.062.02d: víśvā jātāni ójasā
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.062.11c: arātivá cid adrivo
metric = clllclcl
- 8.063.08c: právaś cakrásya vartaním

- metric = LllLclcl
- 8.065.03a: á tvā gīrbhír mahám urúṃ
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.065.06b: práyasvanto havāmahe
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.066.01a: tárobhir vo vidádvasum
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.066.06b: mādāya dyukṣa somapāḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.067.01c: sumṛṭlikām+ abhíṣṭaye
metric = clllclcl
- 8.067.06a: yád vaḥ śrāntāya sunvaté
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.067.07c: ádityā ádbhutainasaḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.067.10c: sumṛṭlikām+ abhíṣṭaye
metric = clllclcl
- 8.067.11c: mákis tokásya no riṣat
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.067.17a: śásvantam hí pracetasah
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.068.02b: śácīvo vísvayā mate
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.068.10a: tám tvā yajñébhír īmahe
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.068.17c: sácā pūtákratau sanam
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.069.03b: sómam śrīṇanti pṛśnayaḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.069.09d: índrāya bráhma údyatam
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.069.18a: ánu pratnásya ókasaḥ
metric = Clllclcl

- 8.072.06b: ásvāvad yójanam brhád
metric = LLLLclcl
- 8.073.01a: úd irāthām ṛtāyaté
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.073.04b: kúha śyenéva petathuḥ
metric = CllLclcl
- 8.073.06b: nédiṣṭhaṃ yāmi āpiyam
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.074.06c: júhvānāso yatásrucaḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.074.08c: táyā vardhasva súṣṭutaḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.074.15c: ném āpo aśvadātarah
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.074.15d: śáviṣṭhād asti mártiyah
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.075.02b: áchā voco vidúṣṭarah
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.075.06c: vṛṣṇe codasva suṣṭutím
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.075.10a: námas te agna ójase
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.075.11b: ágne saṃvéṣiṣo rayím
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.075.12a: má no asmín mahādhané
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.075.12b: párā varḡ bhārabhṛd yathā
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.076.05c: índraṃ gīrbhír havāmahe
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.076.06a: índram pratnéna mánmanā
metric = LllLclcl

- 8.076.11a: ánu tvā ródasī ubhé
metric = CllLclcl
- 8.077.03c: právr̥ddho dasyuhábhavat
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.077.05c: índro brahmábhya íd vr̥dhé
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.077.06a: nír āvidhyad giríbhya á
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.078.09b: kámo gavyúr hiraṇyayúḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.079.07c: bhāvā naḥ soma sám̐ hṛdé
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.080.02b: ámr̥dhro vājasātaye
metric = Cl̥lLclcl
- 8.082.09a: yám̐ te śyenáḥ padābharat
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.083.05b: íśānāśo riśādasah
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.083.05c: ném ādityā aghásya yát
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.083.08a: prá bhrātr̥tvám̐ sudānavo
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.083.09b: índrajyeṣṭhā abhídyavaḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.087.06b: víprāso vājasātaye
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.088.01d: índram̐ gīrbhír navāmahe
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.088.06d: mām̐hiṣṭho vājasātaye
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.089.04b: śrávaś cit te asad bṛhát
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.092.11b: árvadbhiḥ śakra godare

- metric = Llllclcl
- 8.092.14b: ávr̥tran kámakātayaḥ
metric = ClLLclcl
- 8.092.16a: yás te nūnám śatakratav
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.092.17a: yás te citráśravastamo
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.092.18b: tvádattaḥ satya somapāḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 8.093.12a: ádhā te apratiṣkutaḥ
metric = ClLLclcl
- 8.095.02a: á tvā śukrá acucyavuh
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.095.03b: índra śyenábhṛtaḥ sutám
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.095.06d: síśāsanto vanāmahe
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.102.03a: tváyā ha svid yujá vayám
metric = Clllclcl
- 8.102.08b: tváṣṭā rūpéva tákṣiyā
metric = LllLclcl
- 8.102.19c: áthaitādṛg bharāmi te
metric = ClLLclcl
- 8.102.20a: yád agne káni káni cid
metric = ClLLclcl
- 9.001.03b: máṃhiṣṭho vr̥trahántamaḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 9.001.10b: víśvā vr̥trāṇi jighnate
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.002.04b: ápo arṣanti síndhavaḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 9.005.07b: hótārā daíviyā huve
metric = LllLclcl

- 9.009.06c: krívir devír atarpayat
metric = CllLclcl
- 9.010.03b: sómāso góbhír añjate
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.010.04a: pári svānása° índavo
metric = CllLcLcl
- 9.010.07a: samícīnása āsate
metric = cllLclcl
- 9.011.01a: úpāsmāi gāyatā naraḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 9.011.02b: átharvāṇo aśísrayuḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 9.011.03c: sám̐ rājann oṣadhībhiyaḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.013.03a: pávante vājasātaye
metric = CllLclcl
- 9.013.05b: pávantām á suvīriyam
metric = CllLcLcl
- 9.013.06b: ásṛgram vājasātaye
metric = CllLclcl
- 9.014.02c: pariṣkr̥ṇvānti dharaśám̐
metric = cllLclcl
- 9.015.03c: yádī tuñjānti bhúrṇayaḥ
metric = CllLcLcl
- 9.017.01b: ghnānto vṛtrāṇi bhúrṇayaḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 9.017.06c: dádhānāś cákṣasi priyám̐
metric = CllLclcl
- 9.020.07c: dádhāt stotré suvīriyam
metric = CllLcLcl
- 9.025.04a: víśvā rūpāṇi āviśán̐
metric = LllLclcl

- 9.026.01c: víprāso āṇviyā dhiyā
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.026.02c: índuṃ dhartāram ā divāḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.026.05b: hāriṃ hinvanti ádribhiḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 9.028.02b: sómo devébhiyaḥ sutāḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.029.06a: ā indo pāṛthivaṃ rayiṃ
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.030.05b: hāriṃ hinvanti ádribhiḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 9.031.02b: bhávendo dyumnavárdhanaḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 9.032.02b: hāriṃ hinvanti ádribhiḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 9.032.03b: víśvasyāvivaśan matim
metric = Lllclcl
- 9.033.03c: sómā arṣanti víṣṇave
metric = Lllclcl
- 9.035.03a: tváyā vīreṇa vīravo
metric = ClLclcl
- 9.036.05b: sómo divyāni pāṛthivā
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.038.02b: hāriṃ hinvanti ádribhiḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 9.039.06b: hāriṃ hinvanti ádribhiḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 9.041.04c: áśvāvad vājavat sutāḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.042.03b: pávante vājasātaye
metric = ClLclcl
- 9.042.04c: krāndan devāṃ ajījanat

- metric = LllLclcl
- 9.042.06b: ásvāvad vājavat sutāḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.044.05c: sómo devéṣu ā yamat
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.045.04c: índur devéṣu patyate
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.045.06b: yáyā pītó vicákṣase
metric = ClllLclcl
- 9.045.06c: índo stotré suvīriyam
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.046.03b: práyasvantaḥ camú sutāḥ
metric = ClllLclcl
- 9.046.03c: índraṃ vardhanti kármabhiḥ
metric = LlllLclcl
- 9.046.04c: góbhiḥ śrīṇīta matsarám
metric = Llllclcl
- 9.047.02b: cétante dasyutárhaṇā
metric = LlllLclcl
- 9.048.01a: tám tvā ṇṛṇāni bíbhrataṃ
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.048.03b: rájānaṃ sukrato divāḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 9.050.01b: síndhor ūmér iva svanáḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.050.03b: háriṃ hinvanti ádribhiḥ
metric = ClllLclcl
- 9.051.01a: ádhvāyo ádribhiḥ sutám
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.052.01a: pári dyukṣāḥ sanádrayir
metric = ClllLclcl
- 9.052.02a: táva pratnébhir ádhvabhir
metric = ClllLclcl

- 9.061.02b: dívodāsāya sámbaram
metric = Clllclcl
- 9.061.11c: síṣāsanto vanāmahe
metric = Clllclcl
- 9.061.13c: índuṃ devā ayāsiṣuḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 9.061.16c: jyótir vaiśvānarám bṛhát
metric = Llllclcl
- 9.061.22b: índraṃ vṛtrāya hántave
metric = Llllclcl
- 9.061.30a: yá te bhīmāni áyudhā
metric = Llllclcl
- 9.062.09b: svādiṣṭho ángirobhiyaḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 9.062.17b: ráthe yuñjanti yátave
metric = Clllclcl
- 9.062.30c: dádhat stotré suvīriyam
metric = Clllclcl
- 9.063.25b: sómāḥ śukrása índavaḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 9.064.06b: sómā divyāni pāρθivā
metric = Llllclcl
- 9.064.16a: prá hinvānása índavo
metric = Clllclcl
- 9.064.22a: índrāyendo marútvate
metric = Llllclcl
- 9.064.30b: saṃjagmānó diváḥ kavíḥ
metric = llllclcl
- 9.065.08b: háriṃ hinvānti ádribhiḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 9.065.16a: rájā medhābhir iyate
metric = Llllclcl

- 9.065.19a: árṣā soma dyumáttamo
metric = LlllcLcl
- 9.065.24b: pávantām á suvírīyam
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 9.066.13b: ápo arṣanti síndhavaḥ
metric = LlllcLcl
- 9.066.14b: íyakṣantas tuvótayaḥ
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 9.066.26c: háriścandro marúdgāḥ
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 9.066.27c: dádhat stotré suvírīyam
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 9.067.19a: grāvṇā tunnó abhíṣṭutaḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 9.067.19c: dádhat stotré suvírīyam
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 9.067.26b: várṣiṣṭhaiḥ soma dhámabhiḥ
metric = LlllcLcl
- 9.098.06b: svásāro ádrisaṃhatam
metric = ClLLclcl
- 9.098.09a: sá vāṃ yajñéṣu mānavī
metric = ClLLclcl
- 9.099.01b: dhānus tanvanti paúṃsiyam
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 9.099.02d: háriṃ hinvánti yátave
metric = ClLLcLcl
- 9.100.04d: váraṃ vājíva sānasíḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.101.02b: pariprasyádate sutáḥ
metric = clLLclcl
- 9.101.03b: sómaṃ viśváciyā dhiyá
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.101.07d: ví akhyad ródasī ubhé

- metric = CllLclcl
- 9.101.08c: sómāsaḥ kṛṇvate patháḥ
metric = Llllclcl
- 9.101.13a: prá sunvānāsya ándhaso
metric = CllLcLcl
- 9.101.16d: índrasyābhy èti niṣkṛtám
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.105.05b: índo devápsarastamaḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.106.04a: prá dhanvā soma jágrvir
metric = Clllclcl
- 9.107.05d: nṛbhir dhūtó vicakṣaṇáḥ
metric = CllLclcl
- 9.107.06d: mádhvā yajñám mimikṣa naḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 9.111.03d: ágmann uktháni paúmsiyā
metric = LllLcLcl
- 9.112.01c: tákṣā riṣtám rutám bhiśág
metric = LllLcLcl
- 9.114.04a: yát te rājañ chṛtám havís
metric = Llllclcl
- 10.009.09a: ápo adyānv acāriṣaṃ
metric = LllLclcl
- 10.014.14c: sá no devéṣu á yamad
metric = CllLcLcl
- 10.014.15c: idám náma ṛṣibhyaḥ pūrvajébhiyaḥ
metric = cLccLllclcl
- 10.019.01c: ágnīṣomā punarvasū
metric = Llllclcl
- 10.021.01b: hótāraṃ tvā vṛṇīmahe
metric = Llllclcl
- 10.021.04a: yám agne mányase rayím
metric = CllLclcl

- 10.021.05c: bhúvad dūtó vivásvato
metric = CllLcLcl
- 10.022.01d: gúhā vā cārkr̥ṣe girá
metric = CllLclcl
- 10.024.02e: śréṣṭhaṃ no dhehi vāriyaṃ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.025.07e: mǎ no duḥśáṃsa īsatā
metric = LllLclcl
- 10.032.04c: mātá yán mántur yūthásya pūrviyá
metric = LllLllLclcl
- 10.033.04b: rájānaṃ trāsadasyavam
metric = LllLclcl
- 10.036.02d: tád devánāṃ ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe
metric = LllLcLllLclcl
- 10.036.03d: tád devánāṃ ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe
metric = LllLcLllLclcl
- 10.036.04d: tád devánāṃ ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe
metric = LllLcLllLclcl
- 10.036.05d: tád devánāṃ ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe
metric = LllLcLllLclcl
- 10.036.06d: tád devánāṃ ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe
metric = LllLcLllLclcl
- 10.036.07d: tád devánāṃ ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe
metric = LllLcLllLclcl
- 10.036.08d: tád devánāṃ ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe
metric = LllLcLllLclcl
- 10.036.09d: tád devánāṃ ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe
metric = LllLcLllLclcl
- 10.036.10d: tád devánāṃ ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe
metric = LllLcLllLclcl
- 10.036.11d: tád devánāṃ ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe
metric = LllLcLllLclcl

- 10.036.12d: tād devānām ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe
metric = LLLCllLclcl
- 10.057.02b: tántur devéṣu átataḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.062.06c: návagvo nú dáśagvo áṅgirastamo
metric = ClCCllLclcl
- 10.062.06d: sácā devéṣu maṃhate
metric = CllLclcl
- 10.062.10b: smáddiṣṭī góparīṇasā
metric = LllLclcl
- 10.062.10c: yádus turváś ca māmahe
metric = CllLclcl
- 10.085.03b: yát sampiṃśānti óṣadhim
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.085.04d: ná te aśnāti pāṛthivaḥ
metric = ClllcLcl
- 10.085.05d: sámānām māsā ákṛtiḥ
metric = CllLcLcl
- 10.085.06b: nārāśaṃsí niócanī
metric = lllLcLcl
- 10.085.11b: gāvau te sāmanāv itaḥ
metric = LlllcLcl
- 10.085.28d: pátir bandhéṣu badhyate
metric = CllLclcl
- 10.086.01e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.086.02e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.086.03e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.086.04e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.086.05e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ

metric = LllLcLcł

10.086.06e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcł

10.086.07e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcł

10.086.08e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcł

10.086.09e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcł

10.086.10e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcł

10.086.11e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcł

10.086.12e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcł

10.086.13e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcł

10.086.14e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcł

10.086.15e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcł

10.086.16c: séd īśe yásya romaśaṃ
metric = LllLcłcł

10.086.16e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcł

10.086.17c: séd īśe yásya rámbate
metric = LllLcLcł

10.086.17e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcł

10.086.18b: párasvantaṃ hatáṃ vidat
metric = ClllcLcł

10.086.18e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcł

- 10.086.19e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.086.20e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.086.21e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.086.22e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.086.23e: víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.087.24d: ádabdhaṃ vipra mánmabhiḥ
metric = ClllcLcl
- 10.090.01b: sahasrākṣāḥ sahasrapāt
metric = clllcLcl
- 10.090.14d: táthā lokāṃ akalpayan
metric = ClllcLcl
- 10.093.07d: párijmā viśvavedasaḥ
metric = ClllcLcl
- 10.097.08b: gávo goṣṭhād iverate
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.097.09b: átho yūyaṃ stha níṣkṛtīḥ
metric = ClllcLcl
- 10.097.15d: tá no muñcantu áṃhasaḥ
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.097.16d: sárvasmād devakilbiṣát
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.097.21c: sárvāḥ saṃgátya vīrudho
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.101.04c: dhírā devéṣu sumnayá
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.126.01b: dévāso aṣṭa mártiyam
metric = LllLcLcl

- 10.133.05b: sánābhir yás ca níṣṭiyah
metric = CllLcLcl
- 10.136.04b: vísvā rūpāvacākaśat
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.136.06d: sákhā svādúr madíntamaḥ
metric = CllLcLcl
- 10.137.06d: tás te kṛṇvantu bheṣajám
metric = Llllclcl
- 10.140.05b: kṣáyantaṃ rádhaso maháḥ
metric = CllLclcl
- 10.143.06b: máṃhiṣṭhā vísvavedasā
metric = LllLclcl
- 10.146.02d: arañyānir mahīyate
metric = clLLclcl
- 10.153.05b: vísvā jātāni ójasā
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.154.05b: yé gopāyānti sūriyam
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.155.03b: síndhoḥ pāré apūruṣám
metric = LllLclcl
- 10.155.04b: úro maṇḍūradhāṇikīḥ
metric = Clllclcl
- 10.158.03c: cákṣur dhātá dadhātu naḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 10.158.04a: cákṣur no dhehi cákṣuṣe
metric = Llllclcl
- 10.158.04b: cákṣur vikhyaí tanúbhiyah
metric = LllLcLcl
- 10.159.03d: pátyau me ślóka uttamáḥ
metric = LllLclcl
- 10.161.05a: áhārṣaṃ tvávidaṃ tuvā
metric = LllLclcl
- 10.163.05b: lómabhyas te nakhébbhiyah

metric = LlllLcll

10.164.04a: yád indra brahmaṇas pate

metric = Clllclcl

10.166.05c: á vo mūrdhānam akramīm

metric = LllLclcl

10.176.03b: hótā yajñāya nīyate

metric = LllLclcl

10.184.02d: á dhattām púṣkarasrajā

metric = LllLclcl

10.191.02d: saṃjānāná upásate

metric = lllLclcl

Rhythm and melody by book rankings

Skeleton	AccentPattern	Book	Count	Freq	Rank
lCclclL	0100000	1	17	0.0022	92
lCclclL	0100001	1	40	0.0052	5
lCclclL	0000001	1	17	0.0022	95
lCclclL	0000000	1	9	0.0012	229
lCclclL	0000001	2	3	0.0018	139
lCclclL	0100001	2	9	0.0053	21
lCclclL	0100000	2	5	0.0030	86
lCclclL	0000000	2	1	0.0006	599
lCclclL	0100001	3	17	0.0072	7
lCclclL	0100000	3	7	0.0030	73
lCclclL	0000001	3	8	0.0034	63
lCclclL	0000000	3	2	0.0009	352
lCclclL	0100001	4	28	0.0126	1
lCclclL	0100000	4	5	0.0022	83
lCclclL	0000001	4	11	0.0049	28
lCclclL	0000000	4	3	0.0013	179
lCclclL	0100001	5	8	0.0028	63
lCclclL	0000001	5	8	0.0028	65
lCclclL	0100000	5	7	0.0025	102
lCclclL	0000000	5	3	0.0011	309
lCclclL	0100001	6	30	0.0103	1
lCclclL	0000001	6	18	0.0062	9
lCclclL	0100000	6	9	0.0031	56
lCclclL	0000000	6	2	0.0007	409
lCclclL	0100001	7	32	0.0100	3
lCclclL	0000001	7	18	0.0056	17
lCclclL	0000000	7	6	0.0019	142
lCclclL	0100000	7	10	0.0031	77
lCclclL	0000001	8	3	0.0005	427

lCclclL	0100001	8	5	0.0008	298
lCclclL	0100000	8	2	0.0003	688
lCclclL	0000001	9	3	0.0008	356
lCclclL	0100001	9	10	0.0027	81
lCclclL	0100000	9	1	0.0003	1031
lCclclL	0100000	10	26	0.0037	31
lCclclL	0100001	10	51	0.0074	3
lCclclL	0000001	10	23	0.0033	51
lCclclL	0000000	10	4	0.0006	417
lLLcLcL	0000100	1	22	0.0028	61
lLLcLcL	0000101	1	3	0.0004	535
lLLcLcL	0000000	1	11	0.0014	163
lLLcLcL	0010000	1	27	0.0035	47
lLLcLcL	0010100	1	28	0.0036	37
lLLcLcL	0000001	1	8	0.0010	243
lLLcLcL	0010001	1	13	0.0017	132
lLLcLcL	0010101	1	5	0.0006	401
lLLcLcL	0010000	2	4	0.0024	91
lLLcLcL	0010100	2	2	0.0012	194
lLLcLcL	0010101	2	1	0.0006	372
lLLcLcL	0010001	2	1	0.0006	640
lLLcLcL	0000000	2	1	0.0006	725
lLLcLcL	0010001	3	2	0.0009	306
lLLcLcL	0000101	3	2	0.0009	309
lLLcLcL	0000100	3	3	0.0013	217
lLLcLcL	0010000	3	6	0.0026	112
lLLcLcL	0010100	3	8	0.0034	67
lLLcLcL	0000000	3	2	0.0009	374
lLLcLcL	0000001	3	1	0.0004	733
lLLcLcL	0010100	4	2	0.0009	277
lLLcLcL	0010000	4	5	0.0022	115
lLLcLcL	0000100	4	4	0.0018	150
lLLcLcL	0000000	4	3	0.0013	225
lLLcLcL	0010001	4	1	0.0004	837
lLLcLcL	0010001	5	8	0.0028	70
lLLcLcL	0000100	5	12	0.0042	24
lLLcLcL	0000001	5	2	0.0007	362
lLLcLcL	0000000	5	10	0.0035	47
lLLcLcL	0010000	5	20	0.0070	1
lLLcLcL	0010100	5	8	0.0028	81
lLLcLcL	0000101	5	2	0.0007	454
lLLcLcL	0010100	6	6	0.0021	99
lLLcLcL	0010001	6	7	0.0024	86
lLLcLcL	0010000	6	10	0.0034	47
lLLcLcL	0000001	6	3	0.0010	246
lLLcLcL	0000100	6	10	0.0034	48
lLLcLcL	0000000	6	5	0.0017	135
lLLcLcL	0000101	6	1	0.0003	623

lLlCll	0010101	6	1	0.0003	626
lLlCll	0010100	7	1	0.0003	528
lLlCll	0000100	7	4	0.0013	192
lLlCll	0010000	7	4	0.0013	205
lLlCll	0000101	7	2	0.0006	384
lLlCll	0010001	7	1	0.0003	760
lLlCll	0000001	7	1	0.0003	885
lLlCll	0000000	7	2	0.0006	463
lLlCll	0010101	7	1	0.0003	974
lLlCll	0000001	8	12	0.0020	101
lLlCll	0010000	8	66	0.0111	2
lLlCll	0010100	8	36	0.0060	16
lLlCll	0010101	8	6	0.0010	223
lLlCll	0000100	8	66	0.0111	3
lLlCll	0000000	8	28	0.0047	36
lLlCll	0000101	8	13	0.0022	98
lLlCll	0010001	8	23	0.0039	49
lLlCll	0000100	9	22	0.0059	18
lLlCll	0010000	9	19	0.0051	29
lLlCll	0010100	9	26	0.0069	10
lLlCll	0000000	9	3	0.0008	300
lLlCll	0010001	9	16	0.0043	43
lLlCll	0010101	9	3	0.0008	317
lLlCll	0000001	9	4	0.0011	241
lLlCll	0000101	9	3	0.0008	329
lLlCll	0010000	10	29	0.0042	22
lLlCll	0010100	10	39	0.0056	7
lLlCll	0000100	10	10	0.0014	169
lLlCll	0000000	10	5	0.0007	353
lLlCll	0010001	10	8	0.0012	224
lLlCll	0000001	10	2	0.0003	812

Rhythmic and melodic cadences of the Hymn to Nikkal, analyzed across the Rig Veda, with analysis of the rank compared to other rhythmic and accent patterns, and analyzed how frequently the rhythm and accent patterns are repeated across hymns (compared to 1,000 permutations where the same number of lines is randomly placed across a book with the same number of hymns, each with the correct length of lines, as in the authentic text).

Skeleton	AccentPattern	Book	Count	Freq	Rank	RealRatio
SimMin	SimMed	SimMean	SimMax	RealPct		
lCclclL	0100000	1	17	0.0022	92	1.4167
1.0000	1.0625	1.0595	1.4167	100.0		
1.024.08c:	apāde pādā prátidhātave 'kar					
1.024.13c:	ávainaṃ rájā váruṇaḥ sasṛjyād					
1.035.05d:	upásthe víśvā bhúvanāni taṣthuḥ					
1.071.01c:	svásāraḥ śyāvīm áruṣīm ajuṣrañ					

1.072.10d:	prá nícīr agne áruṣīr ajānan					
1.116.08a:	himēnāgnīm ghraṃsám avārayethām					
1.117.21b:	īṣaṃ duhántā mánuṣāya dasrā					
1.117.23d:	apatyasācaṃ śrútiyaṃ rarāthām					
1.152.02a:	etác caná tvo ví ciketad eṣām					
1.152.07b:	nāmasā devāv ávasā vavrtyām					
1.157.05a:	yuvām ha gárbhaṃ jágatiṣu dhattho					
1.162.21c:	hári te yúñjā pṛṣatī abhūtām					
1.179.01d:	ápy ū nú pátnīr vṛṣaṇo jagamyuḥ					
1.179.02d:	sám ū nú pátnīr vṛṣabhir jagamyuḥ					
1.181.05b:	piśáṅgarūpaḥ sádanāni gamyāḥ					
1.186.03a:	práyiṣṭhaṃ+ vo · átithim grṇīṣe					
1.186.10a:	prá ūśvínāv ávase kṛṇudhvām					
lCclclL	0100001	1	40	0.0052	5	1.2903
1.0000	1.1429	1.1344	1.4286	99.4		
1.024.09d:	kṛtām cid énaḥ prá mumugdhi asmát					
1.024.10a:	amí yá ṛkṣā níhitāsa uccá					
1.035.07b:	gabhírávepā ásurah sunītháh					
1.035.10a:	híraṇyahasto ásurah sunītháh					
1.062.03b:	vidát sarámā tánayāya dhāsím					
1.063.04d:	ví dásyūmr yónāv ákrto vrthāṣát					
1.071.07d:	vidá devéṣu prámatiṃ cikitvān					
1.072.04c:	vidán máрто nemádhitā cikitvān					
1.079.01a:	híraṇyakeśo rájaso visāré					
1.095.09a:	urú te jráyaḥ pári eti budhnám					
1.095.09c:	vísvebhir agne sváyaśobhir iddhó					
1.107.01a:	yajñó devánām práti eti ṣumnám					
1.108.04a:	sámiddheṣu agníṣu ānajāná					
1.108.04b:	yatásrucā barhír u tistirāṇá					
1.109.05a:	yuvām indrágnī vásuno vibhāgé					
1.112.24b:	kṛtām no dasrā vṛṣaṇā manīṣām					
1.112.25a:	dýubhir aktúbhiḥ pári pātam asmán					
1.113.03a:	samāno ádhvā svásaror anantás					
1.117.03c:	minántā dásyor áśivasya māyá					
1.118.05c:	pári vām ásvā vápuṣaḥ patamgá					
1.123.05a:	bhágasya svásā váruṇasya jámír					
1.123.08d:	ékaikā krátum pári yanti sadyáh					
1.126.01a:	ámandān stómān prá bhare manīṣá					
1.128.07f:	sá nas trāsate váruṇasya dhūrtér					
1.143.08d:	ánimiṣadbhiḥ pári páhi no jáḥ					
1.148.04c:	ád asya váto ánu vāti śocír					
1.158.01d:	prá yát sasráthe ákavābhir ūtí					
1.162.19d:	tá-tā píṇḍānām prá juhomi agnaú					
1.164.47a:	kṛṣṇām niyānaṃ hárayaḥ suparṇá					
1.165.01d:	árcanti súṣmaṃ vṛṣaṇo vasūyá					
1.165.06d:	vísvaṣya sátror ánamaṃ vadhasnaíḥ					
1.167.07d:	sthirá cij jánīr váhate subhāgáh					
1.169.01b:	mahás cid asi tyájaso varūtá					
1.171.05d:	ugrá ugrébhi stháviraḥ sahodáh					

	1.173.05d:	vavavrúṣaś cit támaso vihantā					
	1.180.08b:	vírudrasya prasrávaṇasya sātaú					
	1.181.02a:	ā vām ásvāsaḥ súcayaḥ payaspā					
	1.181.08d:	gō´r ná séke mánuṣo daśasyān					
	1.186.03c:	ásad yáthā no váruṇaḥ sukírtír					
	1.186.04a:	úpa va eṣe námasā jigīṣā					
lCclclL	0000001	1	17	0.0022	95	1.2143	
1.0000	1.0625	1.0558	1.4167	99.4			
	1.034.09d:	yéna yajñam̐ nāsatiyopayāthāḥ					
	1.059.02c:	tām tvā devāso 'janayanta devām					
	1.062.13c:	sunīthāya naḥ śavasāna nodhāḥ					
	1.063.04b:	vṛtrām̐ yád vajrin vṛṣakarman ubhnāḥ					
	1.063.08a:	tuvām̐ tyām̐ na indara+ deva citrām̐					
	1.116.16d:	ādhattam̐ dasrā bhiṣajāv anarván					
	1.117.12b:	dívo napātā vṛṣaṇā śayutrā					
	1.118.06c:	nīṣ ṭaugriyām̐ pārayathaḥ samudrāt					
	1.122.09a:	jāno yó mitrāvaruṇāv abhidhrúg					
	1.130.10a:	sá no návyebhir vṛṣakarman ukthaíḥ					
	1.153.02b:	áyāmi mitrāvaruṇā suvṛktíḥ					
	1.153.03b:	jánāya mitrāvaruṇā havirdé					
	1.171.03d:	áhāni víśvā maruto jigīṣā					
	1.174.03b:	diyām̐ ca yébhiḥ puruhūta nūnám					
	1.177.03c:	yuktvā vṛṣabhyām̐ vṛṣabha kṣitínām̐					
	1.177.05a:	ó súṣṭuta indara+ yāhi arvān					
	1.180.04b:	apó ná kṣódo avṛṇitam̐ eṣé					
lCclclL	0000000	1	9	0.0012	229	1.5000	
1.0000	1.0000	1.0324	1.2857	100.0			
	1.089.08a:	bhadram̐ kárṇebhiḥ śṛṇuyāma devā					
	1.116.09a:	pārāvatām̐ nāsatiyānudethām̐					
	1.116.14b:	yuvām̐ narā nāsatiyāmumuktam̐					
	1.116.17d:	sám u śriyā nāsatiyā sacethe					
	1.117.11d:	sām̐ viśpālām̐ nāsatiyāriṇītam̐					
	1.117.24d:	új jīvāsa airayataḥ sudānū					
	1.152.01d:	ṛténa mitrāvaruṇā sacethe					
	1.161.14d:	yuṣmām̐ ichántaḥ śavaso napātaḥ					
	1.189.06a:	ví gha tuvāvām̐ ṛtajāta yaṃsad					
lCclclL	0000001	2	3	0.0018	139	1.0000	
1.0000	1.0000	1.0405	3.0000	92.2			
	2.003.10c:	trídhā sámaktaḥ nayatu prajānán					
	2.027.15a:	ubhé asmai pīpayataḥ samīcí					
	2.040.06a:	dhíyam̐ pūṣā jinvatu viśvaminvó					
lCclclL	0100001	2	9	0.0053	21	1.1250	
1.0000	1.1250	1.1315	1.8000	75.9			
	2.014.07b:	bhúmyā upásthe ávapaj jaghanván					
	2.018.05b:	ā catvāriṃśátā háribhir yujánāḥ					
	2.027.08c:	ṛténādityā máhi vo mahityām̐					
	2.030.04b:	vṛkadvaraso ásurasya vírān					
	2.035.09d:	híraṇyavarṇāḥ pári yanti yahvíḥ					
	2.035.12d:	dádhāmi ánnaiḥ pári vanda rgbhíḥ					

	2.038.03c:	ahyárṣūṇāṃ cin ní ayāṃ aviṣyām				
	2.039.01d:	dūtéva hávyā jániyā puruṭrā				
	2.040.01a:	sómāpūṣaṇā jánanā rayīṇām				
lCclclL	0100000		2	5	0.0030	86
1.0000	1.0000	1.0715	1.6667	100.0		1.6667
	2.027.06c:	ténāditiyā ádhi vocatā no				
	2.028.03d:	abhí kṣamadhvaṃ yújiyāya devāḥ				
	2.028.09b:	māhām rājann anyákrtena bhojam				
	2.030.09d:	druhé rīṣantam pári dhehi rājan				
	2.030.10c:	jiyóg abhūvann ánudhūpitāso				
lCclclL	0000000		2	1	0.0006	599
1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	100.0		1.0000
	2.028.03c:	yūyām naḥ puṭrā aditer adabdhā				
lCclclL	0100001		3	17	0.0072	7
1.0000	1.1333	1.1821	1.7000	52.5		1.1333
	3.001.05a:	śukrēbhir áṅgai rája ātatanván				
	3.004.11c:	barhír na āstām áditiḥ supuṭrā				
	3.005.03d:	ábhūd u vípro háviyo matīnām				
	3.007.09c:	déva hotar mandrátaraś cikitván				
	3.008.08c:	sajóṣaso yajñām avantu devā				
	3.008.10b:	caṣālavantaḥ sváravaḥ pṛthivyām				
	3.031.07c:	sasāna máryo yúvabhir makhasyānn				
	3.032.02a:	gávāśiram manthínam indra śukrám				
	3.033.09c:	ní śú namadhvam bhávatā supārā				
	3.034.04b:	jigāyośígbhiḥ pṛtanā abhiṣṭíḥ				
	3.043.04c:	dhānāvad índraḥ sávanam juṣāṇaḥ				
	3.043.06a:	á tvā bṛhánto hárayo yujāná				
	3.052.08b:	puroḷásam vīrátamāya nṛṇām+				
	3.053.07b:	divás puṭrāso ásurasya vīrāḥ				
	3.054.21d:	úd rāyó aśyām sádanam purukṣóḥ				
	3.055.04a:	samāno rájā víbhṛtaḥ puruṭrā				
	3.061.05b:	prá vo bharadhvam námasā suvrktím				
lCclclL	0100000		3	7	0.0030	73
1.0000	1.0000	1.0715	1.7500	65.5		1.0000
	3.001.16a:	upakṣetāras táva supraṇīte				
	3.014.04a:	mitrás ca túbhyam váruṇaḥ sahasvo				
	3.017.05c:	tásyānu dhárma prá yajā cikitvo				
	3.033.03a:	áchā síndhum mātṛtamām ayāsam				
	3.035.08b:	sám indra góbhir mádhumantam akran				
	3.038.08d:	ápīva yóśā jánimāni vavre				
	3.056.04d:	pṛthag vrājantiḥ pári śim avrñjan				
lCclclL	0000001		3	8	0.0034	63
1.0000	1.0000	1.0836	2.0000	90.8		1.1429
	3.006.07a:	divás cid á te rucayanta roká				
	3.007.06b:	mahó mahádbhyām anayanta śūśám				
	3.020.01c:	sujoyótiṣo naḥ śṛṇuvantu devāḥ				
	3.030.07d:	śahásradānā puruhūta rātiḥ				
	3.030.21a:	á no gotrá dardṛhi gopate gāḥ				
	3.052.07a:	pūṣaṇváte te cakṛmā karambhām				

	3.056.04c:	ápaś cid asmā aramanta devīḥ					
	3.059.01a:	mitró jánān yātayati bruvāṇó					
lCclclL	0000000		3	2	0.0009	352	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0190	2.0000		98.1		
	3.032.01c:	praprúthyā śípre maghavann ṛjīṣin					
	3.043.05b:	kuvíd rájānam maghavann ṛjīṣin					
lCclclL	0100001		4	28	0.0126	1	1.4000
1.0769	1.2727	1.3117	1.7500		84.6		
	4.001.04a:	tuvām no agne váruṇasya vidvān					
	4.001.04d:	vísṽā dvéṣāṃsi prá mumugdhi asmát					
	4.001.20c:	agnír devānām áva āvṛṇānáḥ					
	4.002.12b:	nidhāráyanto dúriyāsu āyóḥ					
	4.003.07d:	brávaḥ kád agne sárave bṛhatyaí					
	4.004.01c:	trṣvīm ánu · prásitim druṇānó°					
	4.005.10d:	vṛṣṇaḥ śocíṣaḥ práyatasya jihvá					
	4.014.02b:	jyótir víśvasmai bhúvanāya kṛṇván					
	4.017.12a:	kíyat svid índro ádhi eti mātúḥ					
	4.018.10a:	grṣṭíḥ sasūva stháviraṃ tavāgām					
	4.020.09d:	áthā dadhāti dráviṇaṃ jaritré					
	4.021.05a:	úpa yó námo námasi stabhāyān					
	4.023.03d:	katháinam āhuḥ pápurim jaritré					
	4.027.03d:	kṛśānur ástā mánasā bhurānyān					
	4.033.09a:	ápo hí eṣām ájuṣanta devā					
	4.033.10c:	té rāyás póṣaṃ dráviṇāni asmé					
	4.041.05c:	sá no duhīyad yāvaseva gatví					
	4.041.10a:	ásvyasya tmánā ráthiyasya puṣṭér					
	4.042.01c:	krátuṃ sacante váruṇasya devā					
	4.042.02c:	krátuṃ sacante váruṇasya devā					
	4.042.03c:	tváṣṭeva víśvā bhúvanāni vidvān					
	4.042.06d:	ubhé bhayete rájasī apāré					
	4.043.05a:	urú vām ráthaḥ pári nakṣati dyām					
	4.050.09d:	brahmāṇe rájā tám avanti devāḥ					
	4.051.02d:	uchántir avrañ chúcayaḥ pavākāḥ+					
	4.051.09d:	śukrás tanúbhiḥ súcayo rucānáḥ					
	4.055.06b:	stuvítá devī ápiyebhir iṣṭaíḥ					
	4.057.02a:	kṣétrasya pate mádhumantam ūrmím					
lCclclL	0100000		4	5	0.0022	83	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0502	1.6667		81.6		
	4.001.04b:	devásya héḷo áva yāsisīṣṭhāḥ					
	4.003.12b:	árṇobhir ápo mádhumadbhir agne					
	4.018.08c:	mámac cid ápaḥ síśave mamṛdyur					
	4.043.05c:	mádhvā mádhuvī mádhu vām pruṣāyan					
	4.058.10d:	ghṛtásya dhārā mádhumat pavante					
lCclclL	0000001		4	11	0.0049	28	1.1000
1.0000	1.1000	1.1183	1.5714		70.1		
	4.003.10c:	áspandamāno acarad vayodhá					
	4.004.04c:	yó no árātim samidhāna cakré					
	4.004.15d:	druhó nidó mitramaho avadyāt					
	4.006.06a:	bhadrá te agne suanīka samḍṛg					

4.017.09a:	ayám vṛtaś cātayate samīcīr					
4.019.07c:	dhānvāni ájṛāṃ aprṇak tṛṣāṇāṃ					
4.037.02c:	prá vaḥ śutáso harayanta pūrṇāḥ					
4.043.07d:	śritāḥ kāmo nāsatiyā yuvadrík					
4.044.07d:	śritāḥ kāmo nāsatiyā yuvadrík					
4.055.02d:	ṛtádhitayo rurucanta dasmāḥ					
4.058.07b:	vātapramiyāḥ patayanti yahvāḥ					
lCclclL	0000000	4	3	0.0013	179	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0355	3.0000	93.2		
4.004.14c:	ubhá śámsā sūdaya satyatāte					
4.035.03d:	gaṇám devānām ṛbhavaḥ suhastāḥ					
4.037.04c:	índrasya sūno śavaso napāto					
lCclclL	0100001	5	8	0.0028	63	1.1429
1.0000	1.0000	1.0556	2.0000	95.4		
5.001.09a:	prá sadyó agne áti eṣi anyān					
5.002.03a:	híraṇyadantaṃ sūcivarṇam ārát					
5.012.02b:	ṛtāsya dhārā ánu tṛndhi pūrvīḥ					
5.030.14a:	aúchat sá rátri páritakmiyā yāṃ					
5.030.15a:	cātuḥsahasraṃ gáviyasya paśvāḥ					
5.040.04c:	yuktvá háribhyām úpa yāsad arvān					
5.041.03b:	vāstasya pátman ráthiyasya puṣṭau					
5.042.01d:	átūrtapanthā ásuro mayobhúḥ					
lCclclL	0000001	5	8	0.0028	65	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0576	1.6000	67.1		
5.004.08b:	sáhasaḥ sūno triṣadhastha havýam					
5.029.08c:	kāram ná víśve ahuvanta devá					
5.030.05c:	átaś cid índrād abhayanta devá					
5.041.01a:	kó nú vām mitrāvaruṇāv ṛtāyān					
5.055.10b:	nír aṃhatíbhyo maruto gṛṇānāḥ					
5.062.02a:	tát sú vām mitrāvaruṇā mahitvám					
5.083.10d:	utá prajābhyo avido manīṣām					
5.085.04d:	taviṣiyántaḥ śrathayanta vīrāḥ					
lCclclL	0100000	5	7	0.0025	102	1.1667
1.0000	1.0000	1.0480	1.4000	98.2		
5.012.05b:	śivāsaḥ sánto áśivā abhūvan					
5.030.13d:	aktór víuṣṭau páritakmiyāyāḥ					
5.031.11a:	súraś cid rátham páritakmiyāyām					
5.037.03d:	purú sahásrā pári vartayāte					
5.041.14b:	apás ca áchā sūmakhāya vocam					
5.062.01d:	devānām śréṣṭhaṃ vápuṣām apaśyam					
5.062.02b:	irmá tasthúṣir áhabhir duduhre					
lCclclL	0000000	5	3	0.0011	309	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0200	1.5000	96.0		
5.057.07b:	candravad rádho maruto dadā naḥ					
5.058.03d:	etám juṣadhvaṃ kavayo yuvānaḥ					
5.062.09c:	téna no mitrāvaruṇāv aviṣṭam					
lCclclL	0100001	6	30	0.0103	1	1.5789
1.0345	1.2500	1.2838	1.6667	99.5		
6.001.11c:	brhábhir vājai sthávirebhir asmé					

6.003.05a: sá íd ásteva práti dhād asiṣyāñ
 6.004.05b: vāyúr ná ráṣṭrī áti eti aktún
 6.004.05d: átyo ná hrútaḥ pátataḥ parihrút
 6.006.07b: cítrakṣatra citrátamaḥ vayodhām
 6.007.02a: nābhiḥ yajñānām sádanam rayiñām
 6.018.10a: agnír ná súṣkaḥ vānam índra hetí
 6.018.14a: ánu tváhighne ádha deva devá
 6.027.01a: kím asya máde kím u asya pītáv
 6.027.02a: sád asya máde sád u asya pītáv
 6.027.06a: triṣśácchataḥ varmīṇa índra sākám
 6.029.02a: á yásmin háste náriyā mimikṣúr
 6.029.02d: ádhvann ásvāso vṛṣaṇo yujānáḥ
 6.034.01d: pasprdhṛá índre ádhi ukthaarká
 6.034.04d: satrá vāvṛdhur hávanāni yajñaiḥ
 6.036.01d: yád devéṣu dhāráyathā asuryam
 6.036.05c: áso yáthā naḥ sávasā cakānó
 6.037.05a: índro vājasya sthávirasya dātá
 6.044.19a: á tvā hárayo vṛṣaṇo yujāná
 6.044.22d: índur amuṣṇād áśivasya mājāḥ
 6.047.08c: ṛṣvā ta índra sthávirasya bāhú
 6.049.05b: rátho virúkmān mánasā yujānáḥ
 6.050.04d: bādhé marúto áhuvāma devān
 6.063.02a: áram me gantaḥ hávanāya asmaí
 6.063.04c: prá hótā · gūrtámanā urānó
 6.068.03b: sumnébhir índrāvāruṇā cakāná
 6.068.07c: yésām súṣmaḥ pṛtanāsu sāhvān
 6.068.11c: idám vām ándhaḥ páriṣiktam asmé
 6.069.04c: juṣéthām vísvā hávanā matinām
 6.074.02c: áre bādhethām nírrtim parācaír
 6.005.04b: yó ántaro mitramaho vanuṣyāt
 6.007.01d: āsānn á pátraḥ janayanta devāḥ
 6.008.07b: asmākam páhi triṣadhastha sūrín
 6.010.04d: tiráḥ śocíṣā dadṛṣe pavākáḥ+
 6.015.16a: ágne víśvebhiḥ suanika devaír
 6.018.15d: ukthám návīyo janayasva yajñaiḥ
 6.019.06b: ójiṣṭham ójo abhibhūta ugrám
 6.022.10a: á samyátam indara+ naḥ suastím
 6.026.07c: tváyā yát stávante sadhavīra vīrás
 6.032.04c: puruvīrābhir vṛṣabha kṣitinām
 6.036.01c: satrá vājānām abhavo vibhaktá
 6.047.17c: ánānubhūtīr avadhūnuvānáḥ
 6.049.06a: párijanyavātā vṛṣabhā pṛthivyāḥ
 6.067.03d: chrudhīyatás cid yatatho mahitvá
 6.067.10d: nákir devébhir yatatho mahitvá
 6.068.04c: prá ebhya índrāvāruṇā mahitvá
 6.068.08a: nú na índrāvāruṇā gṛṇāná
 6.075.03b: priyám sákhāyam pariṣasvajāná

lCclclL 0000001 6 18 0.0062 9 1.1250
 1.0000 1.1250 1.1703 1.6364 51.7

lCclclL	0100000	6	9	0.0031	56	1.0000
1.0000	1.1250	1.0895	1.8000	48.4		
	6.006.04a:	yé te súkrásaḥ súcayaḥ súciṣmaḥ				
	6.024.09d:	aktór víuṣṭau páritakmiyāyām				
	6.025.05c:	índra nákiṣ ṭvā práti asti eṣām				
	6.040.02b:	mádāya krátve ápiḥ virapśin				
	6.051.08c:	námo devébhyo náma ísa eṣām				
	6.052.13d:	āsadyāsmín barhíṣi mādayadhvam				
	6.068.11d:	āsadyāsmín barhíṣi mādayethām				
	6.072.05b:	apatyasācaṃ śrútiyaṃ rarāthe				
	6.075.07d:	kṣiṇánti śátrūṃr ánapavyayantaḥ				
lCclclL	0000000	6	2	0.0007	409	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0180	2.0000	98.2		
	6.022.11a:	sá no niyúdbhiḥ puruhūta vedho				
	6.051.06b:	aghāyaté rīradhatā yajatrāḥ				
lCclclL	0100001	7	32	0.0100	3	1.3913
1.0323	1.1852	1.2018	1.5238	98.6		
	7.001.11a:	mā śúne agne ní ṣadāma nṛṇām+				
	7.001.18a:	imó agne vītátamāni havyā				
	7.002.02c:	yé sukrátavaḥ súcayo dhiyamdhāḥ				
	7.002.11c:	barhír na āstām áditiḥ suputrā				
	7.003.02c:	ād asya vāto ánu vāti śocír				
	7.003.06d:	citró ná súraḥ práti cakṣi bhānám				
	7.004.02b:	yáto yáviṣṭho ájaniṣṭa mātúḥ				
	7.005.07b:	vāyúr ná páthaḥ pári pāsi sadyáḥ				
	7.008.03a:	káyā no agne ví vasaḥ suvrktim				
	7.010.05c:	sá hí kṣápāvāṃ ábhavad rayiṇām				
	7.018.11c:	daśmó ná sádman ní śiśāti barhíḥ				
	7.019.11a:	nú indra súra stávamāna ūtí				
	7.021.04b:	ápāṃsi víśvā náriyāṇi vidvān				
	7.021.09c:	vanvāntu smā te ávasā samiké				
	7.035.05d:	śám no rájasas pátir astu jiṣnúḥ				
	7.035.07b:	śám no grāvāṇaḥ sám u santu yajñāḥ				
	7.035.09d:	śám no bhavítṛaṃ sám u astu vāyúḥ				
	7.037.05c:	vavanmā nú te yújiyābhir ūtí				
	7.037.06d:	pṛkṣó no árvā ní uhīta vājí				
	7.042.02d:	huvé devānāṃ jánimāni sattāḥ				
	7.045.02d:	śúraś cid asmā ánu dād apasyām				
	7.046.04c:	á no bhaja barhíṣi jīvaśamsé				
	7.056.12d:	chúcijanmānaḥ súcayaḥ pavākāḥ+				
	7.057.05b:	anavadyāsaḥ súcayaḥ pavākāḥ+				
	7.058.01d:	nákṣante nákaṃ níṛṭter avamśāt				
	7.058.03c:	gató ná ádhvā ví tirāti jantúm				
	7.058.04b:	yuṣmóto árvā sáhuriḥ sahasrí				
	7.064.01a:	diví kṣáyantā rájasaḥ pṛthivyām				
	7.079.04b:	yávat stotṛbhyo árado grṇānā				
	7.098.05c:	yadéd ádevír ásaḥiṣṭa māyā				
	7.099.03b:	sūyavasínī mánuṣe daśasyā				
	7.100.04b:	kṣétrāya víṣnur mánuṣe daśasyán				

lCclclL	0000001	7	18	0.0056	17	1.0588
1.0000	1.1250	1.1164	1.5000	44,8		
	7.001.23a:	sá	márto	agne	suanīka	reván
	7.021.01c:	bódhāmasi	tvā	hariaśva	yajñair	
	7.024.02c:	vīsṛṣṭadhenā	bharate	suvṛktír		
	7.033.05d:	urúm	tṛtsubhyo	akṛṇod	ulokám†	
	7.036.02a:	imām	vām	mitrāvaruṇā	suvṛktím	
	7.037.05b:	yābhir	víveṣo	hariaśva	dhībhíḥ	
	7.044.04b:	ágre	ráthānām	bhavati	prajānán	
	7.056.18d:	só	ádvayāvī	havate	va	ukthaiḥ
	7.058.02d:	vísvo	vo	yāman	bhayate	suvadṛk
	7.058.04a:	yuṣmóto	vípro	marutaḥ	śatasví	
	7.060.09d:	urúm	sudāse	vṛṣaṇā	ulokám†	
	7.061.03a:	prá	urór	mitrāvaruṇā	pṛthivyāḥ	
	7.067.08a:	ékasmin	yóge	bhuraṇā	samāné	
	7.068.04c:	á	valgú	vípro	vavṛtīta	havyaiḥ
	7.093.04d:	prá	no	návyebhis	tirataṃ	dayiṣṇaiḥ+
	7.097.08b:	bṛhaspátim	vāvṛdhatur	mahitvá		
	7.100.01a:	nú	mártio°	dayate	saniṣyán	
	7.103.09d:	taptá	gharmá	aśnuvate	visargám	
lCclclL	0000000	7	6	0.0019	142	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0382	2.0000	82.8		
	7.021.05a:	ná	yātáva	indara+	jūjuvur	no
	7.038.08b:	dhāneṣu	vīprā	amṛtā	ṛtajñāḥ	
	7.056.14d:	gṛhamedhīyam	maruto	juṣadhvam		
	7.086.08a:	ayám	sú	túbhyaṃ	varuṇa	svadhāvo
	7.088.05c:	bṛhántam	mánaṃ	varuṇa	svadhāvaḥ	
	7.093.04c:	índraagnī	vṛtrahaṇā	suvajrā		
lCclclL	0100000	7	10	0.0031	77	1.1111
1.0000	1.0000	1.0618	1.6667	92.1		
	7.027.01a:	índraṃ	náro	nemádhitā	havante	
	7.033.06a:	daṇḍá	ivéd	goájanāsa	āsan	
	7.033.08d:	stómo	vasiṣṭhā	ánuetave	vaḥ	
	7.034.23d:	ubhé	ródasī	pári	pāsato	naḥ
	7.047.02a:	tám	ūrmím	āpo	mádhumattamaṃ	vo
	7.048.04c:	sám	asmé	íṣaṃ	vásavo	dadīran
	7.084.02c:	pári	no	hélo	váruṇasya	vṛjyā
	7.086.03d:	ayám	ha	túbhyaṃ	váruṇo	hṛṇīte
	7.088.07b:	ví	asmát	pásam	váruṇo	mumocat
	7.104.13d:	ubhāv	índrasya	prásitau	śayāte	
lCclclL	0000001	8	3	0.0005	427	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0155	3.0000	97.2		
	8.009.15a:	yán	nāsatiyā	parāké		
	8.048.10b:	yó	mā	ná	ríṣyed	dhariaśva
	8.080.10c:	tásmā	u	rádhaḥ	kṛṇuta	praśastám
lCclclL	0100001	8	5	0.0008	298	1.2500
1.0000	1.0000	1.0326	1.6667	99.5		
	8.042.01c:	ásidad	víśvā	bhúvanāni	samráḍ	
	8.057.04c:	píbatam	sómam	mádhumantam	asmé	

	8.096.03d: āsānn eṣanta śrútiyā upāké					
	8.096.09c: anāyudhāso āsurā adevās					
	8.101.14c: br̥hád dha tasthau bhúvaneṣu antáḥ					
lCclclL	0100000	8	2	0.0003	688	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0140	2.0000	98.6		
	8.048.14a: trátāro devā ádhi vocatā no					
	8.057.01d: idám tr̥tíyaṃ sávanam pibāthaḥ					
lCclclL	0000001	9	3	0.0008	356	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0260	1.5000	94.8		
	9.085.11b: gíro venānām akr̥panta pūrvīḥ					
	9.088.04b: hantā vṛtr̥āṇām āsi soma pūrbhít					
	9.093.03b: índur dhárābhiḥ sacate sumedhāḥ					
lCclclL	0100001	9	10	0.0027	81	1.6667
1.0000	1.1111	1.0821	1.6667	100.0		
	9.088.05d: íyarti sómaḥ pávamāna ūrmím					
	9.089.03d: áśya cákṣasā pári pāti ukṣá					
	9.089.05d: tā im̐ viśvátaḥ pári śanti pūrvīḥ					
	9.092.05c: jyótir yád áhne ákr̥nod ulokám̐					
	9.095.05b: punāná indo ví ṣiyā manīśám					
	9.096.12a: yáthāpavathā mánave vayodhá					
	9.097.11a: ádha dhárāyā mádhuvā pṛcānás					
	9.097.28a: áśvo ná krado vṛṣabhir yujānáḥ					
	9.097.41b: apám̐ yád gárbho ávṛṇīta deván					
	9.097.49c: abhí náraṃ dhījávaṇaṃ ratheṣṭhám					
lCclclL	0100000	9	1	0.0003	1031	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	100.0		
	9.107.09c: samudráṃ ná samváraṇāni agman					
lCclclL	0100000	10	26	0.0037	31	1.2381
1.0000	1.0833	1.0891	1.3684	98.3		
	10.002.04b: vidúṣāṃ devā áviduṣṭarāsaḥ					
	10.010.09a: rátrībhir asmā áhabhir daśasyet					
	10.014.11c: tábhiyām enam pári dehi rájan					
	10.017.04a: áyur viśváyuḥ pári pásati tvā					
	10.027.18a: ví krośanāso víśuañca āyan					
	10.030.07d: devamādanam prá hiṇotanāpaḥ					
	10.030.14b: ádhvaryavaḥ sādáyatā sakhāyaḥ					
	10.031.02a: pári cin márto dráviṇam mamanyād					
	10.031.02d: śréyāmsaṃ dáḥṣam mánasā jagṛbhyāt					
	10.046.02d: ichánto dhírā bhṛgavo avindan					
	10.063.17a: evá platéḥ sūnú avīvṛdhad vo					
	10.064.17a: evá platéḥ sūnú avīvṛdhad vo					
	10.066.02a: índraprasūtā váruṇapráśiṣṭā					
	10.070.02d: devébhiyo devátamaḥ suṣūdat					
	10.071.08d: óhabrahmāṇo ví caranti u tve					
	10.071.11d: yajñásya mátrāṃ ví mimīta u tvaḥ					
	10.087.03c: utántárikṣe pári yāhi rájañ					
	10.087.09b: práñcaṃ vásubhyaḥ prá ṇaya pracetaḥ					
	10.088.16c: sá pratyán víśvā bhúvanāni tasthāv					
	10.089.15c: andhénámítrās támasā sacantām					

10.095.15b:	má tvā vṛkāso áśivāsa u kṣan					
10.098.06b:	ápo devébhīr nívṛtā atiṣṭhan					
10.103.06c:	imāṃ sajātā ánu vīrayadhvam					
10.103.12d:	andhénāmítrās tāmāsā sacantām					
10.128.04d:	vísve devāso ádhi vocatā naḥ					
10.161.01d:	tásyā indrāgnī prá mumuktam enam					
lCclclL	0100001	10	51	0.0074	3	1.4167
1.0200	1.1860	1.1818	1.4167	100.0		
10.004.07c:	rākṣā ṇo agne tánayāni toká					
10.010.02c:	mahás putrásō ásurasya vīrá					
10.010.13d:	pári ṣvajāte líbujeva vṛkṣám					
10.010.14b:	pári ṣvajāte líbujeva vṛkṣám					
10.017.03b:	ánaṣṭapaśur bhúvanasya gopāḥ					
10.027.15b:	aṣṭóttaráttāt sám ajagmīran té					
10.027.19a:	ápaśyaṃ grāmaṃ váhamānam ārád					
10.028.06c:	purú sahāśrā ní śísāmi sākám					
10.030.07a:	yó vo vṛtābhyo ákrṇod ulokámṭ					
10.042.11a:	bṛhaspátir naḥ pári pātu paścād					
10.042.11b:	utóttarasmād ádharād aghāyóḥ					
10.043.11a:	bṛhaspátir naḥ pári pātu paścād					
10.043.11b:	utóttarasmād ádharād aghāyóḥ					
10.044.07b:	áśvā yéśāṃ duryúja āyuyujré					
10.044.11a:	bṛhaspátir naḥ pári pātu paścād					
10.044.11b:	utóttarasmād ádharād aghāyóḥ					
10.047.04c:	dasyuhánam pūrbhídān indra satyám					
10.055.08b:	ásastihá viśvámanās turāśāt					
10.061.09d:	sá dhartá jajñe sáhasā yavīyút					
10.061.24d:	vípraś ca asi śrávasaś ca sātaú					
10.061.26b:	íti subándhur námasā suuktaíḥ					
10.067.02b:	divás putrásō ásurasya vīráḥ					
10.070.09b:	yád ángirasām ábhavaḥ sacābhúḥ					
10.074.05d:	bhártā yó vájraṃ náriyam purukṣúḥ					
10.075.07a:	ṛjīti éni rúsati mahitvá					
10.080.01c:	agní ródasī ví carat samañján					
10.080.03c:	agnír átriṃ gharmá uruṣyad antár					
10.084.07b:	asmábhyam dattām váruṇaś ca manyúḥ					
10.085.19c:	bhāgām devébhyo ví dadhāti āyán					
10.087.12a:	tád agne cákṣuḥ práti dhehi rebhé					
10.088.01c:	tásya bhármaṇe bhúvanāya devá					
10.088.05a:	yáj jātavedo bhúvanasya mūrdhān					
10.088.06d:	ápo yát túrṇis cárati prajānán					
10.089.02b:	éndro vavṛtyād ráthiyeva cakrá					
10.089.04b:	apāḥ prérayam ságarasya budhnát					
10.089.05b:	dhúniḥ śímivāñ chárumām ṛjīśi					
10.095.15d:	sālāvṛkánām hṛdayāni etá					
10.098.05c:	sá úttarasmād ádharam samudrám					
10.099.03a:	sá vájam yátā ápaduṣpadā yán					
10.101.09c:	sá no duhīyad yávaseva gatvī					
10.104.03d:	dhībhír viśvābhiḥ sáciyā grṇánāḥ					

	10.108.01b:	dūrē hí ádhvā jáguriḥ parācaíḥ				
	10.110.10a:	upāvasrja tmāniyā samañján				
	10.117.05c:	ó hí vārtante ráthiyeva cakrá				
	10.123.03c:	ṛtásya sánāv ádhi cakramāñá				
	10.123.06c:	híraṇyapakṣam váruṇasya dūtám				
	10.124.05c:	ṛténa rājann árṛtaṃ viviñcán				
	10.129.01d:	ámbhaḥ kím āsīd gáhanam gabhírám				
	10.139.01d:	sampásyan víśvā bhúvanāni gopáḥ				
	10.165.03a:	hetíḥ pakṣīṇī ná dabhāti asmán				
	10.191.03a:	samānó mántraḥ sámītiḥ samānī				
lCclclL	0000001		10	23	0.0033	51 1.0455
1.0000	1.0952	1.0794	1.2778		48.4	
	10.008.06c:	diví mūrdhānam dadhiṣe suarṣám				
	10.014.01b:	bahúbhyaḥ pánthām anupaspaśánám				
	10.022.13a:	asmé tá ta indara+ santu satyá				
	10.027.09d:	átho áyuktaṃ yunajad vavanván				
	10.029.05c:	gíraś ca yé te tuvijāta pūrvír				
	10.045.01d:	índhāna enam jarate suādhīḥ				
	10.063.17b:	víśva ādityā adite manīśī				
	10.064.17b:	víśva ādityā adite manīśī				
	10.067.11a:	satyām āśíṣam kṛṇutā vayodhai				
	10.077.06a:	prá yád váhadhve marutaḥ parākád				
	10.079.07a:	víśūco áśvān yuyuje vanejá				
	10.083.04b:	svayambhúr bhāmo abhimātiṣāhāḥ				
	10.085.14d:	putráḥ pitárāv avṛṇīta pūṣá				
	10.088.09d:	ṛjūyámāno atapan mahitvá				
	10.103.08c:	devasenánām abhibhañjatínām				
	10.104.05a:	prāñītibhiḥ ṭe hariaśva suṣtóḥ				
	10.110.01c:	ā ca váha mitramahaś cikitván				
	10.110.11b:	agnír devánām abhavat purogáḥ				
	10.120.07c:	ā mātárā sthāpayase jigatnú				
	10.148.02a:	ṛṣvās tuvám indara+ śūra jātó				
	10.179.03d:	píbendra vajrin purukṛj juṣānáḥ				
	10.180.03d:	urúm devébhyo akṛṇor ulokámṭ				
	10.182.02a:	nárāśámso no avatu prayājé				
lCclclL	0000000		10	4	0.0006	417 1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0117	1.3333		96.5	
	10.029.01b:	chúcir vām stómo bhuraṇāv ajīgaḥ				
	10.030.14c:	ní barhīṣi dhattana somiyāso				
	10.049.11c:	víśvā ít tá te harivaḥ śacīvo				
	10.131.05d:	sárasvatī tvā maghavann abhiṣṇak				
lLLcLcL	0000100		1	22	0.0028	61 1.4667
1.0000	1.0476	1.0773	1.3750		100.0	
	1.001.01c:	hótāram ratnadhátamam				
	1.001.07a:	úpa tvāgne divé–dive				
	1.009.01b:	víśvebhiḥ somapárvabhiḥ				
	1.019.04b:	ánādhṛṣṭāsa ójasā				
	1.027.08c:	vájo āsti śravāyiyāḥ				
	1.030.01c:	mámhiṣṭham siñca índubhiḥ				

1.030.05b:	gírvāho vīra yāsya te						
1.030.07a:	yóge-yoge tavástaraṃ						
1.050.12c:	átho hāridravéṣu me						
1.078.03a:	tám u tvā vājasátamam						
1.078.04a:	tám u tvā vṛtrahántamaṃ						
1.081.09b:	vísvam puṣyanti vāriyam						
1.084.11b:	sómaṃ śrīṇanti pṛśnayaḥ						
1.084.11d:	vájraṃ hinvanti sáyakaṃ						
1.090.06c:	mādhvīr naḥ santu óṣadhīḥ						
1.093.02c:	tásmai dhattaṃ suvīriyaṃ						
1.093.10a:	ágniṣomāv anéna vām						
1.093.11a:	ágniṣomāv imāni no						
1.127.02c:	víprebhiḥ śukra mánmabhiḥ						
1.132.05e:	bādhe arcanti ójasā						
1.136.01c:	svādiṣṭham mṛḷayádbhiyām+						
1.187.05b:	táva svādiṣṭha té pito						
lLlCllCll	0000101	1	3	0.0004	535	1.5000	
1.0000	1.0000	1.0105	1.5000	100.0			
1.001.07b:	dóṣāvastar dhiyá vayám						
1.137.01b:	góśrītā matsarā imé						
1.137.01c:	sómāso matsarā imé						
lLlCllCll	0000000	1	11	0.0014	163	1.1000	
1.0000	1.0000	1.0383	1.3750	94.6			
1.003.03c:	á yātaṃ rudravartanī						
1.003.07a:	ómāsaś carṣaṇīdhrto						
1.009.03b:	stómebhir vísvacarṣaṇe						
1.011.06c:	úpātiṣṭhanta girvaṇo						
1.018.03c:	rákṣā ṇo brahmaṇas pate						
1.030.07b:	vāje-vāje havāmahe						
1.040.01a:	út tiṣṭha brahmaṇas pate						
1.129.10g:	rírikṣantaṃ cid adrivaḥ						
1.137.01d:	á rājānā divisprśā						
1.139.05a:	śácībhir naḥ śacīvasū						
1.187.07c:	átrā cin no madho pito						
lLlCllCll	0010000	1	27	0.0035	47	1.3500	
1.0000	1.0800	1.0963	1.4211	99.9			
1.005.01c:	sákhāya stómavāhasaḥ						
1.007.08c:	ísāno apratiṣkutaḥ						
1.014.01b:	vísvebhiḥ sómapítaye						
1.016.01c:	índra tvā súrakahśasaḥ						
1.021.05b:	índrāgnī rákṣa ubjataṃ						
1.022.03c:	táyā yajñám mimikṣataṃ						
1.022.09c:	tváṣṭāraṃ sómapítaye						
1.022.16a:	áto devá avantu no						
1.023.08b:	dévāsaḥ púṣarātayaḥ						
1.023.10a:	vísván devān havāmahe						
1.023.12b:	áto jātá avantu naḥ						
1.023.23a:	ápo adyānv acāriṣaṃ						
1.025.02b:	jihīlānāsya rīradhaḥ						

	1.027.12b:	daívyah ketúh śr̥notu nah					
	1.034.04b:	tr̥iḥ supravīye tr̥ēdhēva śikṣatam					
	1.036.03a:	prá tvā dūtám vṛṇīmahe					
	1.041.02c:	ářiṣṭah sárva edhate					
	1.047.04b:	mádhvā yajñám mimikṣatam					
	1.075.01b:	váco deváṣsarastamam					
	1.093.09c:	sám devatrā babhūvathuḥ					
	1.126.07b:	mā me dabhrāṇi manyathāḥ					
	1.128.04e:	vísṽvā jātāni paspāse					
	1.129.11g:	rakṣohāṇam tvā jījanad vaso					
	1.130.01g:	mámhiṣṭham vājasātaye					
	1.130.03e:	síṣāsann áṅgirastamaḥ					
	1.130.08e:	tvácam kṛṣṇám arandhayat					
	1.135.02e:	sómo devéṣu hūyate					
lLLcLcL	0010100		1	28	0.0036	37	1.1667
1.0000	1.0769	1.0991	1.4000		91.3		
	1.005.03a:	sá ghā no yóga ā bhuvat					
	1.006.02c:	śónā dhṛṣṇú nṛvāhasā					
	1.007.08a:	vṛṣā yūthēva vámsagaḥ					
	1.014.10c:	pībā mitrásya dhāmabhiḥ					
	1.020.06b:	tváṣṭur devásya níṣkṛtam					
	1.022.07b:	vásoś citrásya rádhasaḥ					
	1.026.04a:	ā no barhí riśádaso					
	1.030.09a:	ánu pratnásya ókaso					
	1.036.12b:	ágne devéṣu ápiyam					
	1.037.05a:	prá śamsā góṣu ághniyam					
	1.044.11a:	ní tvā yajñásya sádhanam					
	1.045.06d:	ágne havyāya vólhave					
	1.053.05b:	sám vājebhiḥ puruścandraír abhídyubhiḥ					
	1.080.05a:	índro vṛtrásya dódhataḥ					
	1.080.09d:	índrāya bráhma údyatam					
	1.092.15b:	ásvāṃ adyáruṇāṃ uṣaḥ					
	1.105.05d:	kúva pratná va áhutir					
	1.105.09b:	tátrā me nābhir átatā					
	1.127.10e:	vísṽvasu kṣásu jóguve					
	1.133.04b:	abhivlaṅgaír apāvapaḥ					
	1.134.02c:	góbhiḥ krāṇā abhídyavaḥ					
	1.135.08a:	átrāha tát vahethe mádhva áhutim					
	1.139.01e:	nābhā samdáyi návyasī					
	1.139.08d:	yád vaś citráṃ yugé-yuge					
	1.139.09d:	tésāṃ devéṣu áyatir					
	1.142.09a:	śúcir devéṣu árpitā					
	1.162.22a:	sugáviyam no vājī suásviyam					
	1.182.02c:	pūrṇám rátham vahethe mádhva ácitam					
lLLcLcL	0000001		1	8	0.0010	243	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0256	1.3333		83.8		
	1.007.07c:	ná vindhe asya suṣṭutím					
	1.017.09a:	prá vām aśnotu suṣṭutír					
	1.023.17c:	tá no hinvantu adhvarám					

		1.075.02b:	ágne vedhastama priyám				
		1.091.08b:	rákṣā rājann aghāyatāḥ				
		1.105.12b:	dévāsaḥ supravācanám				
		1.170.02c:	tébhiḥ kalpasva sādhuḃyā				
		1.175.02a:	á nas te gantu matsaró				
lLlC	LcL	0010001	1	13	0.0017	132	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0439	1.3000		57.0		
		1.013.08b:	hótārā daiviyā kaví				
		1.023.18c:	síndhubhyaḥ kártuvaḃ havíḥ				
		1.039.05d:	dévāsaḥ sárvayā viśá				
		1.050.10d:	áganma jyótir uttamám				
		1.075.04b:	ágne mitró asi priyáḥ				
		1.078.02a:	tám u tvā gótamo girá				
		1.080.02b:	sómaḥ syenābhṛtaḥ sutáḥ				
		1.114.01d:	viśvam puṣtám grāme asmínn anāturám				
		1.127.06d:	ádad dhavyāni ádadír				
		1.128.04d:	krátvā vedhá iṣūyaté				
		1.136.05g:	stómair ābhúṣati vratám				
		1.142.08b:	hótārā daiviyā kaví				
		1.188.07b:	hótārā daiviyā kaví				
lLlC	LcL	0010101	1	5	0.0006	401	1.2500
1.0000	1.0000	1.0180	1.6667		99.7		
		1.044.07d:	ágne devám ihá dravát				
		1.075.05b:	yájā devám ṛtám bṛhát				
		1.105.06c:	kád aryamṇó mahás pathá				
		1.105.10b:	mádhya tasthúr mahó diváḥ				
		1.188.09a:	tváṣṭā rūpāni hí prabhúḥ				
lLlC	LcL	0010000	2	4	0.0024	91	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0497	2.0000		85.5		
		2.001.16a:	yé stotṛbhyo góagrām ásvapeśasam				
		2.002.13a:	yé stotṛbhyo góagrām ásvapeśasam				
		2.005.06d:	yávo vṛṣṭíva modate				
		2.041.15b:	dévāsaḥ púṣarātayaḥ				
lLlC	LcL	0010100	2	2	0.0012	194	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0200	2.0000		98.0		
		2.002.12c:	vásvo ráyáḥ puruścandrásya bhúyasaḥ				
		2.041.11b:	ná naḥ paścád aghám naśat				
lLlC	LcL	0010101	2	1	0.0006	372	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000		100.0		
		2.005.05d:	svásāro yá idám yayúḥ				
lLlC	LcL	0010001	2	1	0.0006	640	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000		100.0		
		2.032.07c:	tasyai viśpátniyai havíḥ				
lLlC	LcL	0000000	2	1	0.0006	725	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000		100.0		
		2.041.07b:	ásvāvad yātam aśvinā				
lLlC	LcL	0010001	3	2	0.0009	306	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0170	2.0000		98.3		
		3.012.01a:	índrāgnī á gatam sutám				

	3.045.02d:	índro dṛḷhá+ cid ārujáḥ					
lLlCllCll	0000101		3	2	0.0009	309	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0190	2.0000		98.1		
	3.012.09a:	índrāgnī rocanā diváh					
	3.029.04a:	ílāyās tvā padé vayám					
lLlCllCll	0000100		3	3	0.0013	217	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0305	1.5000		93.9		
	3.013.06c:	śám naḥ śocā marúdvṛdho					
	3.016.03c:	túvidyumna várṣiṣṭhāsyā prajāvato					
	3.021.02d:	śréṣṭhaṃ no dhehi váriyam					
lLlCllCll	0010000		3	6	0.0026	112	1.5000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0643	2.0000		99.9		
	3.024.03a:	ágne dyumnéna jāgrve					
	3.028.01c:	prātaḥsāvé dhiyāvaso					
	3.044.02b:	súryaṃ haryánn arocayaḥ					
	3.052.01c:	índra prātár juṣasva naḥ					
	3.052.02c:	túbhyaṃ havyáni sistrate					
	3.052.04b:	prātaḥsāvé juṣasva naḥ					
lLlCllCll	0010100		3	8	0.0034	67	1.3333
1.0000	1.0000	1.0847	2.0000		99.5		
	3.027.08c:	vípro yajñāsya sādhanah					
	3.029.04d:	ágne havyāya vólhave					
	3.037.05a:	índraṃ vṛtrāya hántave					
	3.040.04c:	kṣáyam cāndrāsa índavaḥ					
	3.040.05c:	táva dyukṣāsa índavaḥ					
	3.044.05a:	índro haryántam árjunaṃ					
	3.044.05b:	vájraṃ súkraír abhívṛtam					
	3.062.09c:	sá naḥ pūṣāvitā bhuvat					
lLlCllCll	0000000		3	2	0.0009	374	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0170	2.0000		98.3		
	3.041.01c:	háribhyaṃ yāhi adrivaḥ					
	3.062.17c:	drāghīṣṭhābhiḥ śucivratā					
lLlCllCll	0000001		3	1	0.0004	733	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000		100.0		
	3.051.12a:	prá te aśnotu kukṣiyóḥ					
lLlCllCll	0010100		4	2	0.0009	277	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0140	2.0000		98.6		
	4.007.02b:	bhúvad devāsya cétanam					
	4.055.10c:	índro no rádhasá gamat					
lLlCllCll	0010000		4	5	0.0022	115	1.6667
1.0000	1.0000	1.0559	1.6667		100.0		
	4.030.02b:	vísavā cakréva vāvṛtuḥ					
	4.030.17c:	índro vidvám apārayat					
	4.032.05a:	sá naś citrábhir adrivo					
	4.047.01a:	váyo súkró ayāmi te					
	4.047.03d:	á yātaṃ sómapītaye					
lLlCllCll	0000100		4	4	0.0018	150	1.3333
1.0000	1.0000	1.0430	2.0000		99.8		
	4.030.14c:	ávāhann indra sámbaram					

	4.030.16b:	pārāvṛktaṃ śatákratuḥ					
	4.031.02b:	mámhiṣṭho matsad ándhasaḥ					
	4.032.02a:	bhṛmiś cid ghāsi tútujir					
lLlCllCll	0000000		4	3	0.0013	225	1.5000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0305	1.5000		100.0		
	4.032.14c:	sómānām indra somapāḥ					
	4.037.05c:	índrasvantaṃ havāmahe					
	4.037.07a:	ví no vājā ṛbhukṣaṇaḥ					
lLlCllCll	0010001		4	1	0.0004	837	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000		100.0		
	4.056.07b:	tárantī pípratī ṛtám					
lLlCllCll	0010001		5	8	0.0028	70	1.3333
1.0000	1.0000	1.0563	1.6000		99.8		
	5.005.11c:	sváhā devébhiyo havíḥ					
	5.023.03c:	hótāraṃ sádmasu priyám					
	5.027.04d:	dádan medhám ṛtāyaté					
	5.052.02b:	sákhāyaḥ sánti dhṛṣṇuyá					
	5.052.04b:	stómaṃ yajñám ca dhṛṣṇuyá					
	5.052.14a:	ácha rṣe mārutaṃ gaṇám					
	5.056.02a:	yáthā cin mányase hṛdá					
	5.061.09b:	práti śyāvāya vartaṇím					
lLlCllCll	0000100		5	12	0.0042	24	1.3333
1.0000	1.0909	1.0870	1.5000		99.5		
	5.006.06b:	víśvam puṣyanti vāriyam					
	5.013.05a:	tvám agne vājasátamaṃ					
	5.013.05b:	víprā vardhanti súṣṭutam					
	5.019.05a:	kríḷan no raśma á bhuvaḥ					
	5.022.04d:	stómair vardhanti átrayo					
	5.038.02a:	yád ím indra śravāyiyam					
	5.039.05d:	gíro vardhanti átrayo					
	5.039.05e:	gíraḥ śumbhanti átrayaḥ					
	5.052.03b:	áti śkandanti sárvarīḥ					
	5.052.09d:	ádrim bhindanti ójaśā					
	5.082.01c:	śráyiṣṭhaṃ+ sarvadhátamaṃ					
	5.086.05c:	árhantā cit puró dadhe					
lLlCllCll	0000001		5	2	0.0007	362	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0150	2.0000		98.5		
	5.010.05b:	bhrájanto yanti dhṛṣṇuyá					
	5.021.02c:	srúcas tvā yanti ānuśák					
lLlCllCll	0000000		5	10	0.0035	47	1.2500
1.0000	1.0000	1.0715	1.4286		98.8		
	5.013.01a:	árcantas tvā havāmahe					
	5.020.03a:	hótāraṃ tvā vṛṇímahe					
	5.020.03d:	práyasvanto havāmahe					
	5.024.04a:	tám tvā śociṣṭha dīdivaḥ					
	5.026.04c:	hótāraṃ tvā vṛṇímahe					
	5.038.01c:	ádhá no viśvacarṣaṇe					
	5.064.03d:	áhiṃsānasya saścire					
	5.071.01a:	á no gantaṃ riśādasā					

	5.074.06d:	ávobhir vājinīvasū					
	5.074.08b:	yāyiṣṭho+ yātu aśvinā					
lLlCllCll	0010000		5	20	0.0070	1	2.5000
1.0000	1.1111	1.1409	1.5385		100.0		
	5.018.03a:	tām vo dīrghāyusociṣaṃ					
	5.025.03c:	āgne rāyó didīhi naḥ					
	5.035.06d:	hāvante vājasātaye					
	5.039.05c:	tāsmā u brāhmavāhase					
	5.061.04b:	māryāso bhādrajānayaḥ					
	5.061.16b:	puruścandrā riśādasah					
	5.074.09c:	arvācīnā vicetasā					
	5.074.09d:	vībhiḥ śyenéva dīyatam					
	5.075.02d:	súṣumnā síndhuvāhasā					
	5.075.05d:	ní yātho ádvayāvinam					
	5.079.01e:	sújāte áśvasūnr̥te					
	5.079.02e:	sújāte áśvasūnr̥te					
	5.079.03e:	sújāte áśvasūnr̥te					
	5.079.04e:	sújāte áśvasūnr̥te					
	5.079.05e:	sújāte áśvasūnr̥te					
	5.079.06e:	sújāte áśvasūnr̥te					
	5.079.07e:	sújāte áśvasūnr̥te					
	5.079.08e:	sújāte áśvasūnr̥te					
	5.079.09e:	sújāte áśvasūnr̥te					
	5.079.10e:	sújāte áśvasūnr̥te					
lLlCllCll	0010100		5	8	0.0028	81	1.1429
1.0000	1.0000	1.0572	1.6000		94.7		
	5.020.01c:	tām no gīrbhīḥ śravāyiyam					
	5.039.03a:	yāt te ditsú prarādhiyam					
	5.052.05a:	árhanto yé sudānavo					
	5.053.13d:	rādho viśvāyu saúbhagam					
	5.064.02d:	víśvāsu kṣāsu jóguve					
	5.073.06b:	nārā sumnéna cétasā					
	5.079.01b:	úṣo rāyé divítmatī					
	5.079.03a:	sā no adyābharādvasur					
lLlCllCll	0000101		5	2	0.0007	454	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0110	2.0000		98.9		
	5.052.12d:	úmā āsan dṛśí tviṣé					
	5.068.01c:	māhikṣatrāv ṛtām br̥hát					
lLlCllCll	0010100		6	6	0.0021	99	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0596	2.0000		74.5		
	6.002.09d:	vānā vṛścānti síkvasaḥ					
	6.015.17c:	yám an̄kūyāntam ānayann					
	6.043.03b:	māde dṛḷhā+ avāsr̥jaḥ					
	6.057.03b:	hārī anyāsya sámbr̥tā					
	6.060.08c:	índrāgnī tābhír á gatam					
	6.061.09b:	svásṛr anyā ṛtāvarī					
lLlCllCll	0010001		6	7	0.0024	86	1.4000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0655	1.7500		99.9		
	6.016.02a:	sá no mandrábhir adhvaré					

	6.016.22b:	stómaṃ yajñám ca dhr̥ṣṇuyá					
	6.046.10b:	abhipraghnánti dhr̥ṣṇuyá					
	6.055.02b:	ísānaṃ rádhaso maháḥ					
	6.059.01d:	índrāgnī jīvatho yuvám					
	6.059.07c:	má no asmín mahādhané					
	6.061.06c:	rádā pūṣéva naḥ saním					
lLlC	lC	0010000	6	10	0.0034	47	1.0000
1.0000	1.1111	1.0945	1.6667		41.3		
	6.016.03c:	ágne yajñéṣu sukrato					
	6.045.04a:	sákhāyo bráhmavāhase					
	6.046.06b:	rájan devéṣu hūmahe					
	6.048.10b:	ádabdhair áprayutvabhiḥ					
	6.052.09c:	sumṛḷiká+ bhavantu naḥ					
	6.055.05b:	svásur jārāḥ śr̥ṇotu naḥ					
	6.056.02c:	índro vṛtrāṇi jighnate					
	6.057.03c:	tábhyāṃ vṛtrāṇi jighnate					
	6.060.09c:	índrāgnī sómapítaye					
	6.075.16b:	śáraye bráhmasaṃśite					
lLlC	lC	0000001	6	3	0.0010	246	1.5000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0280	1.5000		100.0		
	6.016.05b:	dívodāsāya sunvaté					
	6.016.45a:	úd agne bhārata dyumád					
	6.045.21c:	gómadbhir gopate dhr̥ṣát					
lLlC	lC	0000100	6	10	0.0034	48	1.4286
1.0000	1.1111	1.0911	1.6667		99.8		
	6.016.15b:	sám idhe dasyuhántamam					
	6.016.19c:	dívodāsasya sátpatiḥ					
	6.016.31c:	tásmān naḥ pāhi áṃhasaḥ					
	6.042.02b:	sómebhiḥ somapátamam					
	6.045.12b:	vájāṃ indra śraváiyān					
	6.045.19b:	sákhāyaṃ kīricódanam					
	6.051.15b:	índrajyeṣṭhā abhídyavaḥ					
	6.052.08a:	yó vo devā ghṛtásnunā					
	6.053.08a:	yám pūṣan brahmacódanīm					
	6.059.04a:	yá indrāgnī sutéṣu vāṃ					
lLlC	lC	0000000	6	5	0.0017	135	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0458	2.5000		82.5		
	6.016.30c:	rákṣā ṇo brahmaṇas kave					
	6.045.10a:	tám u tvā satya somapā					
	6.047.23d:	dívodāsād asāniṣam					
	6.053.03a:	áditsantaṃ cid āghṛṇe					
	6.059.10a:	índrāgnī ukthavāhasā					
lLlC	lC	0000101	6	1	0.0003	623	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000		100.0		
	6.016.31a:	yó no agne duréva á					
lLlC	lC	0010101	6	1	0.0003	626	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000		100.0		
	6.016.35a:	gárbhe mātúḥ pitúṣ pitá					

lLlCllL	0010100	7	1	0.0003	528	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	100.0		
	7.015.05c: ágre yajñásya sócataḥ					
lLlCllL	0000100	7	4	0.0013	192	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0273	2.0000	92.2		
	7.015.06c: yájiṣṭho havyaṁhánaḥ					
	7.031.01c: sákhāyaḥ somapāvane					
	7.074.03d: mǎ no mardhiṣṭam á gatam					
	7.094.01b: índrāgnī pūrviyástutiḥ					
lLlCllL	0010000	7	4	0.0013	205	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0293	2.0000	91.6		
	7.031.06b: puroyodhás ca vṛtrahan					
	7.032.16d: nákiṣ ṭvā góṣu vṛṇvate					
	7.094.03a: mǎ pāpatváya no narā					
	7.103.01c: vácamaḥ parjányajin vitām					
lLlCllL	0000101	7	2	0.0006	384	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0140	2.0000	98.6		
	7.032.04d: háribhyāṁ yāhi óka á					
	7.066.06b: ádabdhasya vratásya yé					
lLlCllL	0010001	7	1	0.0003	760	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	100.0		
	7.055.01b: vísvā rūpāṇi āviśán					
lLlCllL	0000001	7	1	0.0003	885	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	100.0		
	7.074.04d: á devā yātam asmayú					
lLlCllL	0000000	7	2	0.0006	463	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0110	2.0000	98.9		
	7.094.06b: práyasvanto havāmahe					
	7.096.04c: sárasvantaṁ havāmahe					
lLlCllL	0010101	7	1	0.0003	974	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	100.0		
	7.094.11b: yá mandāná cid á girá					
lLlCllL	0000001	8	12	0.0020	101	1.3333
1.0000	1.0909	1.0814	1.5000	99.6		
	8.001.06a: vāsyaṁ indrāsi me pitúr					
	8.001.16d: ádhā te vaśmi suṣṭutím					
	8.006.11b: gíraḥ śumbhāmi kaṇvavát					
	8.006.30b: jyótiṣ paśyanti vāsarám					
	8.017.05a: á te siñcāmi kukṣiyór					
	8.019.36a: ádān me pauraḥkutsiyáḥ					
	8.023.23b: jyáyīṣṭhābhír+ viaśvavát					
	8.023.24b: stómebhi sthūrayūpavát					
	8.045.27b: vídāno aḥnavāyiyám					
	8.073.01a: úd írāthām ṛtāyaté					
	8.075.06c: vṛṣṇe codasva suṣṭutím					
	8.089.04b: śrávaś cit te asad bṛhát					
lLlCllL	0010000	8	66	0.0111	2	1.7838
1.1579	1.4348	1.4416	1.8333	99.9		
	8.001.07d: prá gāyatrā agāsiṣuḥ					

8.004.18d: máṃhiṣṭho vājasātaye
 8.005.14c: mádhvo rātásya dhiṣṇiyā
 8.005.25c: átriṃ síñjāram aśvinā
 8.006.01c: stómair vatsásya vāvṛdhe
 8.006.21b: káṇvā ukthéna vāvṛdhuḥ
 8.006.37c: hávante vājasātaye
 8.006.40b: vṛṣā vajrī aroravīt
 8.006.43c: káṇvā ukthéna vāvṛdhuḥ
 8.008.09c: áriprā vṛtrahantamā
 8.008.22c: púrutrā vṛtrahantamā
 8.009.21c: yád vā sumnébhir ukthiyā
 8.015.03b: éko vṛtrāṇi jighnase
 8.015.11b: éko vṛtrāṇi tośase
 8.017.08c: índro vṛtrāṇi jighnate
 8.020.07c: vāhante áhрутapsavaḥ
 8.021.01c: vāje citráṃ havāmahe
 8.021.04d: víśvebhiḥ sómapītaye
 8.022.08c: á yātaṃ sómapītaye
 8.023.10a: áchā no ángirastamaṃ
 8.024.14b: dákṣam pṛñcántam abravam
 8.026.16b: stómo dūtó huvan narā
 8.027.16d: áriṣṭaḥ sárva edhate
 8.033.01d: pári stotāra āsate
 8.034.04b: hávante vājasātaye
 8.038.01c: índrāgnī tásya bodhatam
 8.038.02c: índrāgnī tásya bodhatam
 8.038.03c: índrāgnī tásya bodhatam
 8.038.04c: índrāgnī á gataṃ narā
 8.038.05c: índrāgnī á gataṃ narā
 8.038.06c: índrāgnī á gataṃ narā
 8.038.07c: índrāgnī sómapītaye
 8.038.08c: índrāgnī sómapītaye
 8.038.09c: índrāgnī sómapītaye
 8.042.04c: nāsatyā sómapītaye
 8.042.05a: yáthā vām átrir aśvinā
 8.042.05c: nāsatyā sómapītaye
 8.042.06c: nāsatyā sómapītaye
 8.043.28c: táṃ tvā gīrbhír havāmahe
 8.044.04c: ágne súkrāsa irate
 8.044.05c: ágne havyā juṣasva naḥ
 8.044.22c: ágne sakhyásya bodhi naḥ
 8.044.25c: gíro vāśrāsa irate
 8.045.38b: áṣinvan bhúri āvayaḥ
 8.051.07d: dānaṃ devásya pṛcyate
 8.054.05d: bhágo dānāya vṛtrahan
 8.062.11c: arātívā cid adrivo
 8.067.07c: ádityā ádbhutainasaḥ
 8.067.11c: mákis tokásya no riṣat
 8.067.17a: śásvantam hí pracetasah

8.068.02b:	śácīvo víśvayā mate						
8.068.10a:	tāṃ tvā yajñēbhir īmahe						
8.068.17c:	śácā pūtákratau sanam						
8.073.04b:	kúha śyenéva petathuḥ						
8.076.05c:	índraṃ gīrbhír havāmahe						
8.080.02b:	ámṛdhro vājasātaye						
8.083.08a:	prá bhrātrtvāṃ sudānavo						
8.087.06b:	víprāso vājasātaye						
8.088.01d:	índraṃ gīrbhír navāmahe						
8.088.06d:	mámhiṣṭho vājasātaye						
8.092.14b:	ávṛtran kāmakātayaḥ						
8.092.16a:	yás te nūnáṃ śatakratav						
8.092.17a:	yás te citráśravastamo						
8.093.12a:	ádhā te apratiṣkutaṃ						
8.095.02a:	á tvā śukrá acucyavuh						
8.102.19c:	áthaitādr̥g bharāmi te						
llLcLcL	0010100	8	36	0.0060	16	1.3846	
1.0000	1.2414	1.2299	1.5652	97.5			
8.002.39c:	yé asmin kāmam áśriyan						
8.003.06d:	índre svānása° índavaḥ						
8.003.22c:	ádād rāyó vibódhanam						
8.005.13b:	yāviṣṭaṃ túyam á gatam						
8.005.25a:	yáthā cit kāṇvam āvatam						
8.006.03b:	stómair yajñásya sādhanam						
8.006.06a:	ví cid vṛtrásya dódhato						
8.006.24c:	ágre vikṣú pradídayat						
8.006.38c:	ánu svānása° índavaḥ						
8.007.19c:	várdhān kāṇvásya mánmabhiḥ						
8.012.22a:	índraṃ vṛtráya hántave						
8.013.05b:	yát tvā sunvánta īmahe						
8.015.02b:	sáho dādhāra ródasī						
8.018.17a:	té no bhadréṇa sármaṇā						
8.019.28c:	sádā devásya mártiyah						
8.026.13a:	yó vāṃ yajñēbhir ávṛto						
8.027.10b:	dévāso ásti ápiyam						
8.032.12a:	sá naḥ śakráś cid á śakad						
8.033.02d:	índra svabdíva váṃsagaḥ						
8.044.02b:	várdhasvānéna mánmanā						
8.046.05a:	dádhāno gómad ásvavat						
8.046.23a:	dása śyāvā r̥dhádrayo						
8.051.02b:	cháyānaṃ jívrim úddhitam						
8.052.06a:	yásmai tuvāṃ vaso dānáya māmhase						
8.054.03b:	dévāso gántanópa naḥ						
8.060.14b:	jámbhāso yád vitíṣṭhase						
8.062.02b:	ékaḥ kṛṣṭír ayásiyah						
8.062.02d:	víśvā jātāni ójasā						
8.067.01c:	sumṛḷikām+ abhíṣṭaye						
8.067.10c:	sumṛḷikām+ abhíṣṭaye						
8.069.09d:	índrāya bráhma údyatam						

	8.069.18a:	ánu pratnáśya ókaśaḥ					
	8.076.06a:	índram pratnéna mánmanā					
	8.082.09a:	yám te śyenāḥ padābharat					
	8.102.08b:	tváṣṭā rūpéva tákṣiyā					
	8.102.20a:	yád agne káni káni cid					
lLlCllCll	0010101		8	6	0.0010	223	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0368	1.5000		83.7		
	8.004.03a:	yáthā gauró apá kṛtám					
	8.021.13a:	abhrātrvyó anā tuvám					
	8.032.02c:	vádhīd ugró riṇánn apáḥ					
	8.044.23a:	yád agne syám ahám tuvám					
	8.065.03a:	ā tvā gīrbhír mahám urúm					
	8.077.05c:	índro brahmábhya íd vṛdhé					
lLlCllCll	0000100		8	66	0.0111	3	2.6400
1.2000	1.4348	1.4451	1.7838		100.0		
	8.005.05a:	mámhiṣṭhā vājasátamā					
	8.006.31b:	vísve vardhanti paúṃsiyam					
	8.006.36b:	hárībhyām haryatābhiyām					
	8.012.20b:	sómebhiḥ somapátamam					
	8.019.21c:	yájiṣṭham havyvāhanam					
	8.019.31b:	índhānaḥ siṣṇav á dade					
	8.024.17b:	nákiṣ ṭe pūrviyástutim					
	8.024.25b:	yénā damśiṣṭha kṛtvane					
	8.024.26b:	návyam damśiṣṭha sányase					
	8.025.12b:	áriṣyantaḥ sudānave					
	8.026.04b:	rátho yātu śrutó narā					
	8.031.04b:	ásaścantī divé-dive					
	8.032.22c:	dhénā indrāvacākaśat					
	8.039.01f:	nábhantām anyaké same					
	8.039.02f:	nábhantām anyaké same					
	8.039.03f:	nábhantām anyaké same					
	8.039.04f:	nábhantām anyaké same					
	8.039.05f:	nábhantām anyaké same					
	8.039.06f:	nábhantām anyaké same					
	8.039.07f:	nábhantām anyaké same					
	8.039.08f:	nábhantām anyaké same					
	8.039.09f:	nábhantām anyaké same					
	8.039.10f:	nábhantām anyaké same					
	8.040.01f:	nábhantām anyaké same					
	8.040.02g:	nábhantām anyaké same					
	8.040.03f:	nábhantām anyaké same					
	8.040.04f:	nábhantām anyaké same					
	8.040.05f:	nábhantām anyaké same					
	8.040.06f:	nábhantām anyaké same					
	8.040.07f:	nábhantām anyaké same					
	8.040.08d:	úhānā yanti síndhavo					
	8.040.08f:	nábhantām anyaké same					
	8.040.09f:	nábhantām anyaké same					
	8.040.10f:	nábhantām anyaké same					

8.040.11f:	nábhantām anyaké same						
8.041.01f:	nábhantām anyaké same						
8.041.02f:	nábhantām anyaké same						
8.041.03f:	nábhantām anyaké same						
8.041.04f:	nábhantām anyaké same						
8.041.05f:	nábhantām anyaké same						
8.041.06f:	nábhantām anyaké same						
8.041.07f:	nábhantām anyaké same						
8.041.08f:	nábhantām anyaké same						
8.041.09f:	nábhantām anyaké same						
8.041.10f:	nábhantām anyaké same						
8.042.04d:	nábhantām anyaké same						
8.042.05d:	nábhantām anyaké same						
8.042.06d:	nábhantām anyaké same						
8.044.20a:	ádabdhasya svadhávato						
8.045.26c:	átrādediṣṭa paúmsiyam						
8.045.39b:	hārī gr̥bhṇe sumádrathā						
8.047.02b:	ádityāso apākṛtim						
8.053.03b:	mádhvaḥ siñcantu ádrayaḥ						
8.060.03d:	víprebhiḥ śukra mánmabhiḥ						
8.066.01a:	tárobhīr vo vidádvāsum						
8.069.03b:	sómaṃ śrīṇanti pṛśnayaḥ						
8.073.06b:	nēdiṣṭhaṃ yāmi āpiyam						
8.074.06c:	júhvānāso yatásrucaḥ						
8.074.08c:	táyā vardhasva súṣṭutaḥ						
8.074.15c:	ném āpo aśvadātarāḥ						
8.074.15d:	śáviṣṭhād asti mártiyaḥ						
8.075.02b:	áchā voco vidúṣṭaraḥ						
8.075.10a:	námas te agna ójase						
8.075.12b:	pārā varg bhārabhṛd yathā						
8.077.03c:	právr̥ddho dasyuhābhavat						
8.083.09b:	índrajyeṣṭhā abhídyaḥ						
llLcLcL	0000000	8	28	0.0047	36	1.6471	
1.0000	1.1667	1.1809	1.5556	100.0			
8.005.28b:	híraṇyābhīśum aśvinā						
8.007.21b:	ṣtómebhir vṛktabarhiṣaḥ						
8.008.07b:	á no gantaṃ suvarvidā						
8.008.10b:	átiṣṭhad vājinīvasū						
8.008.17a:	á no gantaṃ risādasā						
8.008.22b:	gíro vardhantu aśvinā						
8.020.01b:	prásthāvāno mápa sthātā samanyavaḥ						
8.020.21a:	gāvaś cid ghā samanyavaḥ						
8.022.05b:	híraṇyābhīśur aśvinā						
8.026.05b:	á manyethāṃ vṛṣaṇvasū						
8.027.15a:	prá vaḥ śamsāmi adruhaḥ						
8.033.15d:	mádāya dyukṣa somapāḥ						
8.035.04d:	íṣaṃ no voḷham aśvinā						
8.035.05d:	íṣaṃ no voḷham aśvinā						
8.035.06d:	íṣaṃ no voḷham aśvinā						

8.035.10d:	úrjaṃ no dhattam aśvinā						
8.035.11d:	úrjaṃ no dhattam aśvinā						
8.035.12d:	úrjaṃ no dhattam aśvinā						
8.046.19d:	jyáyiṣṭhaṃ+ codayanmate						
8.052.04b:	vāje vājiñ chatakrato						
8.060.01b:	hótāraṃ tvā vṛṇīmahe						
8.060.20a:	mā no rākṣa á veśid āghṛṇīvaso						
8.065.06b:	práyasvanto havāmahe						
8.066.06b:	mádāya dyukṣa somapāḥ						
8.083.05b:	ísānāśo riśādasah						
8.092.11b:	árvadbhiḥ śakra godare						
8.092.18b:	tvádattaḥ satya somapāḥ						
8.095.06d:	síṣāsanto vanāmahe						
lLlCllCll	0000101	8	13	0.0022	98	1.0000	
1.0000	1.0833	1.0839	1.4444	37.1			
8.005.37c:	yáthā cic caidiyāḥ kaśúḥ						
8.008.11d:	ásamsīt kāviyāḥ kavíḥ						
8.009.16c:	ví āvar devi á matīm						
8.021.11a:	tváyā ha svid yujá vayám						
8.023.05b:	stávāno deviyā kṛpá						
8.027.20d:	úpa stheyāma mādhyā á						
8.033.03a:	kāṇvebhir dhṛṣṇav á dhṛṣád						
8.046.22b:	úṣṭrānāṃ viṃśatīm śatá						
8.047.01c:	yám ādityā abhí druhó						
8.077.06a:	nír āvidhyad giríbhya á						
8.079.07c:	bhāvā naḥ soma sám hṛdé						
8.083.05c:	ném ādityā aghásya yát						
8.102.03a:	tváyā ha svid yujá vayám						
lLlCllCll	0010001	8	23	0.0039	49	1.0952	
1.0000	1.1500	1.1492	1.5333	42.2			
8.006.38a:	ánu tvā ródasī ubhé						
8.012.11a:	gárbho yajñásya devayúḥ						
8.013.13b:	háve madhyáṃdine diváḥ						
8.015.13b:	víśvā rūpāṇi āviśán						
8.019.25a:	yád agne mártiyas tuvám						
8.027.19d:	yád vā madhyáṃdine diváḥ						
8.027.22c:	ásyāma tát ādityā júhvato havír						
8.028.03a:	té no gopá apāciyás						
8.040.01b:	sáhantā dáśatho rayím						
8.041.09a:	yásya śvetá vicakṣañá						
8.043.24b:	ádhyakṣaṃ dhármaṇām imám						
8.044.08c:	ágne yajñám naya rtuthá						
8.047.13b:	dévāso ásti duṣkṛtám						
8.050.06b:	víbhūtiṃ rádhaso maháḥ						
8.052.01b:	sómaṃ śakrápibaḥ sutám						
8.063.08c:	právaś cakrásya vartaním						
8.067.06a:	yád vaḥ śrāntāya sunvaté						
8.072.06b:	ásvāvad yójanam bṛhád						
8.075.11b:	ágne saṃvéṣiṣo rayím						

	8.075.12a:	má no asmín mahādhané					
	8.076.11a:	ánu tvā ródasī ubhé					
	8.078.09b:	kámo gavyúr hiraṇyayúḥ					
	8.095.03b:	índra śyenábhṛtaṃ sutám					
lLlC	0000100		9	22	0.0059	18	1.1000
1.0000	1.1579	1.1715	1.5714		35.1		
	9.001.03b:	mámhiṣṭho vṛtrahántamaḥ					
	9.002.04b:	ápo arṣanti síndhavaḥ					
	9.026.05b:	háriṃ hinvanti ádrībhiḥ					
	9.030.05b:	háriṃ hinvanti ádrībhiḥ					
	9.031.02b:	bhávendo dyumnavárdhanaḥ					
	9.032.02b:	háriṃ hinvanti ádrībhiḥ					
	9.033.03c:	sómā arṣanti víṣṇave					
	9.038.02b:	háriṃ hinvanti ádrībhiḥ					
	9.039.06b:	háriṃ hinvanti ádrībhiḥ					
	9.046.03c:	índraṃ vardhanti kármabhiḥ					
	9.047.02b:	cétante dasyutárhaṇā					
	9.050.03b:	háriṃ hinvanti ádrībhiḥ					
	9.061.02b:	dívodāsāya sámbaram					
	9.062.17b:	rátthe yuñjanti yátave					
	9.064.22a:	índrāyendo marútvate					
	9.065.19a:	árṣā soma dyumáttamo					
	9.066.13b:	ápo arṣanti síndhavaḥ					
	9.066.14b:	íyakṣantas tuvótayaḥ					
	9.066.26c:	háriścandro marúdganaḥ					
	9.067.26b:	várṣiṣṭhaiḥ soma dhámabhiḥ					
	9.099.01b:	dhánus tanvanti paúṃsiyam					
	9.106.04a:	prá dhanvā soma jágrvir					
lLlC	0010000		9	19	0.0051	29	1.2667
1.0000	1.1176	1.1585	1.7273		92.7		
	9.001.10b:	víśvā vṛtrāṇi jighnate					
	9.005.07b:	hótārā daíviyā huve					
	9.009.06c:	krívir devír atarpayat					
	9.010.03b:	sómāso góbhira añjate					
	9.010.07a:	samícínāsa āsate					
	9.011.03c:	śám rājann óśadhībhiyaḥ					
	9.013.03a:	pávante vájasātaye					
	9.013.06b:	ásṛgraṃ vájasātaye					
	9.035.03a:	tváyā vīréṇa vīravo					
	9.042.03b:	pávante vájaśātaye					
	9.042.04c:	krándan devám ajījanat					
	9.045.04c:	índur devéṣu patyate					
	9.061.13c:	índuṃ devá ayāsiṣuḥ					
	9.062.09b:	svádiṣṭho ángirobhiyaḥ					
	9.065.16a:	rājā medhábhir iyate					
	9.098.06b:	svásāro ádrisaṃhatam					
	9.098.09a:	sá vām yajñéṣu mānavī					
	9.105.05b:	índo devápsarastamaḥ					
	9.107.06d:	mádhvā yajñám mimikṣa naḥ					

lLlCllL	0010100		9	26	0.0069	10	1.3000
1.0000	1.1818	1.2070	1.6250		90.8		
	9.010.04a:	pári svānāsa°	índavo				
	9.013.05b:	pāvantām ā	suvīriyam				
	9.015.03c:	yādī tuñjānti	bhūrṇayaḥ				
	9.017.01b:	ghnānto vṛtrāṇi	bhūrṇayaḥ				
	9.020.07c:	dádhat stotré	suvīriyam				
	9.036.05b:	sómo divyāni	pārthivā				
	9.044.05c:	sómo devēṣu ā	yamat				
	9.045.06b:	yáyā pītó	vicákṣase				
	9.045.06c:	índo stotré	suvīriyam				
	9.048.01a:	tām tvā ṛmṇāni	bíbhrataṃ				
	9.052.01a:	pári dyukṣāḥ	sanádrayir				
	9.052.02a:	táva pratnébhir	ádhvabhir				
	9.061.22b:	índraṃ vṛtrāya	hántave				
	9.061.30a:	yá te bhīmāni	áyudhā				
	9.062.30c:	dádhat stotré	suvīriyam				
	9.063.25b:	sómāḥ śukrāsa	índavaḥ				
	9.064.06b:	sómā divyāni	pārthivā				
	9.064.16a:	prá hinvánāsa	índavo				
	9.065.08b:	háriṃ hinvānti	ádribhiḥ				
	9.065.24b:	pāvantām ā	suvīriyam				
	9.066.27c:	dádhat stotré	suvīriyam				
	9.067.19a:	grāvṇā tunnó	abhíṣṭutaḥ				
	9.067.19c:	dádhat stotré	suvīriyam				
	9.099.02d:	háriṃ hinvānti	yátave				
	9.101.13a:	prá sunvánāṣya	ándhaso				
	9.111.03d:	ágmān ukthāni	paúṃsiyā				
lLlCllL	0000000		9	3	0.0008	300	1.5000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0230	1.5000		100.0		
	9.011.01a:	úpāsmāi gāyatā	naraḥ				
	9.011.02b:	átharvāṇo aśísrayuḥ					
	9.061.11c:	síṣāsanto	vanāmahe				
lLlCllL	0010001		9	16	0.0043	43	1.2308
1.0000	1.1429	1.1315	1.6000		92.6		
	9.014.02c:	pariṣkrṇvānti	dharṇasím				
	9.017.06c:	dádhanāś cákṣasi	priyám				
	9.025.04a:	víśvā rūpāṇi	āviśán				
	9.026.01c:	víprāso áṅviyā	dhiyá				
	9.028.02b:	sómo devébhiyaḥ	sutáḥ				
	9.029.06a:	ā indo pārthivaṃ	rayiṃ				
	9.041.04c:	áśvāvad vājavat	sutáḥ				
	9.042.06b:	áśvāvad vājavat	sutáḥ				
	9.050.01b:	síndhor ūrmér	iva svanáḥ				
	9.051.01a:	ádhvāryo ádribhiḥ	sutám				
	9.100.04d:	vāraṃ vājīva	sānasíḥ				
	9.101.02b:	pariprasyánda	sutáḥ				
	9.101.03b:	sómaṃ viśváciyā	dhiyá				
	9.101.07d:	ví akhyad ródasī	ubhé				

9.101.16d:	índrasyābhy èti niṣkṛtām					
9.107.05d:	nṛbhir dhūtó vicakṣaṇáh					
lLlCllCll	0010101	9	3	0.0008	317	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0300	3.0000	94.3		
9.026.02c:	índuṃ dhartāram á diváh					
9.064.30b:	saṃjāgmānó diváh kavíḥ					
9.112.01c:	tákṣā riṣṭām rutám bhiṣág					
lLlCllCll	0000001	9	4	0.0011	241	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0353	2.0000	90.2		
9.032.03b:	vísvasyāvīvaśan matím					
9.046.04c:	góbhiḥ śrīṇīta matsarám					
9.048.03b:	rājānaṃ suktrato diváh					
9.101.08c:	sómāsaḥ kṛṇvate patháh					
lLlCllCll	0000101	9	3	0.0008	329	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0190	1.5000	96.2		
9.046.03b:	prāyasvantaḥ camú sutáh					
9.061.16c:	jyótir vaiśvānarám bṛhát					
9.114.04a:	yát te rājañ chrtām havís					
lLlCllCll	0010000	10	29	0.0042	22	1.9333
1.0000	1.1154	1.1030	1.3810	100.0		
10.009.09a:	ápo adyānv acāriṣaṃ					
10.025.07e:	mā no duḥśāṃsa īsatā					
10.033.04b:	rājānaṃ trāsadasyavam					
10.036.02d:	tád devānām ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe					
10.036.03d:	tád devānām ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe					
10.036.04d:	tád devānām ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe					
10.036.05d:	tád devānām ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe					
10.036.06d:	tád devānām ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe					
10.036.07d:	tád devānām ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe					
10.036.08d:	tád devānām ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe					
10.036.09d:	tád devānām ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe					
10.036.10d:	tád devānām ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe					
10.036.11d:	tád devānām ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe					
10.036.12d:	tád devānām ávo adyá vṛṇīmahe					
10.062.06c:	nāvagvo nú dāsagvo ángirastamo					
10.062.06d:	sácā devéṣu maṃhate					
10.062.10b:	smáddiṣṭī gópariṇasā					
10.062.10c:	yádus turváś ca māmahe					
10.085.28d:	pátir bandhéṣu badhyate					
10.090.14d:	táthā lokāñ akalpayan					
10.097.08b:	gávo goṣṭhád iverate					
10.097.21c:	sárvāḥ saṃgátya vīrudho					
10.143.06b:	mámhiṣṭhā víśvavedasā					
10.146.02d:	araṇyānír mahīyate					
10.158.03c:	čákṣur dhātá dadhātu naḥ					
10.161.05a:	áhārṣaṃ tvāvidaṃ tuvā					
10.166.05c:	á vo mūrdhānam akramīm					
10.176.03b:	hótā yajñāya nīyate					
10.184.02d:	á dhattām púṣkarasrajā					

llLcLcL	0010100		10	39	0.0056	7	3.0000
1.0000	1.1143	1.1360	1.3929		100.0		
	10.014.14c:	sá no devéṣu á yamad					
	10.021.05c:	bhúvad dūtó vivásvato					
	10.057.02b:	tántur devéṣu átataḥ					
	10.085.03b:	yát sampiṃṣánti óṣadhim					
	10.085.05d:	sámānām māsa ákr̥tiḥ					
	10.085.06b:	nārāśaṃsí niócanī					
	10.086.01e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.02e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.03e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.04e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.05e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.06e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.07e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.08e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.09e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.10e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.11e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.12e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.13e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.14e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.15e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.16e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.17c:	séd íše yásya rámbate					
	10.086.17e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.18e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.19e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.20e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.21e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.22e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.086.23e:	víśvasmād índra úttaraḥ					
	10.090.01b:	sahasrākṣáḥ sahasrapāt					
	10.097.09b:	átho yūyám stha níṣkr̥tiḥ					
	10.133.05b:	sánābhir yás ca níṣṭiyah					
	10.136.04b:	víśvā rūpāvacākaśat					
	10.136.06d:	sákhā svādúr madíntamaḥ					
	10.153.05b:	víśvā jātāni ójasā					
	10.154.05b:	yé gopāyánti sūriyam					
	10.158.04b:	cákṣur vikhyaí tanúbhiyah					
	10.191.02d:	saṃjānāná upāsate					
llLcLcL	0000100		10	10	0.0014	169	1.1111
1.0000	1.0000	1.0326	1.2500		97.5		
	10.014.15c:	idám náma řṣibhyaḥ pūrvajébhiyah					
	10.024.02e:	śréṣṭham no dhehi vāriyam					
	10.085.04d:	ná te aśnāti pārhivaḥ					
	10.085.11b:	gāvau te sāmanāv itaḥ					
	10.086.18b:	pārasvantaḥ hatám vidat					
	10.087.24d:	ádabdham vipra mánmabhiḥ					

	10.097.15d:	tá no muñcantu ámhasaḥ					
	10.126.01b:	dévāso aṣṭa mártiyam					
	10.158.04a:	cákṣur no dhehi cákṣuṣe					
	10.163.05b:	lómabhyas te nakhébhiyaḥ					
llLcLcL	0000000		10	5	0.0007	353	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0183	1.6667		93.0		
	10.019.01c:	ágniṣomā punarvasū					
	10.021.01b:	hótāraṃ tvā vṛṇīmahe					
	10.093.07d:	párijmā viśvavedasaḥ					
	10.155.04b:	úro maṇḍūradhāṇikīḥ					
	10.164.04a:	yád indra brahmaṇas pate					
llLcLcL	0010001		10	8	0.0012	224	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0270	1.6000		82.6		
	10.021.04a:	yám agne mányase rayím					
	10.022.01d:	gúhā vā cárkrṣe girá					
	10.032.04c:	mātá yán mántur yūthásya pūrviyá					
	10.086.16c:	séd íse yásya romaśám					
	10.101.04c:	dhírā devéṣu sumnayá					
	10.140.05b:	kṣáyantaṃ rádhaso maháḥ					
	10.155.03b:	síndhoḥ pāré apūruśám					
	10.159.03d:	pátyau me ślóka uttamáḥ					
llLcLcL	0000001		10	2	0.0003	812	1.0000
1.0000	1.0000	1.0160	2.0000		98.4		
	10.097.16d:	sárvasmād devakilbiṣát					
	10.137.06d:	tás te kṛṇvantu bheṣajám					

11 positions from the Hymn to Nikkal in the Rig Veda and the 11-syllable-long Sapphic verse.

11 positions from the Hymn to Nikkal, counted back from Part 3.
Pattern “lllcllclcll”:

- Original : 207/21035 verses
- Permutations: min=3, max=24, mean=11.24, median=11.0, std=3.49
- Percentile rank of real text: 100.0th

11-syllables Sapphic verse.

Pattern “lclllclcll”:

- Original : 72/21035 verses
- Permutations: min=7, max=36, mean=17.20, median=17.0, std=4.33
- Percentile rank of real text: 100.0th

Sappho's verse:

"long - short - long - long - long - **caesura** - short - short - long - short - long - long"
is an abbreviation of the hymn to Nikkal. The **caesura** replaces: "short - long - long" in Nikkal's hymn.

Alcaeus's verse:

"**short** - long - short - long - long - long - short - long - long
long - short - short - long - short - short - long - short - long - long"
expands the rhythm in Nikkal's hymn by adding the bold marked positions in the beginning of each half-line. The rest is unchanged.

Thus, it can be concluded that both Sappho and Alcaeus retake the rhythm of the Hymn to Nikkal. Sappho shortens it. Alcaeus lengthens it. The full verse of the Hymn to Nikkal is found in between the two.

In Rome, Horace continues utilizing these meters unchanged.
Authentic example of Sapphic stanza by Horace:

O Venus regina Cnidi Paphique
Sperne dilectam Cypron et vocanti
Ture te multo glykerai decoram
Transfer in aedem.

Fervidus tecum puer et solutis
Gratiae zonis properentque Nymphae
Et parum comis sine te Juventas
Mercuriusque.

Authentic example by Sappho:

Ἄσπερες μὲν ἀμφὶ κάλαν σελάνναν
ἄψ ἀπυκρύπτοισι φάεννον εἶδος,
ὄπποτα πλήθοισα μάλιστα λάμπη
[ἀργυρίαν γᾶν]

Could something like this have been played with Hurrian music? The accent patterns are repeated over all three lines, and they also match with the Hymn to Nikkal up to the last word of each line, which has the accent a position earlier in Sappho's verses. With Hurrian music following the rhythm and accent, Sappho's verse could have worked for example like:

ti-ti-mi-šar-te || zi-ir-te | ša-ah-re || ša-aš-ša-te || ir-bu-te || um-bu-be | ša-aš-ša-te | ir-bu-te ||
ki-it-me | kab-li-te || ki-it-me ||||

Related articles (selected):

The Rhythm that United Continents, Dan C. Baciú, 2025 <https://bit.ly/Nikkal>
In the Beginning was Music, Dan C. Baciú, 2025 DOI:10.20944/preprints202506.1669.v2
The Rig Veda, Music, and Moses, Dan C. Baciú, 2025